

BAHIR DAR UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF AGRICULTURE AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES
DEPARTMENT OF HORTICULTURE
Ph.D. PROGRAM IN HORTICULTURE

PRODUCTION AND POSTHARVEST OPTIMIZATION OF ONION (*Allium cepa* L.)
IN NORTHWEST ETHIOPIA

Ph.D. DISSERTATION

BY

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JAN, 2025
BAHIRDAR, ETHIOPIA

**PRODUCTION AND POSTHARVEST OPTIMIZATION OF ONION (*Allium cepa*
L.) IN NORTHWEST ETHIOPIA**

Ph.D. Dissertation

By

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**Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for the Degree of
Philosophy of Doctor (Ph.D.) in Horticulture**

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**Jan 2025
Bahir Dar, Ethiopia**

DISSERTATION APPROVAL SHEET

As a member of the board of examiners of degree of Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Horticulture open defence examination, we have read and evaluated this dissertation prepared by Mrs. Yebirzaf Yeshiwas Melese entitled “**Production and Postharvest Optimization of Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) in Northwest Ethiopia**”. We here by certified that the dissertation is accepted for fulfilling the requirements for the award of degree of Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Horticulture.

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that this Dissertation entitled “**Production and Postharvest Optimization of Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) in Northwest Ethiopia**” submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Philosophy of Doctor in “Horticulture” to the Graduate Program of College of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Bahir Dar University by Mrs. Yebirzaf Yeshiwas Melese (ID. No. BDU1300529) is an authentic work carried out by her under our guidance. The matter embodied in this Dissertation work has not been submitted earlier for award of any degree or diploma to the best of our knowledge and belief.

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Above all, I thank the Almighty God and the Saint Virgin Mary for their compassionate help in all aspects of my life.

This thesis would not have been possible without the constant support and encouragement of my supervisors, Professor Melkamu Alemayehu and Professor Enyew Adgo, not to mention their advice and unsurpassed knowledge. I would like to express my sincere and heartfelt gratitude for their constant encouragement, parental affection, keen interest and pain staking efforts taken during the entire course of investigation right from the selection of topic up to the final write-up of my thesis. The past years have brought unexpected challenges, including periods of upheaval due to the challenging times following my son's passing and war, which tested my resilience on both professional and personal fronts. In these trying times, your unwavering support and understanding provided me with the strength and encouragement needed to persevere.

I would like also to express my sincere gratitude to Health Food Africa Project (FSL-BD) in Bahir Dar University financed by European Commission; Horizon 2020 Grant Number 862740 kindly granted the PhD research costs which enabled to successfully and timely accomplish of the research works. I acknowledge Debre Markos University for allowing me to study my PhD and for the financial supports. I also would like to thank Bahir Dar University, College of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences for accepting me as a PhD student and for hosting me, for the academic and technical support.

I wish to express my gratitude to Woramit Fruit and Vegetable Research sub center, Fogera Rice Research and Training Center, Bahir Dar University Horticulture and Post-harvest laboratory, Soil Science Laboratory, and Bahir Dar Meteorology Station. All these organizations kindly provided me with the necessary facilities and support for my research.

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to Dr. Hussen Beshir for his invaluable assistance with the statistical analysis in this study. I wish to express my gratitude to Mr. Tilahun (Mecha Agricultural Office), Mr. Yibeltal from Bahir Dar Zuria district and Mr. Demes from Fogera district Agricultural office for their unreserved support on representative survey site selection, and providing preliminary information required for the study. My thanks also go to the several *Woreda* and *Kebele* agricultural experts. I gratefully acknowledge the farmers, whole-sellers, retailers and consumers who graciously welcomed me into their homes and fields, and spent their valuable time in sharing me their knowledge and expertise.

My sincere thanks also go to Dr. Tadele Amare from Adet Agricultural Research Centre (AARC) for giving me Triple Super Phosphate (TSP) fertilizer for the required experiments in this study. I would like to thank also Mr. Alemu Worku from SNV by providing me required inputs for the study. I would like to thank also Dr. Minale Wondie from Amhara Agricultural Research Institute providing me GPS coordinate data of experimental sites.

I am thankful to, Mr. Yilkal Aschalew, Mr. Melese Wale, Mr. Adam Abebe, Mss. Tiblest Molla, and Mr. Minuyelt Jember for their assistance and encouragement during my course of study. I also extend special thanks to Mr. Mulat Getaneh Mr. Dessie Getahun, Mr. Dessalgn, Mr. Maru Adugna and Mr. Getachew Tigebew for their unreserved support of research work. My heartfelt thanks are also addressed to HFA staffs Mrs. Banchigizy Habesha, Mr. Kefale Berhanu, Mr. Abreham Asmare, Mr Getachew Dagnaw, Mr. Amsalu Atanaw, and Mr. Yayehalem Wassihun.

I show my gratefulness to all staffs of the Department of Horticulture for generous help, kind co-operation and steady encouragement. I owe my most sincere gratitude to my friends, Mastewal Gojjam and Yezihalem Getaneh for augmented moral support.

I would like to address my sincere thanks to Dr. Habtamu Tegen, Dr. Dereje Ademe, and Dr. Yayeh Bitew for their unreserved help throughout this work. Many people helped me in data collection, for which I would like to thank them wholeheartedly. Especially Sefinew Shibabaw, Abaynew Melese, Demelash Eshetie, Melkamu Wudu, Mekonnen Gebru, Mamaru Shitaw and Fentahun Assefa deserve my great thanks.

I would like to express my profound gratefulness to my dear parents, my mother Yerom Getahun, my father Yeshiwas Melese and my sisters (Dejyitenu Yeshiwas, Debrework Yesshiwas, Masresha Yeshiwas, Etsubdink Yeshiwas, Banchiamlk Yeshiwas, Woynesht Yeshiwas, Bethelhem Tadele, Abeba Tadele) and brothers (Muluken Yeshiwas, Tilahun Kassahun, Lijalem Kassahun, Hayleyesus Amssaya, Sewalem Amssaya Gebrie Admas, Abebaw Muluneh, Mezgeb Tamir) who have showered me with their love and have been source of constant encouragement throughout my educational career. My thanks are also due to my in-laws, Ato Tadele Agidew and W/o Getenesh Kebede and their families.

My heartfelt thanks are extended to my beloved family my husband, Assistant professor Esubalew Tadele, my sons, Nathan Esubalew and Nahom Esubalew, my new born daughter Rediet Esubalew for their love and moral support, and cooperation, always with me and sharing responsibility to keeping up the family.

DEDICATION

I lost my son Nahom Esubalew (Biba), while I am working my research work. I am sorry that my son Nahom, you did not get to see my completed dissertation. Nahom (Biba) was not only a beacon of joy but also a constant source of inspiration, reminding me of the enduring power of love, resilience, and the pursuit of knowledge. I'm not really sure what to say. I'm lost for words more than "I dedicate this dissertation to the cherished memory of my beloved son, Nahom who departed this world too soon (April 25/2009 E.C- Pagume 03/2014 E.C). In dedicating this work to his memory, I honour the indelible mark he left on my heart and the enduring influence he had on my academic journey.

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
CSA	Central Statistical Agency
CIMMYT	Center for Improvement of Maize and Wheat
DLS	Diffused light storage
DMRT	Duncan Multiple Range Test
EIAR	Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research
FAO	Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations
FAOSTAT	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations Statistics
LSD	Least Significant Difference
MoARD	Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development
N	Newton
NGOs	None Governmental Organization
RCBD	Randomized Complete Block Design
SAS	Statistical Analysis System
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Sciences
SE	Standard Error
TSS	Total Soluble Solid
TSP	Triple Super Phosphate
t	Ton

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Contents	Page
DISSERTATION APPROVAL SHEET	II
DECLARATION.....	III
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	IV
DEDICATION.....	VII
ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS	VIII
LIST OF TABLES.....	XIII
LIST OF APPENDIX TABLES	XIX
LIST OF APPENDIX FIGURES	XX
GENERAL ABSTRACT	1
CHAPTER 1: GENERAL INTRODUCTION.....	4
1.1. GENERAL BACKGROUND AND JUSTIFICATION	4
1.2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM	8
1.3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY.....	10
<i>1.3.1. General objective</i>	10
<i>1.3.2 Specific objectives</i>	10
CHAPTER 2. GENERAL MATERIALS AND METHODS	13
2.1. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA.....	13
2.2. EXPERIMENTAL MATERIALS	16
2.3. TREATMENTS AND EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN.....	17
2.4. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES	18
2.5. DATA COLLECTION	19
2.6. DATA ANALYSIS	23
CHAPTER 3: POTENTIAL, CONSTRAINTS AND DETERMINANTS OF ONION PRODUCTION AND POSTHARVEST MANAGEMENT IN THE NORTHWEST ETHIOPIAN SUPPLY CHAIN.....	24
3.1. THE RISE AND FALL OF ONION PRODUCTION; ITS MULTIPLE CONSTRAINTS ON PRE- HARVEST AND POST-HARVEST MANAGEMENT ISSUES ALONG THE SUPPLY CHAIN IN NORTHWEST ETHIOPIA	24
<i>3.3.1. Introduction</i>	25
<i>3.3.2. Methodology</i>	28
<i>3.1.3. Results and discussion</i>	33
<i>3.1.5. Conclusions and recommendations</i>	68

3.2. STRATEGIC MAPPING OF ONION SUPPLY CHAINS: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF PRODUCTION AND POST-HARVEST PROCESSES IN NORTHWEST ETHIOPIA.....	70
3.2.1. Introduction	71
3.2.2. Review of related literature	72
3.2.3. Methodology	80
3.2.4. Results and discussion	83
3.2.5. Conclusions and Recommendations	95
CHAPTER 4. ENHANCING BULB YIELD THROUGH NITROGEN FERTILIZATION AND THE USE OF HYBRID ONION VARIETIES IN NORTHWEST ETHIOPIA ...	96
4.1. INTRODUCTION	97
4.2. MATERIALS AND METHODS	99
4.2.1. Description of the study area	99
4.2.2. Experimental materials	99
4.2.3. Treatments and experimental design	100
4.2.4. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES	100
4.2.5. Data Collection	101
4.2.6. Data Analysis	101
4.2.7. Partial Budget Analysis	102
4.3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	102
4.3.1. Effect of nitrogen fertilizer rate on the phenology and vegetative traits of onion varieties	102
4.3.2. Influences of variety and nitrogen fertilizer on bulb yield and quality	105
Total dry bulb yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$)	111
4.3.3. Influence of nitrogen fertilizer on the bulb quality of onion varieties	112
4.3.4. ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF ONION AS INFLUENCED BY VARIETY AND NITROGEN FERTILIZER RATE	114
4.4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	115
CHAPTER 5: INFLUENCE OF CULTIVAR AND PLANT DENSITY ON THE GROWTH, YIELD AND QUALITY OF ONION (<i>ALLIUM CEPA</i>).....	117
5.1. INTRODUCTION	118
5.1.1. Hypotheses testing	120
5.2. MATERIALS AND METHODS	120
5.2.1. Description of the Study Area	120
5.2.2. Experimental Materials	120

5.2.3 <i>Experimental treatments and design</i>	121
5.2.4. <i>Experimental procedures and agronomic management</i>	121
5.2.5. <i>Data Collection</i>	122
5.2.6. <i>Data Analysis</i>	122
5.3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	122
5.3.1. <i>Effects of plant density on the phenology and vegetative traits of onion cultivars</i>	122
5.3.2. EFFECTS OF PLANT POPULATION ON BULB YIELD AND YIELD-RELATED TRAITS. 127	
5.3.3. <i>Marketable bulb yield distribution</i>	136
5.3.4. <i>Quality parameters of onion</i>	139
5.4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	141
CHAPTER 6: EFFECTS OF HYBRID VARIETIES, NITROGEN FERTILIZER, AND	
PACKAGING ON POST-HARVEST QUALITY OF ONION IN NORTHWEST	
ETHIOPIA	142
6.1. INTRODUCTION	143
6.2. MATERIALS AND METHODS	144
6.2.1. <i>Description of the study area</i>	144
6.2.2. <i>Sources of bulbs for the experiment</i>	145
6.2.3 <i>Experimental design and treatments</i>	146
6.2.4. <i>Experimental procedures</i>	146
6.2.5. <i>Data collection</i>	146
6.2.6. <i>Data analysis</i>	147
6.3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	147
6.4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	162
CHAPTER 7: INFLUENCE OF PRE-HARVEST TREATMENTS ON POST HARVEST	
QUALITY AND SHELF LIFE OF ONION (<i>ALLIUM CEPA</i> L.) VARIETIES IN	
BAHIR DAR ZURIA DISTRICT, AMHARA REGION.....	164
7.1. INTRODUCTION	165
7.2. MATERIALS AND METHODS	167
7.2.1. <i>Description of the study area and the storage structure</i>	167
7.2.1.1. <i>Temperature and relative humidity in onion storage structure</i>	168
7.2.2. <i>Sources of bulbs and their preparation for storage</i>	168
7.2.3 <i>Treatments and experimental design</i>	170
7.2.5. <i>Data collection</i>	170
7.2.7. <i>Data analysis</i>	170
7.3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	170
7.4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	185

CHAPTER 8: GENERAL SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS RECOMMENDATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS	186
8.1. SUMMARY/ SYNTHESIS	186
8.2. CONCLUSIONS.....	186
8.3. RECOMMENDATIONS.....	188
8.4. FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS.....	189
REFERENCES.....	190
APPENDIX	218
BIOGRAPHY OF THE AUTHOR	243

LIST OF TABLES

Tables	Page
Table 2.1. Altitudes, temperature, rainfall and soil types at specific experimental sites	14
Table 2.2. Status of nutrients in the experimental locations before planting in 2021/2022 irrigation season.....	15
Table 2.3. List of varieties and their descriptions	17
Table 2.4. Summary of treatments and designs used in the study	17
Table 3.1.1. Sample distribution in the selected districts and kebeles	32
Table 3.1.2. Socio-demographic characteristics of onion supply chain actors in Mecha, Fogera, and Bahir Dar Zuria districts	34
Table 3.1.3. Household age and size of major actors of onion value chain in the study area	34
Table 3.1.4. Chi-square test results for the association between socio- demographic/economic factors and onion production among producers	35
Table 3.1.5. Chi-square results for postharvest loss of onion and Socio-demographic factors at supply chains.....	37
Table 3.1.6. Income sources and annual onion production cycle and by using irrigation ..	39
Table 3.1.7. Transplanting stage and trimming practices of onion seedlings in the study districts.....	41
Table 3.1.8. Irrigation practices in the study districts	42
Table 3.1.9. Hybrid onion varieties grown by onion producers in the study areas and constraints	44
Table 3.1.10. Access for hybrid onion varieties and sources of seeds.....	44
Table 3.1.11. Fertilizer and pesticide access in the study area	46
Table 3.1.12. Type of fertilizers used by respondents in the study area	48
Table 3.1.13. Major diseases in the study area	50
Table 3.1.14. Onion price in the study area	51
Table 3.1.15. The role of brokers/ middle man.....	52
Table 3.1.16. Harvesting practices of onion in the study area	54
Table 3.1.17. Marketing problems in onion produce	56
Table 3.1.18. Post-harvest handling practice of onion at farm level.....	57
Table 3.1.19. Onion handling information of wholesalers and retailers.....	59
Table 3.1.20. Percentage of bulbs unfit for sale at wholesaler and retailer levels	59
Table 3.1.21. Marketing and storage practices of wholesalers and retailers of onion	59
Table 3.1.23. Methods of transportation at wholesalers and retailers chain	64

Table 3.1.24. Communication of wholesalers.....	64
Table 3.1.25. Onion handling practices at consumer’s level	65
Table 3.1.26. Market information	66
Table 3.1.27. Average postharvest losses of onion at the value chain.....	68
Table 3.2.1. Modes of transportation along the supply chain of onion in the study area ...	85
Table 3.2.2. Value addition activities in onion supply chain	86
Table 3.2.3. Margin analysis for the main market actors (N=292) in the value chain of onion (Birr per quintal).....	89
Table 4.1. Effects of variety, nitrogen fertilizer on maturity and growth of the onion across the locations	105
Table 4.2. Influence of variety and nitrogen rate on onion bulb size at three locations ...	107
Table 4.3. Effects of variety and nitrogen on onion bulb yield	111
Table 4.4. Variety and nitrogen effect on onion bulb pungency combined in the three locations.....	112
Table 4.5. The TSS of onion varieties influenced by the interaction of variety and nitrogen combined in the three locations	113
Table 4.6. Partial budget analysis for onion production as influenced by variety and nitrogen fertilizer level across the three locations	114
Table 5.1. Effects of cultivar and plant density on the number of days to physiological maturity of onion plants.....	124
Table 5.2. Effects of onion cultivar and plant density on leaf number and diameter across three locations	127
Table 5.3. The main effects of cultivar and density on onion average bulb diameter and bulb weight across the three locations	130
Table 5.4. Responses of onion bulb yield to cultivar and plant population across the three locations.....	134
Table 6.1. Effects of variety, packaging material, and nitrogen fertilizer rate combined over growing locations on selected postharvest parameters of onion bulbs	151
Table 6.2. Effects of variety, packaging material, and nitrogen fertilizer after four months storage duration on marketability of onion bulbs: across locations.....	155
Table 6.3. Proportion of marketable onion bulbs in different weeks of storage as influenced by the interaction effect of variety and storage materials combined over the three locations	156
Table 6.4. Interaction effect of variety, packaging material, and nitrogen fertilizer on the TSS content of stored onion bulbs across locations	159
Table 6.5. Interaction effect of variety and packaging materials on firmness (Newton) of onion bulb combined over the three locations	161

Table 7.1.Spouting percentage of onion as affected by variety – storage period interaction	172
Table 7.2.Interaction effects of variety and storage duration on bulb decay percentage..	175
Table 7.3.Interaction effects of variety and pre-harvest treatment on the total soluble solid and firmness of onion bulbs over storage duration.....	179
Table 7.4. Interaction effects of varieties and storage duration on bulb weight loss percentage	182
Table 7.5.Interaction effects of variety and pre-harvest treatments on marketable bulb percentage	184

LIST OF FIGURES

Figures	Page
Figure 1.1. Analytical framework of the study	11
Figure 2.1. Map of the study sites: (a) map of Ethiopia, (b) map of the Amhara National Regional State where the study area is located, (c) map that shows the study area with topographic information and the locations of the sites	14
Figure 2.2. Minimum (bottom) and maximum (top) temperatures at the testing sites during the 2021/2022 cropping season.....	15
Figure 3.1.1. Conceptual framework of the onion supply chain.....	32
Figure 3.1.2. Major irrigation water sources for irrigated onion production in the study area.....	43
Figure 3.1.3. (a) Percentage of farmers started hybrid onion production and (b) farmer`s preference for hybrid variety and associated reasons	45
Figure 3.1.4. Rates of organic (a) and inorganic (b) fertilizers applied by onion growing farmers	48
Figure 3.1.5. Onion production trend in Ethiopia (1995EC/2001 to 2015EC/2021).....	49
Figure 3.1.6. Major onion production constraints in the study area	50
Figure 3.1.7. Methods used for harvesting stage determination of onion practiced by farmers	54
Figure 3.1.8. Cultural practices applied by farmers before onion harvesting	55
Figure 3.1.9. Percentage of onion bulbs deemed unsuitable for market due to post-harvest losses.....	57
Figure 3.1.10. Main reasons for the postharvest loss of onion	61
Figure 3.1.11. Measures that farmers are practicing to minimize loss after harvest.....	61
Figure 3.1.12. a. Experience in selling at the wholesaler b. Experience in selling at the retailers.....	62
Figure 3.1.13. (a) Amount bought and (b) method of storage at wholesaler level; (c) Quantity of onions purchased at a time by retailers (in Quintals)	63
Figure 3.1.14. a. Presence of onion bulb quality problems b. Types of quality problems..	66
Figure 3.2.1. Fertilizer consumption trend in kilograms per hectare of arable land in Ethiopia (1993–2022) Source; World Bank (2022).....	78
Figure 3.2.2. Onion production trend (2002–2021). Source; CSA (2022)	84

Figure 3.2.3. Onion supply chain and volume share of the flows.....	88
3.2. 4. Onion supply chain map.....	94
Figure 4 1.Effect of nitrogen rate on the marketable bulb yield of onion varieties	109
Figure 4 2.Relationship between marketable yield and traits (a) plant height, (b) bulb diameter (c) average bulb weight.....	110
Figure 4 3. Polynomial curve fit and regression equation illustrating the relationship between nitrogen rate (kg ha^{-1}) and net benefit (Birr ha^{-1})	115
Figure 5.1.Effects of cultivar and density on the diameter of the onion bulb neck at the three locations	125
Figure 5.2.Effects of cultivar and density on the diameter of the onion bulb neck at the three locations	129
Figure 5.3. Trends in marketable onion bulb yield are influenced by plant density across locations	133
Figure 5.4.Trends in marketable bulb yield influenced by (a), bulb diameter; (b), bulb weight; and (c) bulb weight as related to days to physiological maturity across plant density and locations.....	135
Figure 5.5.Trends in the distribution of bulb size as affected by plant density across the three locations.	139
Figure 6.1.a. Temperature variations in storage room of onion in 2023; b. Average relative humidity and temperature variations in storage room of onion in 2023.....	145
Figure 6.2. Interaction effect of variety and packaging materials on the decay percentage of onion bulbs combined over the three locations	152
Figure 6.3. Effects of packaging material and variety on weight loss percentage of onion after five months storage duration combined over the three locations	154
Figure 6.4.Effects of variety, packaging material, and nitrogen fertilizer on the TSS content of stored onion bulbs for four months: across locations	159
Figure 6.5.Effects of variety, packaging material and nitrogen fertilizer on bulb firmness of onion combined over three locations.....	161
Figure 7.1. Maps of field experimental (Zenzelma campus).	168
Figure 7.2. Sprouting percentage as influenced by varieties under different pre-harvest treatments and storage durations.....	172
Figure 7.3. Decay percentage of onion bulbs as influenced by pre-harvest treatment, variety and storage duration.....	175

Figure 7.4. Total Soluble Solid (TSS) of onion bulbs as influenced by pre-harvest treatments, variety and storage period	177
Figure 7.5. Main effects variety and pre-harvest treatment on firmness of onion bulb....	179
Figure 7.6. Main effects varieties and pre-harvest treatments on firmness of onion bulb at different storage duration.....	182
Figure 7.7. Main effects of varieties and pre-harvest treatments on marketable bulb percentage	184

LIST OF APPENDIX TABLES

Tables	Page
Appendix Table 3.2.1. Authors contribution	231
Appendix Table 4.1. Mean squares and significance levels for onion traits tested	233
Appendix Table 5.1. Mean squares and significance level for onion traits tested.....	234
Appendix Table 6.1. Mean square values and significance level for post-harvest quality traits of onion.....	235
Appendix Table 7.1. Mean square values and significance level for post-harvest quality traits of onion.....	236

LIST OF APPENDIX FIGURES

Figures	Page
Appendix Figure 2.1. Onion seedling at nursery	237
Appendix Figure 2.2. Transplanting	237
Appendix Figure 2.3. Data collection in field.....	237
Appendix Figure 2.4. Field performance	238
Appendix Figure 2.5. Harvested bulb yield	238
Appendix Figure 2.6. Data collection on quality parameters.....	239
Appendix Figure 2.7. Field supervision.....	239
Appendix Figure 2.8. Stored onion bulbs	239
Appendix Figure 3.1.1. Survey on onion production practices in the study area	240
Appendix Figure 3.1.2. Hybrid onion varieties (Jambar, Russet and Red Coach) under production in the study area.....	240
Appendix Figure 3.1.3. Farmers harvesting and post-harvest handling practices	241
Appendix Figure 3.1.4. Post-harvest handling practices by farmers	242

PRODUCTION AND POSTHARVEST OPTIMIZATION OF ONION (*Allium cepa* L.) IN NORTHWEST ETHIOPIA

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GENERAL ABSTRACT

Onion is an economically important cash crop in Ethiopia and the Amhara region, widely produced using irrigation systems to support year-round cultivation and meet market demand. Despite its importance, production faces challenges such as low productivity due to a lack of improved varieties with extended shelf life, inappropriate fertilization, inadequate plant density, and substantial postharvest losses. This study aimed to assess farmers' knowledge and management practices, identify key supply chain constraints, and optimize nitrogen fertilizer rates and plant populations to enhance onion growth, yield, and quality in 20221–2023 in North Mecha (Koga), Bahir Dar Zuria (Woramit), and Fogera (Woreta) districts. Field experiments were arranged in a factorial design using a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications. The survey showed that onion production is dominated by adults with large households, but faces challenges like input shortages, high costs, delays, and major post-harvest losses. Seven alternative marketing channels were identified, involving key actors such as farmers, local collectors, brokers, transporters, wholesalers, retailers, and consumers. The majority of the produce (66.15%) was sold to wholesalers. However, producers received only a small share of the final consumer price, while experiencing the highest average postharvest losses among all actors in the supply chain. The experimental results indicate that onion growth and yield performance are significantly influenced by planting density, variety, nitrogen fertilizer rate,

and growing location. Hybrid varieties Russet and Jambar consistently exhibited superior performance, achieving the highest bulb diameter, weight, harvest index, firmness, total yield, and marketable yield under a planting density of 666,666 plants ha⁻¹ across all locations. Marketable bulb yield was positively correlated with bulb weight, and bulb diameter. Specifically, Russet and Jambar recorded the highest marketable yields of 28.54 t ha⁻¹ and 26.61 t ha⁻¹, respectively. Planting at higher densities (666,666 plants ha⁻¹) with a spacing of 5 cm × 20 cm × 40 cm between plants, rows, and double rows resulted in the highest marketable yield (28.42 t ha⁻¹). The application of 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen fertilizer further enhanced growth and yield parameters, with Russet and Jambar achieving yields of 26.50 t ha⁻¹ and 24.57 t ha⁻¹, respectively, across locations. The combination of these hybrid varieties with optimal nitrogen application (82 kg ha⁻¹) also provided the highest net benefits. Postharvest quality was significantly influenced by storage materials, nitrogen fertilizer, and variety. Proper handling allowed onions to be stored for up to one month without significant losses, regardless of storage materials or production location. Russet and Jambar varieties, stored on locally constructed shelves with optimum nitrogen fertilizer, exhibited delayed sprouting, minimal decay, lower weight loss, and better firmness. In contrast, Bombay Red and Red Coach varieties showed higher storage losses. The study recommends that producers and traders in the study area and similar agro-ecologies adopt Russet and Jambar varieties, combined with higher planting densities and 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen fertilizer. Storing bulbs on shelves until market conditions improve can contribute to a sustainable onion supply chain. This study is the first of its kind and underscores the need for further exploration, particularly to evaluate various hybrid onion cultivars at elevated plant density levels. The use of phosphorus fertilizer is also recommended for future research. Furthermore, the study found that pre-harvest treatments, such as toppling at 90% neck fall, improved postharvest storage. Onions from the Jambar and Russet varieties were able to be stored for up to four weeks without significant loss. However, due to the study's limitation to a single season and location, further research is needed to test plant growth

hormones (e.g., sprout inhibitors) and to validate these findings across multiple locations and seasons.

Keywords: Onion, Supply chain, Constraint, Market channel, Plant density, Russet variety, Postharvest, Nitrogen fertilizer, Storage period, Growth, Yield, Quality, Net benefit, Marketable bulb yield, Packaging material, Toppling, Postharvest loss, Shelf life

Chapter 1: GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1. General Background and Justification

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is a bulb crop belonging to the genus *Allium* of the family Alliaceae. Originating in southwestern Asia, onions have become one of the most widely cultivated vegetables for bulb production over the past 4,000 years (Kumar et al., 2007; Brewster, 2008).

Globally, onions rank as the second most cultivated vegetable, following tomatoes in terms of both cultivation area and economic significance (FAO, 2022). In 2018, total onion production, including green onions and shallots, reached 100 million tons, nearly doubling over two decades (FAOSTAT, 2020). This supports a global economy valued at \$6 billion annually, fulfilling both domestic and export demands. Onions are grown in over 130 countries, with China, India, and the United States as the top producers. Egypt leads Africa in onion production, yielding over 2.2 million metric tons annually, ranking fourth globally (World Atlas, 2024).

In Africa, Egypt's substantial production accounts for a significant share of the continent's contribution to global onion output. Ethiopia, introduced to onion cultivation in the 1970s, has become the third-largest producer of onions in Africa. Despite being the third-largest producer in Africa, Ethiopia's contribution to global production remains limited at 2.7% (FAOSTAT, 2020). The Amhara region, particularly the northwestern areas, accounts for over half of the national production, demonstrating significant potential for expansion.

Onions are cultivated primarily for their characteristic pungency, adding flavor to a variety of dishes, including sauces, soups, sandwiches, and snacks like onion chips. Rich in flavonoids, volatile oils, and allylprophl sulfides, onions serve as valuable condiments and

are a source of essential vitamins and minerals. Both bulbs and green leaves can be consumed fresh, cooked, or in soups and salads. Onions are also recognized for their medicinal properties, offering potential health benefits, such as reducing the risk of high blood pressure, cancer, heart disease, and diabetes, along with exhibiting antibacterial, antiviral, antiallergenic, and anti-inflammatory effects (Raemaekers, 2001; Renbomo and Biswas, 2017). Additionally, onions play a crucial role in income generation and export, contributing significantly to the global economy.

In Ethiopia, onions were introduced by foreign sources in the 1970s and have become integral to the country's agriculture (Lemma Dessalegn and Shimelis Aklilu, 2003). Onions, categorized as cool-season crops, are adaptable to various climatic conditions, thriving at altitudes ranging from 500 to 2400 m.a.s.l., with an optimal range of 700-2200 m.a.s.l. They prefer well-drained sandy loam soils rich in organic matter, with an ideal soil pH between 6.2 and 7.0 (Lemma Dessalegn and Shimelis Aklilu, 2003; MoARD, 2019). Onions are cultivated year-round by both small-scale farmers and commercial growers, utilizing irrigation and rain-fed systems to meet local demand and support export markets (Nikus Olani and Mulugeta Fikre, 2010; Sara Belay et al., 2015; MoARD, 2019).

Despite being the third-largest onion producer in Africa, following Egypt and South Africa, Ethiopia contributed only 2.7% to total world production between 2000 and 2011 (FAOSTAT, 2020). The Amhara region is the primary producer, contributing 54% of the national yield, with an average yield of 16 tons per hectare during the 2021/22 main season (Yebirzaf Yeshiwas et al., 2024). Specifically, in the northwestern Ethiopia, which includes the Fogera, Dera, Mecha, and Bahir Dar Zuria districts, onion production is rapidly expanding, demonstrating a competitive advantage. In 2017/18, the Mecha district cultivated 943.75 hectares with an average yield of 18 t ha⁻¹, while Fogera cultivated 11,880.5 hectares with an average yield of 20.3 t ha⁻¹, highlighting opportunities for higher profitability and expansion.

However, onion productivity in Ethiopia, at 11.7 t ha⁻¹, remains below the global average of 21.1 t ha⁻¹ (CSA, 2020; FAOSTAT, 2022). Several factors contribute to this low productivity, including a lack of improved cultivars, inappropriate agronomic practices, weak extension services, pest and disease infestations, inadequate marketing systems, fluctuating climatic conditions, poor infrastructure, and high postharvest losses (AgroBIG, 2016; Habtamu Gudisa, 2017; Agidew Abebe, 2018; Almaz Giziew, 2018; Taye Melese et al., 2018; Muluneh Bekele et al., 2019a). Among these, major challenges include the absence of improved varieties, inappropriate agronomic practices, nitrogen fertilizer rates, plant population issues, weak market linkage, poor product handling, and high postharvest losses (AgroBIG, 2016; Kassa Getu and Ahmed Ibrahim, 2018; Muluneh Bekele et al., 2019b).

Feeding the growing global population, expected to reach 10 billion by 2050, requires a 70% increase in yield or the cultivation of two million hectares additional land, scarce resources (FAO, 2009). To address this, options, including use of improved varieties, optimized agronomic practices such as nitrogen fertilization, plant population management, reduction of postharvest losses are essential activities.

Hybrid onions offer higher yields, uniformity, and better storage potential. Hybrid cultivars can potentially double yields compared to open-pollinated varieties, making them key to improving productivity (Agnieszka et al., 2017). In Ethiopia, efforts to improve onion production include the development of 28 improved open-pollinated and hybrid varieties (Lemma Dessalegn and Shimelis Aklilu, 2003; MoARD, 2019). However, complete production technologies remain inadequately addressed. Hybrid onion can be stored for up to five months, depending on the storage conditions (MoARD, 2019). Focusing on improved cultivars with better storage characteristics is crucial for enhancing yield per hectare (Mondal, 1991).

Proper spacing in onion cultivation reduces competition for resources like water, nutrients, and light, leading to better yields and quality (Nehra et al., 1988; Nichols and Heydecker, 1964). Optimizing plant population ensures efficient land use and maximizes yield. Wider spacing improves yield per plant, while closer spacing boosts yield per unit area up to a certain point (Abubaker, 2008; Bhuiyan et al., 2012; Haile and Abate, 2020; Tsegaye et al., 2022). Nitrogen management is also critical, insufficient nitrogen reduces yields (Lee, 2014; Kahan et al., 2021), while excessive nitrogen can harm plants and the environment (Buckland, 2013; Geary et al., 2015). Careful optimization of spacing and nitrogen application is vital for maximizing onion yields sustainably. Hybrid compared with open-pollinated varieties, hybrid onion varieties, with rapid adaptability, uniformity, and double yield potential, require higher nutritive inputs to achieve their yield potential (Meer, 1994; Hyde, 2010; Singh and Bhonde., 2011; Agnieszka et al., 2017).

Onion storage is crucial for maintaining supply for export and processing markets. Storage potential and shelf-life are influenced by factors such as mineral nutrition, cultivar differences, climate, storage methods, and growth regulators (Adamicki, 2005; Ullah et al., 2008). In Ethiopia, onion storage poses a significant challenge, with reported losses of up to 100%, primarily due to the cultivation of short-storage, open-pollinated cultivars. Overall, postharvest losses in horticultural crops in Ethiopia can range from 15–70%, with onion losses estimated at 13–36% in specific regions (Ko *et al.*, 2002; Daniels and Fors, 2015).

Improving storage techniques can address postharvest losses, which include physiological weight loss, sprouting, and rotting. Storage duration is influenced by bulb characteristics such as dry matter content, soluble solids, and pungency (Ko et al., 2002). The shelf life of onions is a genetic trait, which can be enhanced by effective crop management and appropriate storage conditions (Agnieszka et al., 2017).

Addressing the production-to-market chain issues through improved market linkages and price stability can enhance smallholder farmers' incomes and boost national production efficiency (AgroBIG, 2016; Agidew Abebe, 2018). In Ethiopia, onion market supply is often surplus during peak production seasons due to poor storage capabilities. Farmers are not benefited a price advantage because of inconsistent supply and inadequate storage capacity, resulting in lower prices during main production season. Strategies to ensure a year-round supply include efficient pre-harvest treatments, improved storage technologies, and better handling practices, which can reduce losses and stabilize the market (Adamicki, 2005; Yebirzaf Yeshiwas et al., 2023).

Hence, studies on the performance of various hybrid onion varieties under different agronomic practices and postharvest handling methods are essential for realizing the crop's full potential in northwestern Ethiopia.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Onion plays a significant role in Ethiopia, serving as one of the primary cash crops grown by smallholder farmers across the country, including the Amhara region. Despite its recent introduction, it is a popular vegetable crop, because of its high yield potential per unit area, and ease of propagation by seed (Asfaw Zeleke and Eshetu Derso, 2015; MoARD, 2019).

In 2022, Ethiopia ranked as the world's 50th largest onion exporter, with exports valued at \$5.12 million, making onions the country's 61st most exported product. Major export markets included Djibouti (\$1.56M), the Netherlands, Germany (\$1.24M), Switzerland (\$295K), and Kenya (\$250K). Between 2021 and 2022, Ethiopian onion exports experienced significant growth in the Netherlands (+\$320K), Kenya (+\$93.5K), and Norway (+\$43.7K) (OEC, 2024). This growth highlights the potential of onion production to contribute significantly to improving farmers' incomes and livelihoods, as well as bolstering the national economy (Habtamu Mossie, 2020). However, this potential remains

constrained by several challenges, including the lack of improved varieties, inappropriate agronomic practices, low soil fertility, improper fertilizer use, limited land availability, and environmental degradation. Additional issues such as a weak extension system, pest and disease infestations, inadequate storage facilities, poor market linkages, and high postharvest losses have further hindered onion production and productivity, particularly in the Amhara Region (Agidew Abebe, 2018; Almaz Giziew, 2018; Taye Melese et al., 2018; Muluneh Bekele et al., 2019a).

Farmers in Ethiopia traditionally use open-pollinated varieties, primarily Bombay Red and Adama Red. Recently, however, hybrid onion varieties with higher yield potential have been introduced into the farming system. Despite this advancement, farmers continue to apply agronomic practices recommended for open-pollinated varieties. On the other hand, the required agronomic practices like the fertilizer rate and spacing of plants depend on the yielding potential of the crop, the soil fertility status and the environmental and edaphic conditions of the growing areas (Habtamu Gudisa, 2017; Yebirzaf Yesheiwias et al., 2023). In this regard, identifying the optimum nitrogen fertilizer rate and plant population of hybrid onion varieties is necessary to enhance the productivity of onion in Amhara region.

Postharvest loss is another critical challenge in Ethiopian onion production. Losses occur in the form of sprouting, weight loss, decay, and bulb rotting at various stages of the supply chain. Factors such as pre-harvest agronomic practices, mineral nutrition, choice of varieties, climatic conditions during the growing season, and storage methods significantly influence onion storability (Adamicki, 2005; Ullah et al., 2008). Smallholder farmers in Ethiopia including Amhara Region are producing mainly Bombay Red and Adama Red varieties, which are suitable in most cases for fresh consumption. Storing of these varieties is mostly associated with high postharvest loss. Storage, however, is critical for ensuring a continuous market supply, avoiding price fluctuations, and stabilizing farmers' incomes. Introducing onion varieties with better storability and improved storage methods to prolong

shelf life is necessary to reduce postharvest losses and support a sustainable supply chain. The present study was thus initiated to identify the major constraints along the onion value chain and optimize agronomic practices for hybrid onion varieties to enhance onion production and productivity in northwestern Ethiopia.

1.3. Objectives of the Study

1.3.1. General objective

The overall objective of the study was contributing for the enhancement of production and productivity of onion through optimization of agronomic practices of hybrid onion varieties and reduction of postharvest losses by using pre-harvest treatments and proper packaging methods in northwestern Ethiopia.

1.3.2 Specific objectives

- To identify the management practices and constraints of onion production by smallholder and analyze the onion supply chain in in northwestern Ethiopia.
- To investigate the effects of planting density and variety on the growth, yield, and quality of onion
- To study the influence of nitrogen fertilizer rate onion variety on the growth, yield and shelf life of onion bulb
- To study the influence of packaging material and variety on the shelf life and quality of onion bulb
- To evaluate effectiveness of pre-harvest treatment and variety on the shelf life and postharvest quality of onion bulbs

The analytical framework that visualizes interconnection of these objectives and their contribution to each other is indicated in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1. Analytical framework of the study

1.4. Organization of the Dissertation

The dissertation is structured into eight chapters.

The first chapter: is a general introduction, offering a comprehensive overview of the study. It provides background information on the global status of onion production, highlighting its importance as a widely cultivated and consumed vegetable. It also examines onion production in Ethiopia, underscoring its significance to smallholder farmers and the national economy. The chapter identifies key challenges contributing to low onion productivity, such as the lack of improved varieties, inappropriate agronomic practices, low soil fertility, and high postharvest losses. Additionally, it outlines the impact of inadequate storage facilities and weak market linkages.

The second chapter described the general materials used and the methods followed, it includes area description, methods of data collection, and statistical methods for data analysis to achieve the study objectives.

The third chapter was a survey that assesses the onion management practices followed by smallholder farmers, the constraints of production and postharvest management of onion along the supply chain in northwest Ethiopia. It also deals with the identification of major supply chain actors of onion and their role and the marketing channel of onion.

The chapters 4 - 7 were experimental studies, stated the theoretical background information that supported the necessity of conducting the particular experiment. Additionally, the specific objectives and methods, planting materials, experimental design and treatments used, the collected data and their method of analysis and key findings were briefly presented.

Chapter 8 stated a general conclusion and recommendation based on the findings of the study. In this chapter suggestions for future research areas were also made.

Chapter 2. GENERAL MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Description of the Study Area

Field experiments were conducted at three districts of Amhara Region namely North Mecha (Koga), Fogera (Woreta), and Bahir Dar Zuria (Woramit) districts (Fig. 2.1) during the 2021/2022 irrigation season.

The Fogera district is one of the 126 districts of the Amhara Regional State. The district is situated at 11°58' N latitude and 37°41' E longitude. Woreta is the capital city of the district and is located 625 km from Addis Ababa and 55 km from the regional capital, Bahir Dar. The average annual rainfall is 1216.3 mm, with long and short cropping seasons. Its altitude ranges from 1774 to 2410 meters above sea level. The climate is almost medium highland with an average temperature ranging from 10.3 °C to 27.2 °C.

North Mecha district is one of the 14 districts found in Amhara National Regional State of West Gojjam Administrative Zone. It is located 515 km north of Addis Ababa, the country's capital, and 37 km southwest of Bahir Dar, capital city of the Amhara Regional State. Merawi, Woreda's capital city, is located on the main road connecting Addis Ababa and Bahir Dar. The district is located between 11°05' N to 11°38' N and 37°00' E to 37°23' E. The study area receives an annual mean rainfall of 1395.23 mm. The mean maximum and minimum temperature of the study area are 27 °C and 12.8 °C respectively.

Bahir Dar Zuria district is located around Bahir Dar town, within 37°10' East of longitude and 11°15' North of latitude. It is approximately 578 km northwest of Addis Ababa. The mean altitude of the district is 1,800 meter above sea level, and the temperature of the district ranges from 10 °C to 38 °C throughout the year, with a mean annual rainfall of 750 mm. The map of the experimental locations and specific trial sites represents distinct agroecologies conditions (Figure 2.1).

The geographical locations, altitudes, rainfall, and soil types of the districts are presented in Table 2.1. The average maximum and minimum temperatures of Woreta and Woramit during the experimental period were 29 °C and 17.8 °C and 28 °C and 12.4 °C, respectively. The Koga experimental site had mean maximum and minimum temperatures of 28.8 °C and 9.5 °C, respectively, as indicated in Figure 2.2 (Regional Meteorological Station, 2022).

Figure 2.1. Map of the study sites: (a) map of Ethiopia, (b) map of the Amhara National Regional State where the study area is located, (c) map that shows the study area with topographic information and the locations of the sites

Table 2.1. Altitudes, temperature, rainfall and soil types at specific experimental sites

Location	Lat. (N)	Long.(E)	Altitude (masl)	Rainfall (mm)	Soil texture
Woramit	11°38'	37°10'	1800	1248.8	Nitisoile
Koga	11°20'	37°7'	1953	1300 -1380	Nitisoile
Woreta	11°55'	37°42'	1828	1250	Vertisol

Figure 2.2. Minimum (bottom) and maximum (top) temperatures at the testing sites during the 2021/2022 cropping season

Source: Regional Meteorological Station (2022)

Selected properties of the soil in the experimental locations

Soil samples from the experimental sites were collected via standard procedures prior to planting at each site. A composite soil sample was taken before the experimental plot was plowed by mixing samples collected at eight different locations along the two diagonal lines of the field at 0-20 cm depth via an auger. The physical and chemical properties of the composite soils from each location were analyzed at the Soil and Plant Nutrition Laboratory of the College of Agricultural and Environmental Sciences, Bahir Dar University. The results of the soil analysis are presented in Table 2.2.

Table 2.2. Status of nutrients in the experimental locations before planting in 2021/2022 irrigation season

Soil properties	Soil Sample		
	Koga	Woramit	Woreta
Texture			
Sand (%)	56	44	43
Silt (%)	16	24	15
Clay (%)	28	32	42
Textural class	Sandy Clay Loam	Clay Loam	Clay
pH _{H₂O} (1:2.5)	5.40	5.69	6.02
EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	161.30	89.10	74.00
Organic Carbon (%)	2.18	1.72	1.33
Organic Matter (%)	3.77	2.96	2.29
CEC ($\text{cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$)	27.60	26.00	41.40
Total Nitrogen (%)	0.42	0.17	0.18
Available Phosphorus (mg/kg) [Olsen method]	10.02	20.24	6.48

The textural class of the experimental soil was found to be sandy clay loam in Koga, clay loam in Woramit and clay in Woreta, with pH values of 5.4, 5.69 and 6.06, respectively. The pH of Woreta falls within the optimal range, whereas those of Koga and Woramit are slightly acidic and are within a preferred range for most crops. The electrical conductivity values of the experimental soils are within acceptable limits for onions, indicating that the sites had low salinity levels. The organic matter content of the site is in the medium range (2-4%) for Ethiopian soils per the criteria developed by Murphy (1968). The total nitrogen content of the soils was found to be high in Koga and low in Woreta and Woramit, on the basis of the rating by Tekalign Tadesse *et al.* (1991). The Olsen extractable available phosphorus (P) content of the soil was 10.02 mg kg⁻¹ in Koga (rated as medium), 20.24 mg kg⁻¹ in Woramit (rated as medium), and 6.48 mg kg⁻¹ in Woreta (rated as low), according to Landon (1991). The cation exchange capacity (CEC) of the soil was 27, 26, and 41, ranging from medium to high according to the rating by Jackson (1975) (Table 2.2).

2.2. Experimental Materials

Three hybrid F₁ onion varieties, Russet, Red Coach, and Jambar, and one open pollinated Bombay Red variety were used as control in this study. The seeds of the hybrid varieties

were collected from commercial suppliers (Eshet Agricultural Input Supplier, Bahir Dar, Ethiopia), while the seeds of the Bombay Red variety were obtained from the Melkassa Agricultural Research Center (MARC). The onion varieties were selected on basis of the the results of the preliminary pilot survey in which the farmers preferred them on the basis of their growth and yield performance. The general characteristics of the selected onion varieties are presented below.

Table 2.3. List of varieties and their descriptions

Variety name	Year of release/registration	Area of adaptation		Maturity days
		Altitude (m)	Rainfall (mm)	
Russet F _I	2013	1500-2200	Irrigated	90-110
Red Coach F _I	2015	500-2200	Irrigated	107-120
Jambar F _I	2011	1000-2500	Irrigated	90-110
Bombay Red	1980	700-2000	Irrigated	110-120

Source: MoARD (2004, 2016, 2019).

2.3. Treatments and Experimental Design

The treatments and designs used for the experiments in the study are summarized below in Table 2.4.

Table 2.4. Summary of treatments and designs used in the study

No	Title of the experiment	Treatments	Design	Rep
1	Potential constraints and determinants: onion production and postharvest management in the northwest Ethiopian supply chain - The rise and fall of onion production; its multiple constraints on pre-harvest and post-harvest management issues along the supply chain in northwest Ethiopia	Assess the major production and post-harvest handling determinants: farm, wholesale, retailer and consumers levels	Survey	

	- Strategic mapping of onion supply chains: a comprehensive analysis of production and post-harvest processes in Northwest Ethiopia			
2	Enhancing bulb yield through fertilization and the use of hybrid onion varieties in northwest Ethiopia	4*4 factorial arrangement. Four varieties, four levels of N fertilizer rate (0, 41, 82, and 123 kg ha ⁻¹), in three locations	RCBD	3
3	Influence of cultivar and plant density on the growth, bulb yield of bulb and quality traits of onion (<i>Allium cepa</i> L.)	4*3 factorial arrangement. Four varieties, and three levels of planting density, (666,666 ha ⁻¹ , 333,333 ha ⁻¹ and 222,222 ha ⁻¹), in three locations	RCBD	3
4	Effect of packaging materials on the shelf life and quality of hybrid onion varieties in north-western Ethiopia	4*4*3 factorial combinations, four varieties, four levels of N fertilizer, and three types of packaging materials (burlap sack, wooden/mesh shelves, and open floor),	RCBD	3
5	Influence of pre-harvest treatments on shelf life and post-harvest Quality of Hybrid Onion (<i>Allium cepa</i> L.) varieties in Bahir Dar zuria district of Amhara Region	4*4*3 factorial arrangement. Three varieties and four levels of pre-harvest treatments (Topped at 70% neck fall and irrigated before 3 days of harvesting; Topped at 90% neck fall, Topped at 70% neck fall, Control: Un-topped, Un-irrigated	RCBD	3

2.4. Experimental Procedures

Seeds of each variety were sown on well-prepared raised beds and mulched with straw. After germination the mulching material was removed. Watering was done using a fine watering can where the frequency was determined based on climatic conditions. The seedlings were maintained for 55 days after sowing and hardened before being transplanted to the field. This was done by reducing the frequency of watering and making the soil with low moisture status when the seedlings were ready for field planting.

Healthy and vigorous 12-15 cm long seedlings were carefully raised for transplanting (Appendix Figure 2.1). The selected seedlings were transplanted in January 2022 with a recommended double row planting system: 40 cm between irrigation furrows, 20 cm spacing between rows, and 5 cm, 10 cm, and 15 cm intra-row spacing with plant populations of high, medium and low plants per hectare, respectively, for the population density experiment and spacing of 40 cm × 20 cm × 10 cm for the nitrogen experiment (Appendix Figure 2.2) (MoARD, 2004). In each plot, there were three double rows.

All agronomic practices were applied according to the recommendations for onion (MoARD, 2004). On the basis of the rates of the treatments, nitrogen fertilizer was applied in the form of urea (46% N) in two equal splits, where the first 50% of the nitrogen was applied 15 days after transplanting, while the remaining 50% was applied one month after transplanting. Triple superphosphate (46% P₂O₅) was used as a source of phosphorus and was applied uniformly for all plots at the rate of 92 kg ha⁻¹ P₂O₅ at the time of transplanting (Nikus Olani and Mulugeta Fiker, 2010).

Irrigation water was applied at four-day intervals using furrow irrigation for the first four weeks and then extended to seven-day intervals until the physiological maturity stage. The application of irrigation water was completely stopped 15 days before harvesting for curing purposes. Onion bulbs were harvested when approximately 70% of the plants in each plot displayed neck fall, although the specific timing varied depending on the nature of the experiment (IPGRI, 2001; MoARD, 2004).

2.5. Data Collection

Measurements of onion growth, yield, and quality parameters were recorded from the central 4 rows of the net plot area at the physiological maturity stage and harvesting time (Appendix Figure 2.3 - Appendix Figure 2.8).

Growth parameters

Plant height (cm): was measured using ruler from the soil surface to the tip of the longest mature leaves at physiological maturity.

Leaf number per plant: it was the total count of leaves per plant at physiological maturity.

Leaf diameter (cm): refers to the maximum diameter of the longest leaf measured by using digital caliper at the widest point of the leaf.

Bulb neck diameter (cm): the average neck widths of ten randomly selected matured bulbs were measured by using digital caliper and expressed in centimetre.

Days to physiological maturity: refers to the actual number of days from date of transplanting to the day at which more than 70% of the plants in a plot showed yellowing and dried leaves.

Yield parameters

Bulb length (cm): refers to the height of the cured bulb measured by using a digital Vernier caliper from the bottom to the top of the matured bulb.

Bulb diameter (cm): was measured by using a digital Vernier caliper at the widest point in the middle portion of the mature bulb after curing.

Harvest index: this was the ratio of total fresh bulb yield to total fresh biomass yield which was recorded from ten randomly selected plants at harvest time and expressed as a percentage.

$$\text{Harvest index (HI)} = (\text{EY}/\text{BY}) * 100$$

Where EY = weight of fresh bulb (economic yield); BY = weight of biological yield (above and belowground dry weight).

The average bulb weight (g): it was computed by weighing ten randomly selected marketable bulbs harvested from the net plot area and averaging per bulb.

Marketable bulb yield (t ha⁻¹): marketable bulbs are bulbs that are free of splitting, damages, rotting and discoloration and greater than 20 g (Lemma Dessalegn and Shimeles Aklilu, 2003). Such bulbs harvested from the net plot area were weighed by using digital weighing balance and expressed in ton ha⁻¹ were considered as marketable bulb yield.

Unmarketable bulb yield (t ha⁻¹): are bulbs that fail to meet market standards due to being undersized (<20g), diseased, decayed, or showing physiological disorders, such as splitting. These bulbs were collected, weighed, and their yield calculated per hectare, using the same procedure applied for determining marketable bulb yield.

Total bulb yield (t ha⁻¹) was determined by the summation of marketable and unmarketable bulb yields.

Bulb size distribution: marketable bulb yield was categorized as small (20-50 g), medium (50–100 g), and large (>100 g) based on Lemma Dessalegn and Shimelis Aklilu (2003). Each category was weighed and expressed in t ha⁻¹.

Bulb quality parameters

The postharvest quality data were measured over distinct storage durations, spanning four-five months for Chapter 6 and three months for Chapter 7.

1. Total soluble solid (TSS) (%) was determined using the procedures described by Waskar *et al.* (1999). The juice of the four sample bulbs was extracted using a juice extractor and the extracted juices were filtered using sieve. The TSS was determined using ATAGO® PR-32 α by placing one to two drops of clean juice on the prism at a monthly interval in the four months storage experiment. The refractometer was standardized using distilled water (0% TSS). The prism of the refractometer was washed with distilled water and dried before the next use.

2. **Firmness (N)** was determined with a portable fruit penetrometer (GY-4 model S/N G2001707622) using an 8 mm stainless steel punch. The bulb was penetrated on at the two opposite sides at its equatorial region and the average of the two measurements in Newton (N) was taken in monthly interval in the storage experiment.
3. **Pungency (D. mol/ml)** content of the pyruvic acid developed in homogenized 4 sample bulb tissue was used as a measure of pungency following the modified procedures of Anthon and Barrett (2003).
4. **Days to the first sprouting:** Onions were monitored daily to detect visible sprouts on at least one bulb by visual inspection. The number of days elapsed from storage to the first sighting of sprouting was counted and used as days to the first sprouting.
5. **The physiological weight loss (%) of onion bulbs** was determined according to the methods described by Waskar *et al.* (1999) using the formula below [2]. The difference between the initial weight and successive weights gave the weight loss and expressed in percentages.

$$\text{Weight loss of bulbs \%} = \left(\frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \right) * 100 \dots \dots \dots [2]$$

6. **Percentage of sprouted bulbs** was ascertained by counting the number of bulbs sprouted at the beginning and mid of each month until the storage period and divided by the total initial number of bulbs, then multiplied by 100. After each inspection, sprouted bulbs were removed to prevent double counting. Bulbs that sprouted and rotten simultaneously were classified as sprouted.
7. **Percentage of decay/rotten bulbs** was determined by counting the number of decayed bulbs and expressing them as a percentage of the total initial number of bulbs [3]. The percentage of rotted bulbs was calculated cumulatively, which was calculated at the beginning and midpoint of each month during a five, and three-months storage period. Rotted bulbs were discarded after each count to avoid duplicate counting.

$$\text{Percentage decay (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of decayed bulbs}}{\text{Total number of initial bulbs}} \right) * 100 \dots \dots [3]$$

8. **Percentage of marketable bulbs** was assessed subjectively according to the methods described by Mohammed *et al.* (1999). It was evaluated by observing the level of visible

rotting, mold, discoloration, sprouting and shriveling of stored bulbs. Percentage of marketable bulbs was determined as the proportion of number of bulbs free of above-mentioned parameters (marketable) to the total number of stored bulbs and expressed as a percentage. It was taken in monthly interval during the storage period [4].

$$\text{Marketable onion bulbs (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of marketable bulbs}}{\text{Total number of initially stored bulbs}} \right) * 100 \dots \dots \dots [4]$$

2.6. Data Analysis

The collected data was initially checked for the fulfilment of all the ANOVA assumptions (normality and homogeneity) by using Shapiro-Wilk normality test and Leven`s homogeneity test. The data was subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the PROC MIXED procedure of SAS computer software version 9.0 (SAS Institute Inc., 2008) as required. When ANOVA showed significant differences ($P < 0.05$), the mean separation was carried out using the least significant difference (LSD) (Gomez and Gomez, 1984). In addition, a simple Pearson correlation analysis was performed to reveal the magnitudes and directions of the relationships between the selected growths, yield and quality parameters of onion.

Chapter 3: POTENTIAL, CONSTRAINTS AND DETERMINANTS OF ONION PRODUCTION AND POSTHARVEST MANAGEMENT IN THE NORTHWEST ETHIOPIAN SUPPLY CHAIN

3.1. The Rise and Fall of Onion Production; its Multiple Constraints on Pre-Harvest and Post-Harvest Management Issues Along the Supply Chain in Northwest Ethiopia

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Published by Elsevier Ltd, Cell Press, Heliyon

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e15905>

Abstract

Food and nutrition security is not only addressed by increasing production alone, it should also ensure by reducing food loss. Onion has a great contribution to both economic and health issues, however, its production and productivity in the country is low. Thus, the study was initiated to identify multiple constraints on onion production and postharvest handling practices and to determine the extent of postharvest loss along the supply chain in northwest Ethiopia. Survey was conducted at farm, wholesale, retailer, and consumer's level. The multistage sampling procedure was employed. The results revealed that sex, age, educational level, production experience, land covered by onion, and household size have a significant influence on onion production. Sex, age, education level, active household size, selling experience, amount purchased, and storage duration have a significant association with onion production and postharvest loss. Major onion production and postharvest loss constraints were high perishable nature of the crop, poor market linkage problem, low

market price, lack of awareness of using postharvest technologies, absence of better storable varieties and access to fertilizer and disease and insect pests. The whole purchased produce never reached the consumer's hands. The total postharvest loss of onion at the farmer, wholesale, retail, and consumer level was found to be 29.8%, of which the higher proportion of losses (35.5%) was observed at the farmer's level. Based on the findings of the present study, onion producers were challenged by timely and adequate supply and high cost of major production inputs and high postharvest loss. Therefore, producers and handlers in the supply chain need to be trained on affordable and applicable postharvest technologies. In addition, continuous capacity-building training, improving infrastructures, and input access along the supply chain should be designed and implemented to improve better crop management and postharvest handling practices. Moreover, marketing cooperatives working on onion postharvest handling and marketing systems should be functional to absorb surplus production and ensure continuous supply to the market. Thus, meaningful interventions in the development and implementation of policy on sustainable production, handling practices, and supply of onion should be designed.

Keywords: Onion, Supply chain, Yield constraints, Pre-harvest handling, Post-harvest loss

3.3.1. Introduction

Feeding a global population of 10 billion by 2050 is expected to become one of the greatest challenges of this time, which will require a 70% increase in food production (Tilman *et al.*, 2001; FAO, 2009). Food and nutrition security continues to pose a challenge to African countries taking into consideration the fast-rising population growth coupled with decreasing natural resources such as land and the stress posed to water resources by climate change (Sowe *et al.*, 2020). An increase in malnutrition has occurred in different parts of the world. Food and nutrition security is not only addressed by increasing production alone but also by reducing food losses. At this time, the most urgent need is to increase production

with proper postharvest management of onion in a sustainable manner and improve farm income to insure household food and nutritional security.

Onion is one of the more intensively consumed and most important cash-generating crop for farmers around northwestern Ethiopia (Kassa Getu and Ibrahim Ahmed, 2018). Even though the crop has a great contribution to both economic and health issues, its production and productivity are not scaled to the required level. Its production trend is not consistent, rises over in a certain period of time and falls in another period of time. Thus, farmers are not yet benefited from onion production. There are a number of factors associated for these low levels of onion production. These factors are improper agronomic practices, high cost of production inputs, lack of adequate storage facilities, limited access to improved seeds, high cost of transport, fluctuation of market price and lack of sufficient capital, and postharvest losses (Grema and Gashua, 2014).

Onion postharvest loss begins from production and it is inevitable after harvesting particularly during storage. Its postharvest losses are incurred at each channel in the supply chain where the produce passes through. Therefore, identifying major constraints of onion is important to alleviate the existing problems along the supply chain and to design intervention strategies. Thus, detecting multiple factors that determine the rise and fall of the production and postharvest handling of onion from the farm to the consumers would give direction to farmers and concerned bodies to improve problems in the production and continuous supply. This study was therefore initiated;

- To investigate the skills and knowledge of farmers in the management practices and postharvest handling of onion.
- To identify major onion production and postharvest handling constraints in supply chains in northwestern Ethiopia.
- To determine the extent of postharvest loss of onion along the supply chain

3.3.1.1. Hypothetical framework

Household size positively influences the production, supply, and postharvest loss reduction activities. Household heads with large-sized family members eases the operations of farm activities in the production and management of harvested onions through additional labor force (Abedullah *et al.*, 2009; Achoja and Obodaya, 2019; Mukaila *et al.*, 2021; Debebe Sisay, 2022). The experience of the household in the production and selling of onion also enhances the skills and knowledge in the production and postharvest management operations. As a result, it was possible to hypothesize that farmer and trader with longer experiences are expected to have better skill on production and post-harvest management. Experienced farmers have better administrative abilities towards production and handling (Koye, 2022). Accordingly, as the age of the farmers increased, their capability in managing of the farm increased that in turn increased the yield of onion. Similarly, education enhances the decision-making abilities of farmers, traders and consumers to accept and practice new ideas and technologies. Furthermore, formal education positively influences the willingness of farmers and traders to produce better and reduce the extent of postharvest loss (Obayelu *et al.*, 2021).

High production costs decrease the ability of farmers to cover more hectares of land with onion that in turn reduces the quantity produced and supply of the market (Agumas Yideg, 2019). As a result, we hypothesized that the cost of farm inputs like fertilizer, pesticides, and fuel negatively influences the production of onion. The use of improved seed varieties contributes by about 5 to 30% to the crop yield (Baliyan, 2014). Thus, using hybrid varieties enhances the productivity of onion. According to Falola *et al.* (2023) an increase in harvested and purchased volume of onion increases the quantity of postharvest losses. According to Kader (2005), as the stay in the market increases the produce deterioration rate will be increased. Thus, the number of days required to finish the selling activities has a positive relation with the spoilage proportion of onion.

3.3.2. Methodology

3.3.2.1. Study area description

The study was conducted in three potential onion-producing districts and six *kebeles* of north-west Amhara, Ethiopia. Major onion-producing *kebeles* are namely: Mecha district (*Kudmi and Enguti kebeles*), Fogera district (*Shina and Kuhar Micael kebeles*), and Bahir Dar Zuria district (*Yigoma, and Sebatamit kebeles*) from August 2021–March 2022. The three districts Fogera, Mecha, and Bahir Dar Zuria are geographically located between 11°58' N latitude and 37°41' E longitude, 11°05' N to 11°38' N, and 37°00' E to 37°23' E and 29°27' 34", 35°58' 40" East of longitude and 13°38'19', 12°1'37" North of latitude respectively (Figure 2.1).

3.3.2.2. Data types, sources, and collection methods

To achieve the study objectives, primary data were collected through face-to-face interviews with key informants and supply chain actors, direct field observation, and market observations. Data on socio-demographic and socio-economic characteristics, onion production practices, and constraints related to farmers' onion production, utilization, marketing, harvesting, postharvest handling practices, postharvest loss, and their interaction with the respective actors were collected from the respondents.

To collect primary data, a structured questionnaire was used Elahi *et al.* (2022), through key informant interviews, farmers, wholesalers, retailers, consumers, direct field observations, and market assessment. The structure of the questionnaire was designed as both open-ended and close-ended. The close-ended questions were designed to list or select a suitable response and they were coded. The open-ended questions were prepared by letting the respondents freely explain any of their ideas (Appendix 1). Before the interviews, the respondents have informed and convinced about the purpose of the study and each respondent had asked for their agreement before the interview. In addition, respondents were

given the right to drop the questions which are uncomfortable for them and replace them with other voluntary respondents and their responses were kept strictly confidential (Elahi *et al.* 2021).

Secondary data were collected by using document analysis techniques. Documents of Agricultural Offices at all level and other relevant offices were used as a source for secondary data. Moreover, a systematic review of peer-reviewed journal articles, proceedings and books was done to collect the necessary information. The questionnaires for the interview that were prepared in the English language were translated into the local language of respondents, Amharic to avoid the language barrier. The questionnaires used for the interview consisted of socio-demographic and socio-economic characteristics of households, questions on farming knowledge and practices, questions on access to production inputs, harvesting, and postharvest handling practices, and access to market information. During the field observation (physical observation), onion production and handling practice was observed to determine the type and causes of postharvest loss at the time of harvesting. In addition, onion production, agronomic management, major disease and insect pests, and harvesting and postharvest handling activities were also observed to have more reliable information about the existing onion handling practices in the supply chain.

3.3.2.3. Sampling technique and sample size determination

A reconnaissance survey was carried out together with the district horticulture experts to get an overview of the status of onion production in the selected areas. The survey was conducted following the supply chains of onion production, marketing (wholesale, retail) and consumption to identify the major constraints in the production and postharvest handling processes.

Multistage sampling procedure was employed as indicated by (Abbas *et al.*, 2022; Elahi *et al.*, 2022). At the first stage two potential onion-producing Zones such as South Gonder, and West Gojjam were selected were selected purposely. At the second stage three potential onion-producing districts Fogera, North Mecha and Bahir Dar Zuria districts were selected purposely from major onion-producing zones. At the third stage two highly potential onion-producing *kebeles* were selected purposely from major onion-producing *kebeles*. The selected two *kebeles* have high onion production capacity and have market-linkage with the major onion marketing centers of the country. In the fourth stage, onion-producing households were randomly selected from the two *kebeles* for an interview purpose. In the fifth stage, wholesalers, retailers, and consumers at Bahir Dar, Woreta, and Merawi cities were purposely selected based on their capacities. The retailer's chain included the roadside sellers, town market displayers, and other small-scale traders. Yamane's (1967) sampling formula [1] with a 7% precision level was applied to draw the sample sizes of the households.

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \quad [1]$$

Where; n is the required sample size, N is the target population size (total number of onion-producing households), and e is the precision level (7%). The 7% precision level was used to minimize the sample size. Consequently, the representative proportional sample size was calculated.

Accordingly, a total of 197 onion-producing farmers, 15 wholesalers, 50 retailers, and 50 consumers were selected and interviewed in the onion supply chain. Moreover, a key informant discussion was also conducted with agricultural office managers, development agents, and agricultural officers to augment the information supplied by respondents (Table 3.1.1). Respondents from the consumer chain were interviewed considering the market nearness and vicinity of the study area. They were interviewed about their daily experience with the quality and handling of the onion together. Key informant interviews with farmers, wholesalers, retailers, and development agents were conducted.

3.3.2.4. Conceptual framework

Based on the literature review and empirical evidences, the interrelationships of key variables including institutional, production, socioeconomics and demographic variables, farm and market related variables were considered in the present study (Figure 3.1.1). Sociodemographic variables were age, educational level, sex, and household size while production variables were access to improved onion varieties, access to fertilizer, and access to pesticides. Institutional factors like access to credit, participation in training, membership in cooperatives, farmer and farm-related variables (like land allocated to onions, onion farming experience), and market factors like (lagged onion market price, distance to nearest market, selling experience) influenced on market participation. Market participation leads to the level of participation (amount of onion sales) which in turn increased the household income.

3.3.2.5. Data analysis

The collected data was coded, entered and analysed using the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) software 16.0 version. By excluding the personal information (name of respondents), the collected data were encoded in SPSS for further analysis. The data were checked for possible outliers before running for statistical analysis. Preliminary descriptive analysis was carried out to identify inconsistencies and irregularities in data entry, which were then corrected by crosschecking the questionnaires. Microsoft Excel computer program was also used to draw graphs and error bars. A descriptive statistic like frequency, mean, percentage, and etc was used. Furthermore, inferential statistics (using the Chi-square test) was implemented to explore the significant association between socio-demographic, socio-economic aspects and onion production and postharvest management determinants. In addition, mean comparison techniques such as ANOVA and independent sample-t test were employed to compare the differences in onion production and postharvest management constraints among the supply chain actors or handling practices.

Table 3.1.1. Sample distribution in the selected districts and kebeles

District	Kebeles	Total onion producing households	Number of proportional sampled (7%)
Mecha	Kudmi	300	12
	Engutti	300	12
Fogera	Shina	1058	40
	Quhar Michael	850	33
Bahir Dar Zuria	Yigoma	1715	65
	Sebatamit	920	35
	Total	5143	197

Source: District agricultural office, (2021)

Figure 3.1.1. Conceptual framework of the onion supply chain

Source: Own conceptualization

3.1.3. Results and discussion

3.1.3.1. Socio-demographic characteristics

The results of the present finding indicated that male-headed households were the dominant producers (98.5%) and wholesalers of onion (100%), while female-headed households were dominant in the retailer (75.8%) and consumer (94%) chain. The results implying that the majority of the onion-producing and wholesaling households in the study area are male-headed (Table 3.1.2). The present finding is in line with Samuel Gebrselassie (2013), who indicated that female farmers were discouraged to own their farms/enterprises due to time scarcity, price fluctuations, and lack of working capitals, difficulties in selling of onions and other high-value crops in Ethiopia. Similarly, based on the study conducted on the banana value chain in Uganda all wholesalers in the study area were male headed (Kikulwe, 2018). Yebirzaf Yeshiwas and Esubalew Tadele (2021) also reported that women headed households were the dominant retailers (85%) in the fruit and vegetable business in Debre Markos town, Ethiopia.

Regarding the educational status of producers, five respondents (3.6%) were attended higher education and 18 (9.1%) were attended the grades 10 to 12, while 37 (18.8%) respondents were illiterate, and 83 (18.8 %) were able to read and write. On the other hand, the dominant supply chain actors in at the wholesaler, retailer, and consumer level were attained their secondary school (grade 10-12) as indicated in Table 3.1.2. Among the supply-chain actors, wholesalers and retailers had the better level of education, which showed that more educated youths prefer and compete for marketing of onion.

The survey results also showed that the average ages of the household-heads participated in production, wholesaler, retailer, and consumer were 44, 43, 37, and 38 years, respectively (Table 3.1.3). These indicate that the production and marketing of onion in the study area is dominated by adult and educated persons. Age is the primary demographic feature used to

characterize the working capabilities of the respondents. Similar results were reported by Habtamu Mossie *et al.* (2020) and Teklebrhan Abrha *et al.* (2020) who reported the average age of onion producers is around 44 years. Previous studies, for instance, confirmed that the average household size in the East Shewa Zone of Ethiopia was ranged from 5.4 to 5.5 (~6) family members (CSA, 2011; Gezai Abera *et al.*, 2020). Having a family with high household size has a positive impact on the production and handling of onions, and it also helps to reduce the cost of production and marketing as they use family labor during the production and marketing activities.

Table 3.1.2. Socio-demographic characteristics of onion supply chain actors in Mecha, Fogera, and Bahir Dar Zuria districts

Questions	Status	Producer (N=197)		Wholesaler N=(15)		Retailer N=(30)		Consumer N=(50)	
		Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Sex	Male	194	98.5	15	100	5	15.2	3	6
	Female	3	1.5	-	-	25	75.8	47	94
Marital status	Married	187	94.9	12	80.0	18	60.0	34	68
	Single	7	3.6	3	20.0	8	26.7	8	16
	Widowed	3	1.5	0	0	2	6.7	4	8
	Divorced	0	0	0	0	2	6.7	4	8
Education al status	Illiterate	37	18.8	0	0	0	0	7	14
	Read and write only	83	42.1	0	0	0	26.7	7	14
	1-6	31	15.7	1	6.7	0	10	4	8
	7-9	20	10.2	7	46.7	0	33.4	3	6.0
	10-12	18	9.1	7	46.7	0	20	16	32
	College level	1	0.5	0	0	0	10	8	16
	Higher education	7	3.6	0	0	0	0	5	10

Source: Own survey (2022) Where % =Percentage, Freq= Frequency

Table 3.1.3. Household age and size of major actors of onion value chain in the study area

Indicators	Producer N=197	Wholesaler N=15	Retailer N=30	Consumer N=50
	Mean SD	Mean SD	Mean SD	Mean SD
Age of the household head(year)	44.7±8.728	43.33±8.812	37.56±6.806	38±9.88
Total household size(number)	5.7±1.704	4.67±1.63	4.93±1.617	4.8±1.89

Socio-demographic characteristics and their association with onion production

The Chi-Square analysis was used to determine the significance of certain variables on onion production. The present study indicated that sex ($X^2 = 89.125$ and $p = 0.009^{**}$), age ($X^2 = 2957.97$ and $p = 0.000^{***}$) educational level ($X^2 = 406.61$ and $p = 0.04^*$) had a significant influence on onion production. Household size ($X^2 = 622.6$ and $p = 0.000^{**}$), production experience ($X^2 = 1212.57$ and $p = 0.000^{**}$), land covered by onion ($X^2 = 894.4$ and $p = 0.000^{**}$) also had significant effect on the production of onion (Table 3.1.4). Likewise, independent variables such as sex, education level, household size, production experience, and land covered by onion ($X^2 = 1101.73$ and $p = 0.000^{**}$) were found to be very highly significantly associated with the dependent variable onion yield. However, marital status ($X^2=112$ and $p = 0.686$) was not significantly associated with the dependent variable onion yield. As expected, educational level, household size and production experience positively influence onion production.

Table 3.1.4. Chi-square test results for the association between socio-demographic/economic factors and onion production among producers

Variable	Chi-square value(X^2)	d.f	P-value
Sex	89.125	60	0.009**
Age	2957.97	2520	0.000***
Educational level	406.61	360	0.04*
Marital status	112.026	120	0.686ns
Household size (number)	622.6	413	0.000***
Production experience (year)	1212.57	960	0.000***
Land covered by onion(ha)	1101.73	480	0.000***

Where, NS=non-significant, *, **and*** significance difference at 5%, and 1% probability levels, respectively. ha=hectare

Chi-square test on postharvest loss at indicated that the independent variables such as sex, age, education level, active household size, selling experience, amount purchased and storage duration have significant associations with postharvest loss at producers and

consumers levels. At the retailer's level, selling experience and storage duration are significantly associated (Table 3.1.5). As expected, age, educational level, household size, production experience, amount of onion bulbs harvested/purchased positively influence the postharvest loss along the supply chain. The present findings are in line with the results of other scholars who reported the increase of the spoilage percentage as the waiting time for selling increases, due to the longer exposure of the commodity to the fluctuating environmental condition (Kereth *et al.*, 2013; Adugna Debela *et al.*, 2011; Yebirzaf Yeshiwas and Esubalew Tadele, 2021). Similar results were reported as the age and sex of traders did not significantly influence the postharvest loss of fruits and vegetables at wholesalers, as also reported by Masood (2011); Yebirzaf Yeshiwas and Esubalew Tadele (2021). In contrast to the present findings, Gezai Abera *et al.* (2020) reported that gender has a significant contribution to the postharvest loss of tomatoes. At the wholesaler's level, independent variables did not significantly associate with the postharvest loss. At the consumer level, age and total household size influenced the likelihood of onion postharvest loss, while the amount purchased and storage duration significantly impacted the extent of the loss; however, educational level and marital status did not have a significant effect (Table 3.1.5), which is probably associated with relatively high level of education of the consumers.

Table 3.1.5. Chi-square results for postharvest loss of onion and Socio-demographic factors at supply chains

Variable	Producer			Wholesalers			Retailers			Consumers		
	X ²	d.f	Pvalue	X ²	d.f	Pvalue	X ²	d.f	Pvalue	X ²	d.f	Pvalue
Sex	99.87	66	0.005**	No statistics are computed because sex of the respondents is a constant.			16.000 a	15	0.709ns	4.331	11	0.959
Age	3561.55	2772	0.000***	138.7499	130	0.284	2.586E2a	240	0.195ns	3305.60	220	0.000**
Educational status	406.6	354	0.028**	38.750a	30	0.131	81.944a	90	0.715ns	70.694a	66	0.324ns
Marital status	122.11	132	0.72ns	11.875	10	0.294ns	40.602a	45	45.487a	45.487a	33	0.072ns
Total household size	554.48	462	0.002**	63.54a	60	0.353ns	107.22	90	0.104ns	157.35	88	0.000**
Producing/Selling experience	1212.32	1056	0.001**	75.417a	70	0.308	175.41a	135	0.011*			
Amount harvested/ purchased	10743.73	3960	0.000**	1.238E2a	100	0.05*	71.825	60	0.141ns	22.312E2a	132	0.000**
Storage duration				55.417a	50	0.278ns	48.018a	32	0.034*	2.654E2a	156	0.000**

NS=Non-significant, *, **and*** significance difference at 5%, and 1%, probability levels respectively

Farmer`s knowledge on onion production practices in the study areas

The present result indicated that households in the study districts have diversified income sources. A mixed type of farming including the production of cereal, and vegetable crops, and rearing animals were the major source of income of the farmers (Table 3.1.6).

Among the vegetable crops, onion was the primary source of income and shared 86.6% of household`s income followed by tomato (8.1%), potato (4.1%), head cabbage (0.5%), pepper (0.5%), and papaya (Table 3.1.6 and Appendix Figure 3.1.1).

Approximately 64% of respondents cultivated onions on their own land, while 22.8% grew onions on family-owned land (Table 3.1.6). Relatively farmers produce their onions on rental land are covered a larger area. In contrast to the present study, Baloch *et al.* (2014) reported 31.6% of onion farmers have ownership and the remaining 68.4% produce onions on rental land.

The study results also indicated that the majority of onion producers 172 (87.3%) produced onion once per year while 25 (12.7%) of the respondents produced twice per year using irrigation in the study area. Onion producing households in the study area owned a total average of 1.09 ± 0.47 ha cultivated land. Of which about 0.49 ± 0.297 ha of land was covered with onion. While the minimum land allocated for onion was 0.125 ha and the maximum was 2ha (Table 3.1.6). This implies that onion farming becomes a promising venture. Mixed farming provides resilience to farmers against climatic and market shocks, and its predominance in Ethiopia supports the role of onion production in complementing other farming practices to enhance food security and income (Gebru Yohannes *et al.*, 2020). Onions, as a high-value cash crop, generate substantial income even on small plots of land, playing a significant role in improving rural livelihoods (Mohammed Ali *et al.*, 2019).

Despite Ethiopia's small average farm size, typically less than one hectare, onion production remains profitable due to its high yield potential and suitability for double cropping during the irrigation season (Alemayehu Gebre et al., 2018). This practice not only boosts annual yields but also stabilizes income, as onions thrive under irrigation systems (Bekele Tadesse and Kebede Abebe, 2021).

Table 3.1.6. Income sources and annual onion production cycle and by using irrigation

Questioners		Frequency	Percentage
Main income sources	Vegetable production	43	21.8
	Cereals production	2	1.0
	Mixed	152	77.2
Comparative income source from vegetables	Onion	171	86.8
	Tomato	16	8.1
	Potato	8	4.1
	Cabbage	1	0.5
	Pepper	1	0.5
Means of land acquisitions	Owned	126	64.0
	Gift	17	8.6
	Family	45	22.8
	Rented	3	1.5
	Inherited	6	3.0
Onion production per year by using irrigation	Once	172	87.3
	Twice	25	12.7
Land covered by onion in ha	Mean	Minimum	Maximum
	0.49	0.125	2.000

Source: own survey (2022)

Onion seedling management and transplanting practices

The result revealed that all respondents in the study area produced onions by transplanting. More than 80% (158) of the respondents transplanted onion seedlings at the age ranging from 40-50 days after seed sowing. Transplanting onion seedlings within this age range allows for the development of robust root systems and minimizes transplanting shock, which are crucial for better field establishment. Younger seedlings (less than 40 days) are often too fragile to withstand transplanting stress, while older seedlings (beyond 50 days) may exhibit reduced vigor and adaptability to field conditions. The observed practice demonstrates the farmers' understanding of the critical timing needed to balance seedling vigor and ease of handling during transplanting.

Trimming of seedlings 3–4 days before transplanting and during transplanting was a common practice (63.5%) in onion production in the study area. On the other hand, 72 respondents (36.5%) did not trim the tops of seedlings (Table 3.1.7). According to the farmers, trimming of longer leaves is useful for ease of transplanting, uniformity of seedling and avoiding seedling lodging. It also enhances field establishment and initiation of new growth. From a scientific perspective, trimming the seedlings serves to reduce transplanting stress by minimizing the amount of leaf area, which in turn reduces water loss through transpiration. The reduction in leaf area also helps the seedlings focus energy on root development and adaptation to the new field conditions, fostering quicker establishment (Ali Mohammed et al., 2019). Additionally, trimming promotes uniformity, ensuring that all seedlings are of similar size and structure, which is essential for efficient spacing and growth. Studies by Gebru Yohannes et al. (2020) have shown that uniform seedling size leads to better crop performance, as it reduces competition among plants for resources.

Farmers trim their seedlings to produce suitable and uniform seedlings for transplanting, to avoid lodging of vigorous grown seedlings, to hasten field establishment after transplanting, to initiate/rejuvenate new leaf regrowth, and to avoid pre-translating bulb development.

The present survey results also indicated that the planting distance between irrigation furrows, between rows, and plants varies from one farmer to another. About 36 of the respondents (18.6%) transplanted onion seedlings through broadcast planting, which is mostly practiced in Fogera district. Farmers believe that this type of transplanting demands less labor during planting and weeding, is simple to irrigate, and is used to save water and labor. The minimum planting distances implemented by farmers were 10 cm, 10 cm, and 3 cm between the irrigation furrow, row, and plants, respectively while the maximum were 60 cm, 40 cm, and 7 cm between furrows, rows, and plants, respectively. The majority of farmers transplanted the onion seedlings using 5 cm intra row. The three (3) cm intra-row spacing is very narrow for onions, which increases the number of unmarketable small bulbs.

A similar result was observed by Nikus Olani, and Mulugeta Fikre (2010); Habtamu Tegen *et al.* (2016) who reported 6 cm as optimum intra-row spacing to obtain the highest marketable bulb yield of onion with the maximum number of medium-sized bulbs.

Table 3.1.7. Transplanting stage and trimming practices of onion seedlings in the study districts

Questioners	Status	Producer (N=197)	
		Frequency	Percentage
Stage of transplanting	30 Days	8	4.1
	35 Days	12	6.1
	40 Days	48	24.4
	45 Days	56	28.4
	50 Days	54	27.4
	55 Days	13	6.6
	60 Days	6	3.0
Practice of trimming seedlings	Yes	125	63.5
	No	72	36.5

Irrigation access, sources and associated problems

In the study area, onion production was entirely carried out during the offseason using irrigation (Table 3.1.8). However, the access to irrigation was varied from one farmer to the other. From the total respondents about 77 (77%) in the Bahir Dar Zuria district, and 4 (16.7) at Mecha district were accessing sufficient irrigation water. They apply irrigation water in 7–14 days and 7–16 days interval at Bahir Dar Zuria and Mecha districts, respectively. However, at the Fogera district all respondents did not get sufficient irrigation water. They apply irrigation water every 15 days at an early stage (up to one month of transplanting) and every 7–10 days one month after transplanting. The longer irrigation interval at Fogera district was because the soil is vertisol, the better capacity to hold water (Table 3.1.8). However, despite the soil’s water-holding capacity, the insufficient irrigation access remains a challenge for optimal crop growth. Agumas Yideg (2019) reported similar results were in, onion producers are suffered from irrigation water shortage in Fogera district.

As illustrated in Fig. 3.1.2, the major irrigation water sources for the production of onion in the study area are rivers, dams and groundwater. In Bahir Dar Zuria district Andassa, Abay, Tikurit, Yeshmet, and Yizana are the major irrigation sources. In Mecha district, the only irrigation source for the production of onion was Koga Irrigation Dam while in Fogera district, Gumara and Guanta Rivers and groundwater are the major irrigation water sources. There is sufficient irrigation water in the Andassa kebele, and in fact, the area experiences flooding due to an excess of available water. The primary sources of irrigation water in Andassa are the Abay and Tikurit rivers (Figure 3.1.2). Generally, onion production in Fogera and Mecha districts frequently encountered shortage of irrigation water, especially during the months March and April in relation to the use of irrigation. The major reason for shortage of irrigation water in Fogera district is the poor infrastructure in the irrigation scheme where no primary and secondary channels are constructed. Farmers are using pumps to deliver water to their farms, which increases the cost of production due to high price of fuel and labor. Moreover, water resource competition is the other problem in Fogera district. Currently more farmers are producing tef and wheat using irrigation water, which contribute the scarcity of water for onion production. The main cause of irrigation water scarcity in North Mecha district is the delayed release from the source/dam.

Table 3.1.8. Irrigation practices in the study districts

Questioners		B/Dar Zuria (N=100)		Mecha (N=24)		Fogera (N=73)	
		Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Access to sufficient irrigation water	Yes	77	77.0	4	16.7	0	0
	No	23	23.0	20	83.3	100	100
		7	49	49.0	10	41.7	
Irrigation frequency (days)	8	17	17.0				
	10	13	13.0	9	37.5	25	34.2
	12	12	12.0	3	12.5	1	1.4
	13	6	6.0			1	1.4
	14	3	3.0				
	15			1	4.2	10	13.7
	16			1	4.2		
	Applied every 15 days during the early transplanting stage and every 10 days MAT					14	19.2

Applied every 15 days during the early transplanting stage and 7 days MAT	14	19.2
Applied every 15 days early and 8 days MAT	8	11.0

Where, Freq= frequency; % = Percentage; MAT= Months after Transplanting

Figure 3.1.2. Major irrigation water sources for irrigated onion production in the study area

Use of hybrid onion variety and access to their seeds

The use of varieties with better quality is a basic input and foundation for enhanced productivity and longer storage period. Hybrid crops including onion with high yielding capacity play an important role in supporting global food security. They produce higher yields and are often more resistant than open pollinated varieties to disease and climate stress. In the study area, farmers have experiences in using hybrid onion varieties. About 26 (13.2%) of the respondents are producing hybrid onion varieties such as Jambar, Russet, and Red Coach. The varieties are produced on large areas as well as in the demonstration plots (Table 3.1.9 and Appendix Figure 3.2.2). On the other hand, 86.8% of the respondents (171) did not producing hybrid onion varieties associated with high cost of seeds, lack of extension advices, and lack of awareness (Table 3.1.9). Since the start of hybrid onion production, three years ago, the proportion of farmers that started hybrid onion production

is in increasing trend. Among the hybrid onion producing farmers, about 7.69% of the respondents started the production in 2018 production season while 80.76% of the respondents started during the 2020 production season (Figure 3.1.3a). The trend suggests that with better awareness and improved extension advice, more farmers are likely to adopt the production of hybrid onion varieties in the future. Due to their higher yield potential, high market demand and prolonged shelf life (Figure 3.1.3b), the respondents will continue the production of hybrid onion varieties in the near future. Among the onion producers, 4.56 % of the respondents preferred the Jambar variety, followed by 4.06% who favored the Russet variety. Additionally, 4.56% of respondents preferred a combination of Jambar, Russet, and Red Coach varieties.

Access to quality seed for onion producers is essential to increase crop productivity. In the study area, 34 (17.3%) respondents have sufficient access to hybrid seed varieties. However, 163 (82.7%) respondents have no information about the accessibility or inaccessibility of seeds. According to the respondents, local market and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) were the main seed/seedling sources of hybrid onion varieties where SNV project was the major seed/seedling supplies as explained by the District Agriculture Officers (Table 3.1.10).

Table 3.1.9. Hybrid onion varieties grown by onion producers in the study areas and constraints

Questioners	Options	Frequency	Percentage
Growing hybrid onion varieties	Yes	26	13.2
	No	171	86.8
Name of varieties	Jambar	9	
	Red Coach	7	
	Russet	17	
Extent of production	Production in large areas	26	
	At demonstration plot	4	
Reasons for not using hybrid onion varieties	High cost of the seeds	55	27.9
	Lack of extension advice	53	26.9
	Lack of awareness	63	32.0

Table 3.1.10. Access for hybrid onion varieties and sources of seeds

Questioners		Frequency	Percentage
		(N=197)	
Sufficient access for hybrid varieties	Yes	34	17.3
	No/DHI	163	82.7
Sources of hybrid onion seeds	Market	10	5.1
	NGOs	16	8.1
Way of getting seeds	Purchase	11	5.6
	Gift	15	7.6

Figure 3.1.3. (a) Percentage of farmers started hybrid onion production and (b) farmer`s preference for hybrid variety and associated reasons

Access and supply of fertilizer, pesticides and credit

The present study indicated that farmers were not able to access fertilizers timely and adequately from the formal suppliers such as cooperatives. About 6.1% of the respondents obtained fertilizers from cooperatives, while 93.9% of the respondents purchased fertilizers from the local markets with high prices due to inadequate supply of fertilizers by the cooperatives. The farmers also purchased pesticides from suppliers at the nearby markets (Table 3.1.11).

The reasons for inadequate access to fertilizers are mostly due to supply shortage at country or regional level, which is determined by the price and availability in the international markets. Delayed supply and unfair distribution within the country and region may also create problems in the accessibility of the fertilizers. Most of the farmers purchased

fertilizers from local traders with the highest price to solve the accessibility of fertilizers (Table 3.1.11). Some farmers applied the quantity of fertilizers they got from cooperatives and additionally used organic fertilizers like compost as compensation to the remaining amount of inorganic fertilizers. Others used the saved fertilizers from the previous cropping season and/or purchased the fertilizers in advance before the onion growing season is approaching.

Credit facility access enhances the financial capacity of onion producers which enables them to purchase required production inputs such as improved varieties of seed, chemical fertilizers, pesticides, insecticides, fuel, etc. As a result, access to credit in the study area was not well practiced, as a result, the farmer's areas purchased all farm inputs in cash.

Table 3.1.11. Fertilizer and pesticide access in the study area

Questioners		Frequency (N=197)	Percentage
Access for fertilizer in terms of time and adequacy	Yes	2	1.0
	No	192	97.5
Sources of fertilizer	Cooperatives	12	6.1
	Local market and Cooperatives	185	93.9
Source of pesticide	Local market	197	100
Reasons for inadequate access	Supply shortage, high-cost urea	197	100
Measures taken by farmers to solve the accessibility of fertilizers	Addressing the amount, we get and using organic fertilizer	30	15.1
	Purchasing at high prices from merchants	179	90.5
	Early purchasing and storage	31	15.7
	Purchasing form local market and use of organic fertilizer	9	4.6
	Use of organic fertilizers alone	14	7.1

Fertilizer and pesticide application rate

High and better yield can only be achieved with the application of optimum rates of fertilizers and the proper use of pesticides. The use of optimum nitrogen rate also increases the total yield, and average bulb size and reduces the percentage of bolting (Aklilu Nigussie *et al.*, 2015). In the study area, all respondents were applying chemical fertilizer/synthetic fertilizers (NPS or NPSB and Urea), and organic fertilizers such as compost and animal manure for onion production. The quantity of fertilizers and chemicals applied varied among respondents. Most respondents (77.7%) used a combination of NPS or NPSB and urea fertilizers for onion production, while 14.2% used only NPS or NPSB, and 7.1% applied a mix of urea, NPS or NPSB, and organic fertilizers (Table 3.1.12).

In the study area, NPS/B is the primary source of nutrients for onion production. However, most respondents (193 or 98%) applied it incorrectly. They also noted that soil fertility decreases annually, requiring increasing amounts of fertilizer. Without applying higher rates of fertilizer, they do not expect to achieve better yields. Farmers in the study area used urea and NPS/NPSB at the ranges of 25-350 kg ha⁻¹ and 25-500 kg ha⁻¹, respectively, for the production of onion with the mean values of 105 kg ha⁻¹ and 143 kg ha⁻¹ in the same order (Figure 3.1.4b). Accordingly, farmers in the study area applied about 5.04% more urea and only 72.5% of the national blanket recommended NPS/NPSB fertilizer rates, which are 100 kg ha⁻¹ urea and 200 kg ha⁻¹ NPSB.

The figure 3.1.4a illustrates the variation in organic fertilizer application rates (in quintals per hectare) among respondents. The most frequent application rate is 20 quintals per hectare, with some respondents applying between 10 and 50 quintals per hectare. This indicates a moderate range of organic fertilizer usage.

The primary reasons for applying slightly more urea but less NPS or NPSB and agrochemicals than the recommended rates include declining soil fertility, limited awareness among farmers, and reduced effectiveness of agro-chemicals. Farmers

emphasized that declining soil fertility has led to increased reliance on urea to maintain yields, while limited accessibility to fertilizers has resulted in the underutilization of NPS or NPSB.

The results indicate that the primary drawback of the recommended fertilizer rate is low yield, reported by the majority of respondents (140). This is followed by issues related to adequate availability but supply problems, cited by 55 respondents. Smaller proportions of farmers highlighted concerns such as reduced efficacy of chemicals (11), frequent pesticide variation (9), and inaccessibility (5). These findings suggest that while fertilizer availability and supply inconsistencies are notable, the major concern remains the inability to achieve optimal yields.

Table 3.1.12. Type of fertilizers used by respondents in the study area

Questioners	Frequency (N=197)	Percentage
Use of fertilizer	Yes	197 100.0
Type of fertilizer used	NPS or NPSB	28 14.2
	NPS or NPSB and Urea	153 77.7
	NPS or NPSB, Urea	14 7.1
	Organic	
	NPS and organic fertilizer	2 1.0
Proper application of recommended fertilizer and chemical rate	Yes	4 2.0
	No (higher and lower)	193 98.0

Figure 3.1.4. Rates of organic (a) and inorganic (b) fertilizers applied by onion growing farmers

Major constraints of onion production

The current survey result indicated that the average yield of onion in the study area was 16 t ha⁻¹, which is better than the average onion yield in Amhara National Regional State (11.67 t ha⁻¹) reported by CSA (2017). Nevertheless, the productivity of onion in the study area is below the world average of 21.1 t ha⁻¹ (FAO, 2022). According to the data of the Central Statistical Authority, the area allocated for the production of onion in Ethiopia is in increasing trend from 1995 EC/2001 to 2015 EC/2021 while the productivity decreased in the same years (Figure 3.1.5).

In this regard, onion growers reported multiple production constraints including absence of storable onion varieties and associated high postharvest losses, shortage and high costs of fertilizers and other farm inputs and lack of infrastructures including roads and storage facilities (Figure 3.1.5). Costs of farm inputs like fertilizer, pesticides, and fuel negatively influence the production of onion and its supply to market.

The results of the present study are in line with the findings of Kassa Getu and Ahmed Ibrahim (2018) who indicated that high cost of inputs, and weak market linkage are the major constraints that hinder onion productivity. The results are also in agreement with the study conducted by Almaz Giziaw (2014) who reported that the onion and tomato value chain is complicated associated with lack of production and marketing skills.

Figure 3.1.6. Onion production trend in Ethiopia (1995EC/2001 to 2015EC/2021)

Source; CSA (2020)

Figure 3.1.7. Major onion production constraints in the study area

Disease and insect pests

In the study area, diseases and insect pest infestation were very high. Powdery mildew (*Leveillula taurica*), Downy mildew (*Peronospora destructor*) (Mech), and Black fungus and Thrips (*Thrips tabaci*) were the major diseases and insect pest of onion identified by the farmers and district extension officers in the study area. Farmers used different kinds of chemicals for the management of onion pests including Omaxis as preventive chemical for disease, the fungicide Redomil Gold for the control powdery mildew, Ajanta (Deltamethrin) and Prostar 70 WP for the management of Thrips. During chemical application, the farmers were not wearing safety clothes (Table 3.1.13).

Table 3.1.13. Major diseases in the study area

Questioners	Frequency (N=197)	%
Major diseases		
Downy mildew (<i>Peronospora destructor</i>) Mech (local name)	44	22.3
Powdery Mildew (<i>Leveillula taurica</i>)	151	76.6
Black fungus (Mold)	30	15.2
Major insect pests		
Thrips (<i>Thrips tabaci</i>)	197	100.0

Market price

Farmers grow onion for market supply and to get cash. However, due to its perishability nature, production is seriously affected by price fluctuations every year. The present result indicated that the minimum lagged price of onion during peak harvesting time was one birr per kilogram, while during the offseason, it was 13 Birr kg⁻¹. The maximum lagged price during peak harvesting time was seven Birr kg⁻¹, whereas during the offseason, it reached 32 Birr kg⁻¹. Due to poor storage facilities and lack of storable onion varieties, the farmers did not benefited from the increased onion prices at the offseason (Table 3.1.14). These results are in line with the findings of Almaz Giziew *et al.* (2014) who reported that onion production is affected by price fluctuations and unfair prices.

Table 3.1.14. Onion price in the study area

Indicators	Producer N=(197)		
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean _ SD
The market price of onion at its pick harvesting season in 2020 Birr/Q	0.1	7	1.9±1.009
The market price of onions per kilogram during the off-season (summer) in 2020.	13	32	21.62±5.59574
	Frequency (N=197)		%
Trend of onion price	Increasing	197	100
Benefit of farmers from the increased onion price	Yes	4	2.0
	No	193	98.0

Where Q=quintal

Role of Brokers in marketing of onions

In the study area, there are middlemen (brokers) that facilitate the marketing process and provide information in the chain, mainly between farmers and wholesalers. The broker also checks the quality of the onion bulbs and supervises the onion harvesting process. They play as a major actor in the determination of onion prices between the farmers and wholesalers. According to the respondents, the brokers in most cases determined the price in favour of the wholeseller and underestimate the selling price of onion. Due to the

perishable nature of the crop, Brokers put pressure on producers to sell their onions at low prices. In some cases, they created problems in the payment of the money when they took the onions in credit basis. According to the information of the respondents, farmers did not store onion for a long period of time (Table 3.1.15). Brokers play a key role in agricultural marketing by linking farmers to buyers, facilitating price negotiations, and managing logistics, particularly for perishable goods. They reduce market uncertainties by providing market information and sometimes offering credit to farmers. However, brokers may exploit farmers through unfair pricing, high commissions, and price manipulation, which limits farmers' bargaining power.

Table 3.1.15. The role of brokers/ middle man

Questioners		Frequency (N=197)	%
Availability of brokers	Yes	197	100
Who decide the selling price	Yourself	1	0.5
	Brokers	179	90.9
	Market demand and supply	9	4.6
	By negotiation	8	4.1
Involvement of brokers with regard to selling price	Negotiating the market	32	
	Contacting sellers and buyers	2	
	Underestimation of the price	180	
	Provision of credit	17	
	Disrupt the link b/n farmers and merchant	15	
Problems created by brokers with regard to onion market	Took to limited client, incorrect weighing of product, Wrong price information	197	100.0

3.1.3.3. Harvesting and postharvest handling practices in the onion supply chains

Post-harvest handling practices at farm level

Harvesting

The stage of maturity is one of the most important factors determining crop quality and storability/shelf life. Harvesting immature onion bulbs can lead to bruising, hastened

sprouting time, and highest weight loss. Onions are usually harvested when the neck of onion bulbs fails down to the ground. Manual harvesting is the most common practice in the study area. The majority of onion producers 120 (60.9%) responded that onion harvesting is done based on bulb maturity, when the leaf's color changed from deep green to light green or yellowish. In the study area, almost all onion producers harvested their produce at any time of the day by digging with human power by using a hoe (*Ankassie, Mekotkocha*) which damages bulbs during digging and hastens the spoilage rate of bulbs.

Onion bulbs are susceptible to high storage losses as they contain a high amount of water. Once harvested, their internally stored food and water decline over time. As a result, bulbs are subject to sprouting, rotting, and shrinkage losses during storage. Curing techniques help to improve the shelf life (storage quality) of onion, which in turn increases the return from onion production and stabilizes the market situation. In the present study, most of the farmers don't practice curing/drying after harvesting. After harvesting, the bulbs are typically left in the field for several days, often in a shaded, well-ventilated area, to dry, allowing the outer layers of the onion skins to become papery and the necks of the bulbs to tighten. However, in the study area only 7% of the respondents cured the harvested onion bulbs for five days in the production field, while the remaining respondents did not practice curing (Table 3.1.16).

Different types of maturity indices were used by the farmers to determine the maturity stage of onion in the study area. Among the indices are leaf drooping/drying, leaf color change, neck fail, days after transplanting (90–120), market demand, bolting, high pungency of leaves during leaf cutting, and crack of the soil around the bulb (Figure 3.1.7). Farmers in the study area use some scientifically valid maturity indicators, such as leaf color change and neck failure, to determine onion readiness for harvest. However, their manual harvesting methods often damage the bulbs, leading to spoilage. The lack of curing reflects a gap in

awareness about its importance for improving storage quality. Educating farmers on proper post-harvest handling, including curing, could improve onion quality and market stability.

Table 3.1.16. Harvesting practices of onion in the study area

Questioners		Frequency (N=197)	%
Criterion for determining the date of harvesting	Maturity	120	60.9
	Market price	8	4.1
	Maturity and market price	69	35.0
Harvesting time	Anytime/the whole day	197	100.0
Method of harvesting	Pulling by hand	9	4.6
	Digging by hoe/ <i>Ankassie</i>	176	89.3
	Digging and hand pulling	12	6.1
Time of top removal	5 days after harvesting	7	3.6
	At the point of sell	66	33.5
	Immediately after harvest	124	62.9

Figure 3.1.8. Methods used for harvesting stage determination of onion practiced by farmers

Various cultural practices were applied before harvesting, including toppling, irrigating fields a few days prior to harvest, stopping irrigation, and reducing irrigation frequencies (Figure 3.1.8). Toppling was applied to enhance bulb quality and filling, and to increase bulb weight by translocating food from the leaf part to the bulb and to stopping further vegetative growth. Farmers demonstrate a practical understanding of how irrigation affects onion quality, recognizing that pre-harvest irrigation improves bulb weight, color, and yield. They also understand that reducing or stopping irrigation helps prevent rotting, sprouting, and strengthens bulb skin. These practices reflect a solid grasp of water management for

better onion production. However, there may be room for improvement in optimizing the timing and application of these techniques. Further education could enhance their knowledge and overall productivity.

Figure 3.1.9. Cultural practices applied by farmers before onion harvesting

Transportation

According to the survey, open truck was mostly used by whole sellers, local collectors, and retailers for the transportation of onion. On the other hand, farmers used animal driven cart and human labour to deliver onion to the market. All onion producers in the study area faced significant market challenges, as highlighted in Table 3.1.17. These issues included price fluctuations, lack of organized markets, and limited bargaining power due to dependence on middlemen. The absence of proper storage facilities exacerbated the problem, forcing farmers to sell immediately after harvest at low prices. Moreover, poor market information hindered their ability to make informed decisions about when and where to sell, resulting in reduced profitability. These challenges emphasize the need for improved marketing strategies, such as cooperative marketing, better storage solutions, and access to reliable market data, to enhance producers' incomes and market stability. Aemro Worku and Ali Ulku (2022) reported similar practices as the primary mode of transportation to deliver the harvested onions to the nearest market place where animal driven cart (62.8%) followed by truck (19.7%) and labor (17.5%) were the major once. According to the observations made during the survey, road access of the study area is poor and not suitable, which causes

bruising and mechanical damages through vibration leading to high of postharvest losses of onion bulbs. In this regard, Idah *et al.* (2007) reported that vibration due to roughness of roads is one of the major causes of postharvest losses of fruits and vegetables.

Table 3.1.17. Marketing problems in onion produce

Questioners		Frequency	%
Type of transport used	Animal driven cart	59	
	Human labor	24	
	Open Track	127	
Presence of market problems with regard to onion price	Yes	197	100.0
Storing onion bulbs for late selling	Yes	35	17.8
	No	162	82.2
Storage duration (N =35)	5 days	7	3.6
	6 days	12	6.1
	1 week	10	5
	2 weeks	3	1.5
	2 months by renting storage room	2	1

Marketing and storage problem of onion at farm level

The production of onion in the study area is during the irrigation season that leads over-saturation of the market and reduction of the prices in the production season. On the other hand, only 17.8% respondents were able to store the onion bulbs for five days to two months for late selling at a better price. Most of the farmers (82.2%) prefer to sell their produces immediately after harvest with the current market prices, which are mostly unsatisfactory and low. These situations significantly reduce the income of the farmers and their motivation towards the production onion in the next production season. The possible reasons for not storing onion by farmers could be poor storability of onion varieties, lack of affordable storage technologies and high postharvest losses due to inappropriate curing and handling practices. Emana Bezabih (2017) reported that over 30% of postharvest losses of vegetables in Ethiopia were attributed mainly to inadequate handling practices, inefficient marketing systems, insufficient storage facilities, and substandard transportation infrastructure.

Postharvest handling practices and losses

Inadequate postharvest management of onions in the study area led to significant losses. Poor agronomic practices, improper sorting, packaging, transportation, and lack of storage facilities contributed to mechanical damage, sprouting, and rotting. During the 2020 cropping season, unsuitable bulbs accounted for 2–100% of harvested produce, particularly when harvesting was delayed due to low market prices (Figure 3.1.9). Onions were packed in poorly ventilated burlap sacks, exposed to harsh sunlight, and overloaded during transport, increasing damage and losses (Table 3.1.18).

Figure 3.1.10. Percentage of onion bulbs deemed unsuitable for market due to post-harvest losses

Table 3.1.18. Post-harvest handling practice of onion at farm level

Questions	Response	Frequency(N=197)	%
Is there any post-harvest loss?	Yes	197	100.0
What type of container do you use for marketing onions?	Burlap sack (100 kg)	197	100.0
What storage method or material do you use at home?	Jute/burlap bag	87	44.2
	Spread on ground	88	44.7
	Shelf	10	5.1
	Field	11	6.1
Who are your main customers for selling onions?	Cooperatives	6	3.0
	Wholesalers	177	94.3
	Local collectors	11	5.6
	Retailers	3	1.5

	Consumers	2	1.0
Why do you prefer selling to these buyers?	Better price	2	1.0
	Large volume of purchase	166	84.3
	No option	29	14.7
Are marketing cooperatives available to collect harvested onions?	Yes	62	31.5
	No	135	68.5
Are you interested in selling your onions through cooperatives?	Yes	188	95.4
	No	9	4.6
Do you think onion farming is profitable?	Yes, except market problem and poor storage period of varieties	197	100
How do you get information about buyers/transporters?	Through brokers	197	100.0

Selling experience and marketing practices of wholesaler and retailer of onion

Producers (local collectors) were the sole suppliers of onions to the wholesalers while retailers were bought the onion bulbs from wholesalers and producers. Both wholesalers (73.3%) and retailers (100%) received sample onion bulbs before the buying contract. However, the buyers observed often quality differences between the sampled and delivered onion bulbs (Table 3.1.19). Furthermore, all the wholesalers and retailers reported experiencing losses during the selling and storage of onions, including spoilage, shrinkage, and physical damage to the bulbs. On average, 4.5% of onion bulbs at wholesalers and 13.93% at retailers are deemed unsuitable for sale (Table 3.1.20; Appendix Figure 3.1.3. and Appendix Figure 3.1.4).

The widespread use of burlap sacks as primary packaging materials is attributed to their affordability and accessibility (Table 3.1.21). However, these sacks lack adequate ventilation, leading to issues like sprouting and rotting of onion bulbs. Kader and Rolle (2004) highlighted that sack containers for fruits and vegetables can trap heat generated by metabolic reactions, accelerating mechanical damage and increasing susceptibility to microbial attacks.

Table 3.1.19. Onion handling information of wholesalers and retailers

Questioners		Wholesalers(N=15)		Retailers(N=30)	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Sources of onion bulbs	Producers (local collectors)	15	100		
	Wholesalers			15	50
	Wholesalers + producers			15	50
Presence of quality problem	Yes	15	100.0	30	100.0
Type of problems/issues	Damaged	4	39.9	19	63.3
	Size (under sized)	4	26.7	19	63.3
	Disease	4	26.6	10	33.3
	Sprouting	4	26.7	9	30
	Decay	3	20	28	93.3
	Immature bulbs	6	40	7	23.3
	Shriveling			2	6.7
Evaluation of samples of the onions before buying them	Yes	11	73.3	30	100
	No	4	26.7		

Table 3.1.20. Percentage of bulbs unfit for sale at wholesaler and retailer levels

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation
Whole sellers	2%	7%	4.5	1.43
Retailers	5%	25%	13.93	7.65

Table 3.1.21. Marketing and storage practices of wholesalers and retailers of onion

Questioners		Wholesalers(N=15)		Retailers(N=30)	
		Freq	%	Freq	%
Do you sell all the bought onions	No	15	100.0	30	100
Are there any storage possibilities for onions at the market?	Yes	15	100.0	30	100.0
How many days are required to finish selling of your onion bulbs? _____ days	4			6	20.0
	5	2	13.3	12	40.0
	6	3	20.0	7	23.3
	7	7	46.7	4	13.3
	8	3	20.0	1	3.3
What do you do with unmarketable onions?	Throwing	15	100.0	30	100
What do you do to reduce postharvest losses?	Sorting, ventilation	15	100	25	83.3
	Spreading during night			2	6.7
	Nothing			3	10.0
	4 days			1	3.3

How often do you purchase new onions from suppliers? _____ days.	5 days			3	10.0
	6 days			18	60.0
	every week	3	20	8	26.7
	depends on market demand	11	73.3		
	Up on finishing	1	6.7		
How do you store onions?	Using Jute bag	6	40.0	30	100
	Heaping on the floor	6	40.0		
	Using wooden box	3	20.0		
What type of packaging material do you use to transport onions to the market?	Jute/Burlap sack	15	100.0	30	100

Where, Freq = frequency

Causes of postharvest loss and strategies to be implemented to minimize losses at wholesaler and retailer chain

The result revealed that at the retailer level, all respondents indicated that there is postharvest loss. The major causes for loss are bruising, sprouting, damage during harvesting and transport, decay, disease, mechanical damage, damage during harvesting, transportation, perishability nature, rotting, mechanical damage and shrivelling (Figure 3.1.10). Market problems are delayed sales, while improper sorting practices, rotting due to inadequate drying, pest infestations, and a lack of awareness of proper postharvest practices. Addressing these challenges requires improved infrastructure, such as ventilated and moisture-controlled storage facilities, training in handling and sorting techniques, and better market access. Scheduling harvests during dry periods and reducing dependency on brokers can also mitigate losses. Coordinated efforts across the value chain are essential to reduce these losses and ensure sustainable production.

Figure 3.1.11. Main reasons for the postharvest loss of onion

To minimize losses, farmers adopted strategies such as immediate sales, delaying top removal, adjusting planting times, adjusting planting time, and constructing storage rooms (Figure 3.1.11). Despite these efforts, 100% of respondents used burlap sacks for marketing. For home storage, 44.7% spread bulbs on the ground, 44.2% used jute sacks, and 6.1% and 5.1% utilized on-field and shelf storage, respectively (Table 3.1.18).

Figure 3.1.12. Measures that farmers are practicing to minimize loss after harvest

The survey results indicated that wholesaler and retailer respondents had 5 years-15 years and 4 year-13 years of experiences in buying and selling of onion (Figures 3.1.12a and b).

Despite their extensive experience, survey observations revealed that wholesalers and retailers lack adequate knowledge in post-harvest handling practice.

Figure 3.1.13. a. Experience in selling at the wholesaler b. Experience in selling at the retailers

Quantity of onions purchased and duration of storage

The survey results indicated that wholesalers bought 10-70.2 quintals of onion at a time while retailers 0.25-1.0 quintals. Traders stored the onion bulbs by spreading or heaping on the ground floor and using wooden box (Figures 3.1.13a, b and c). The traders also indicate that the demand for onion is year-round, but they face an onion supply shortage from May to October. Because there is no practice of storage of bulbs for late selling and there is no production during this month's/production seasonality. During these seasons, the price of onion increases above 3-fold compared with pick harvesting seasons such as February to March at pick harvesting season, the price falls because of the large supply as all farmers plant at similar planting times.

Figure 3.1.14. (a) Amount bought and (b) method of storage at wholesaler level; (c) Quantity of onions purchased at a time by retailers (in Quintals)

Mode of transportation of onions at wholesalers and retailer's level

In this study, there were different modes of transportation used by the traders of onion from farm to marketing chain. The majority of the onion wholesalers (86.7%) transport their produce from the farm to the local markets by using an open FSR truck. While 13.3% of wholesalers used open Isuzu trucks. The difference between the transportation methods is the amount of onions load. FSR trucks can load 50-80 quintal fresh onions, while Isuzu trucks can load 40-60 quinatl. Among retailers, 36.7% were transporting onion by using *careta*, 30% by using *hand cart*, 23.3% by using *animal-driven cart* and 13.3% by using the motor. As Rehman *et al.* (2007) explained that ultimate care should be given to the transportation of the produce to avoid mechanical injury and damage and deterioration of the produce. For wholesalers, on loading of the transportation process, there is postharvest loss, caused by bruising, crashing, mechanical damage, and high heat generated in the bulbs. Retailers during transportation, they did not record any loss of bulbs because short-distance transport and small volume transportation (Table 3.1.23). In addition, retailers during storage were frequently ventilating the bulbs, sorted, discarded the rotten bulbs, and sold them at relatively discount prices. About 80% of wholesalers indicate that they have no contact with farmers, all contacts are through brokers, and the remaining 20% of farmers can have contact with farmers. The wholesalers do not have any information about the onion

varieties they bought. They got information about transportation trucks also through brokers (Table 3.1.24).

Table 3.1.22. Methods of transportation at wholesalers and retailers chain

Questioners	Options	Wholesalers(N=15)		Retailers(N=30)	
		Freq(N=197)	%	Freq(N=197)	%
What type of transportation you are using?	Open FSR truck	13	86.7		
	Open Isuzu truck	2	13.3		
	Animal driven Gari			7	23.3
	<i>Hand Gari</i>			8	30
	<i>Careta</i>			11	36.7
	Motor			4	13.3
At what time you transport onion from the farm to your location?	Any time	15	100.00	30	100
Is there any loss during transportation?	Yes	15	100.00		
	No			30	100
If yes common causes for loss during transportation?	Bruising	11	73.4		
	Crushing/ Mechanical Damage	3	20.1		
	High heat	1	6.7		

Table 3.1.23. Communication of wholesalers

Questioners	Response	Frequency (N=15)	%
Do you have contact with farmers?	Yes, have direct contact	3	20.0
	All contact goes through brokers	12	80.00
What onion-varieties you bought?	Don't have information	15	100.0
How do the wholesaler find trucks for onion transportation?	Drivers	1	6.7
	Through brokers	14	93.3

3.1.3.4. Consumer-level post-harvest management practices

Consumers stand at the final stage of the onion value chain. They are affected financially as well as in terms of the availability of quality and quantity of safe produces. The survey results revealed that approximately 23 consumers face quality issues, such as sprouting, undersized bulbs, bruising, and decay, particularly during the rainy season after purchase

(Figures 3.1.14a and b). During this season, it is generally challenging to find quality onion bulbs. On average, consumers purchase between 1 kg and 50 kg of onions at a time, though not all of the purchased bulbs are used. Depending on the storage method and initial quality, consumers experience issues such as shriveling, sprouting, bruising, and rotting. Consumers store onion bulbs for periods ranging from 5 days to 3 months, with the majority using methods such as spreading the bulbs on the ground or storing them in polyester plastic bags. Other storage methods include using Hode/Zenbil, baskets, plastic rakes, shelves, storing under beds, and drying in the sunlight (Table 3.1.25).

The survey also indicated that consumers purchasing larger quantities of onions tend to buy from wholesalers, while those buying smaller quantities typically purchase from retailers. About 40% of respondents buy from retailers, 26% from wholesalers, 12% from producers, and 22% from both wholesalers and retailers. Price discounts for bulk purchases from wholesalers and the ability to select specific bulbs from retailers influence consumer preferences. Consumers seeking fresh and unmixed bulbs prefer to buy from producers and retailers. Proximity is another important factor when selecting where to purchase onions. Many consumers purchase larger quantities during periods of low prices and surplus supply (Tables 3.1.22 and 26). As noted by Yigzaw Dessalegn et al. (2016), damaged, wilted, and overripe fruits and vegetables, instead of being discarded, could be utilized as animal feed, compost for organic fertilizer, or other energy sources.

Table 3.1.24. Onion handling practices at consumer’s level

Questioners	Options	Frequency	Percent
Causes of postharvest losses	Bruising	8	16
	Rotting	26	52
	Sprouting	28	56
	Shrivelling	8	16
What methods are used to minimize onion loss during storage?	Applying cold charcoal ash	4	8
	Ventilating by spreading on the ground	34	68
	Sorting	10	20
	Nothing	10	20
	Sun drying	3	6
	5 days - 2 weeks	2	4.0

How long you store onion bulbs?	1 week	16	32
	2 week	21	42
	1 month	3	6
	2 month	7	14
	3 months	1	2.0
How do you store bulbs for consumption?	Basket	3	6
	Drying on the sun	2	4.0
	Ground /spread on the ground	14	28
	Hod/ <i>Zenbil</i>	8	16.0
	Plastic rake	5	10
	Polyester plastic bag	12	24
	Spreading on shelf	3	6.0
	Spreading under bed	2	4.0

Table 3.1.25. Market information

Questioners	Options	Frequency	Percent
From where do you buy onions and why do you buy onions from that certain place?	Wholesalers and retailers	11	22
	Producers/ farmers	6	12
	Retailers	20	40
	wholesaler's	13	26
Do you sometimes buy more or fewer onions than you need?	No	14	28
	Yes, too little during supply shortage too much during low price and during surplus	36	72

Figure 3.1.15. a. Presence of onion bulb quality problems b. Types of quality problems

Role of vegetable marketing cooperatives in the study areas

In the study areas (Andassa, Kudmi, and Fogera), fruit and vegetable marketing cooperatives were established. However, except the cooperative in Fogera, cooperatives in Andassa and Kudmi kebeles are not functional. The fruit and vegetable marketing cooperative in Fogera district is found in *Kuahir mical* kebele. The name of the cooperative is Lomidir and it has 240 members where 221 are male and 19 are female. The cooperative operates with established working guidelines and has a strong capacity during peak harvesting seasons, often producing more onions than they can handle. However, they face challenges with a lack of inputs during the off-season. The cooperative prioritizes attractive, color-sorted onions of marketable size, which are received and ranked first. Each week, they handle up to 12 tons of onions, which are delivered to wholesalers, hotels, and markets in Addis Ababa. For storage, they use methods such as spreading onions on beds or shelves and storing them in burlap sacks. The cooperative buys produce from its members twice a week, typically on rest days. Despite their success, they struggle with inadequate storage space and the lack of proper storage infrastructure, particularly shelves, to maintain the quality of the onion

Extent of losses in supply chain of onion

As shown in Table 3.1.27, the total postharvest loss of onions across the farmer, wholesale, retail, and consumer levels was found to be 29.775%. The highest proportion of losses (35.5%) occurred at the farmer level, followed by the retail level. At the wholesaler level, losses accounted for 27.77%, with 19.81% loss at the consumer level. The findings highlight those postharvest losses along the supply chain primarily impact farmers and retailers, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions at these stages. The lowest loss (16.87%) was observed at the consumer`s level.

The highest level of postharvest loss at the farm level could be due to the improper pre-and post-harvesting factors such as pest, mechanical damages and the presence of rain during harvesting. On the other hand, the observed high percentage of postharvest loss at the retail level, could be accounted by the cumulative effects of improper handling, packaging and transportation at the wholesaler and the retail levels. Wholesalers sold onion to the retailers in mass without sorting the damaged, diseased and under-sized bulbs, which also contribute to the high level of postharvest losses at the retailer level. On the other hand, retailers practiced sorting and sold quality bulbs to consumers that increases the proportion of unsold bulbs and thus increases the postharvest losses. Generally, postharvest loss is a serious challenge in the value chain of onion production, which is about 29.8% in the present study. In this regard, Calica and Cabanayan (2018) also reported about 31.49 % postharvest losses of onions in the Philippines. The present results are in line with the findings of Emanu Bezabih (2017) who reported that producers (farmers) and retailer are mostly affected by postharvest losses along the supply chain of onion. Similarly, Falola *et al.* (2023) also reported that onion farmers experienced a 23.9% postharvest loss in Nigeria.

Table 3.1.26. Average postharvest losses of onion at the value chain

Supply chain	Average loss (%)*	Share to the total losses (%)
Producers	10.58	35.5
Wholesaler	5.9	19.81
Retailer	8.27	27.77
Consumer	5.025	16.87
Total	29.775	100

*Losses were estimated as the difference between the quantity harvested/purchased and quantity sold in relation to the total quantity harvested/ purchased.

3.1.5. Conclusions and recommendations

The salient findings of the present study indicated that sex, age, educational level, production experience, land covered by onion, and household size have a significant influence on the production of onion. Sex, age, education level, active household size,

selling experience, amount purchased and storage duration have significant associations with the production and postharvest losses of onion. Improper postharvest handling practices, poor market linkage, poor storability of varieties, fertilizer shortage, disease, and insect pests were the major constraints of onion production. Onion producers were challenged by untimely and inadequate supply and unfairly high costs of the major production inputs. There are a significant quality differences between the sampled and delivered onion bulbs to traders in the marketing process, which were expressed in terms of damaged, undersized, sprouted, and immatured bulbs. The whole purchased produces never reached the consumer's hands. There was loss within each supply chain. The estimated postharvest loss at the whole value chain of onion was about 29.8%. Of which the higher proportion of losses (35.5%) was observed at the farmer's level (production chain). The existing problems and perishability nature of the crop aggravate the onion postharvest loss. Therefore, producers and handlers in the supply chain need to be trained on affordable and applicable postharvest technologies. Continuous capacity-building trainings, improvement of the infrastructures and access to inputs should be designed and implemented along the supply chain to improve crop management and postharvest handling practices. Moreover, marketing cooperatives working on the marketing system should be active and functional. The information from the current study can be used as baseline for policymakers and researchers to improve the production and productivity and to minimize the postharvest losses of onion. In this regard, meaningful interventions in the development and implementation of policy on sustainable production, handling practices and supply of onion should be designed to improve the livelihood of farmers.

3.2. Strategic Mapping of Onion Supply Chains: A Comprehensive Analysis of Production and Post-Harvest Processes in Northwest Ethiopia

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Published in: *Frontiers in Sustainability* <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsus.2024.1387907>

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Abstract

Onions is a significant vegetable crop in Ethiopia, serving as a source of income for smallholder farmers. However, various challenges in the production and post-harvest handling processes impede a consistent supply and marketing of the crop. This study focused on a comprehensive analysis of the onion supply chain, ranging from production to post-harvest handling, to address the existing production and marketing processes. The research initiative was undertaken to map the onion supply chain from farmers to consumers, intending to establish an improved marketing system in northwest Ethiopia. The study area covered three onion-producing districts of Amhara Region. Data collection involved interviews, observations, and market assessments using a structured questionnaire. Sampling followed a multistage sampling technique. Analysis included descriptive statistics and food system analysis to map the supply chain and estimate marketing margins. According to the results, postharvest loss presents a major obstacle in the production of onion and negatively impacts its growth. The study identified seven alternative channels of onion marketing where different actors involved throughout the supply chain. Key stakeholders include farmers, local collectors, brokers, transporters, wholesalers, retailers, and consumers. Packaging and sorting activities are implemented at different supply chain stages to minimize post-harvest losses. Farm-level activities, including curing, sorting, grading, and ventilating were crucial for the reduction of losses. The perishable nature of onion bulbs and the existing production and handling challenges exacerbate post-harvest losses. Efforts to address this challenge demands a comprehensive approach, integrating interventions across the value chain, from improved cultivars and storage infrastructure to

enhanced market access strategies. Hence, stakeholders and governmental organizations are urged to promote onion value-addition technologies, including the establishment of processing industries. Such endeavors promote collaborative efforts across the onion supply chain, ensuring sustainable benefits for producers and traders.

Keywords: Onion supply chain; Mapping, Market channel, Smallholder farmers, Production challenges, Market prices, post-harvest handling, post-harvest losses

3.2.1. Introduction

Ethiopia's diverse agro-climatic conditions are highly suitable for producing a wide range of vegetable crops, including onions, which serve as both a vital food source and a cash crop (Dawit Alemu et al., 2004; Lemma Dessalegn et al., 2006). Onion (*Allium cepa*) is the second most important vegetable in the country, cultivated on small and large-scale farms for domestic consumption and export (Lemma Dessalegn and Shimelis Aklilu, 2003). Despite its profitability and increasing production area, the sector faces significant challenges, including limited access to quality inputs, inadequate agronomic practices, poor extension services, and ineffective disease and pest management (AgroBIG, 2016; Agidew Abebe, 2018). Postharvest losses due to high moisture content, mechanical damage, diseases, pests, bruising, and shriveling further hinder supply chain efficiency, while seasonal production cycles complicate year-round market demand (Kitinoja and Kader, 2002; Pessu et al., 2011).

The onion supply chain in Ethiopia also suffers from inadequate storage facilities, inefficient handling and transportation networks, pricing inconsistencies, and weak market coordination (Carvalho et al., 2012; AgroBIG, 2016; Agidew Abebe, 2018). Beyond meeting domestic demands, onions contribute significantly to the national economy, with products like bulbs and cut flowers being exported globally, generating annual sales of 2.0 million Birr (Lemma Dessalegn and Shimelis Aklilu, 2003; CSA, 2018). Farmers in northwestern Ethiopia also produce onions as a cash crop, influenced by year-round

consumer demand and dynamic market forces (Kassa Getu and Ahmed Ibrahim, 2018; CSA, 2018). To improve productivity, livelihoods, and economic resilience, addressing these multifaceted challenges is crucial, and evaluating the supply chain remains vital for sustainable onion production (MoA, 2020; Masamha et al., 2018).

This study, focusing on Northwest Ethiopia, seeks to address gaps by analyzing production and postharvest processes, and mapping supply chain actors. By offering actionable insights, it aims to inform decision-makers, scholars, and industry stakeholders, enhancing supply chain resilience and promoting sustainable farming practices for improved productivity and regional economic development. Additionally, it builds upon previous research that emphasized production and marketing but paid limited attention to postharvest processes and comprehensive value chain analysis.

3.2.2. Review of related literature

3.2.2.1. Food supply chain

According to Van der Vorst et al. (2007) and FAO (2007), a supply chain encompasses the end-to-end processes from production to consumption, involving multiple organizations to fulfill customer demands. It manages the flow of materials, information, funds, and products, covering product development, marketing, operations, sales, and customer service. Supply chain mapping visually represents its structure to comprehend functionality and complexity. The food supply chain scrutinizes production, storage, transportation, trading, processing, and retailing. It is influenced by external factors like transportation and regulatory bodies. Business services that provide inputs and assistance, interact with the food supply system, shaping its dynamics (Van Berkum et al., 2018). Understanding these details is essential for effective management and optimization of supply chain processes.

Mila et al. (2022) state that supply chain analysis systematically elucidates the movement of goods and services from origin to destination, facilitating effective production management for quality control and enhanced year-round market access. The importance of supply chains has steadily increased as companies in various industries realize the benefits of establishing collaborative relationships both within and outside of their own organizations (Gallo et al., 2019).

3.2.2.2 Supply chain actors and their roles

Stakeholders in supply chain management play a crucial role for various reasons, including sharing information, collecting, packing, distributing, selling, processing, buying, and consuming produces (Minnens et al., 2019; Adamashvili et al., 2021). Their involvement is integral for enhancing sustainability performance (Tsoufias et al., 2019). For the impactful interventions, it is necessary to prioritize and understand the stakeholders, their interactions, and interrelations (WCDI, 2021). In the case of onion, various chain actors directly or indirectly contribute to the overall supply chain dynamics.

Supply chain actors and dynamics in onion production

- **Input Suppliers:** Provide agricultural inputs (seeds, compost, fertilizer, pesticides) from various sources, including government, individuals, and growers (Addisu Hailu et al., 2017; Wudineh Getahun et al., 2018).
- **Producers/Farmers:** Undertake field operations, from field preparation to postharvest handling of the crop. They are the major value chain contributors. They apply inputs and manage the cultivation of crops and participate in marketing processes (Agidew Abebe, 2018).
- **Local Collectors:** Middlemen/wholesalers facilitating onion distribution for specific wholesalers and retailers (Kassa Getu and Ahmed Ibrahim, 2018).
- **Brokers/Middlemen:** Intermediaries between farmers and wholesalers and providing market information (Daniels and Fors, 2015).

- Wholesalers: Purchase and supply large volumes of locally produced or imported onions to retailers and consumers (Wudineh Getahun et al., 2018).
- Retailers: Sell onions and other items in public markets, acting as the final link between producers and consumers (Daniels and Fors, 2015).
- Consumers: Household, cafes, restaurants, and hotels purchasing onions directly from producers, retailers, or wholesalers.
- Chain Supporters: Organizations providing diverse support, funds, and research collaboration, including research institutes, universities, credit unions, governmental and non-governmental organizations (SNV), infrastructure, and private companies.
- Influencer Actors (Enabling Environment): Policies, regulatory frameworks, financial sectors, trade and market development offices, business support services, land administration, and environmental protection offices shaping the overall onion supply chain (WCDI, 2021).
- Extension Services: Extension workers and research centers providing technical advice and improved onion varieties (WCDI, 2021).
- Influencer Actors (Policies and Regulatory Frameworks): Policies and regulations in financial sectors, trade, and market development, impacting the onion supply chain (WCDI, 2021).

3.2.2.3 Constraints of onion production

Onion production in the Amhara Region, Ethiopia faces challenges despite a labor-intensive approach, with over 50% of the population capable of engaging in cultivation (BoFED, 2003). Sustainable strategies encompass good management, cultural practices, new variety development, and improved production input access. However, obstacles like low soil fertility, inadequate post-harvest technologies, improper agronomic practices, inappropriate fertilizer use, pests, diseases, and costly production inputs contribute to Ethiopia's low and unstable onion yields (Lemma Dessalegn and Shimelis Aklilu, 2003; Kumilachew Alamerie et al., 2014), preventing farmers from maximizing the benefits of onion cultivation.

Mila et al. (2022) highlighted a lack of research and market information, while Berhanu Gebremedhin et al. (2009) observed that insufficient access to improved inputs and limited land holdings result in inadequate production to meet household consumption needs. Getu and Ibrahim (2018) noted the crucial role of fertilizers and pesticides in boosting onion productivity in the Amhara region. However, challenges such as high costs and improper access lead to suboptimal fertilizer use by most farmers, impacting crop yield.

Bewuketu Haile et al. (2016) found that the primary constraint in onion production in the Masha district is the lack of pesticides. Melkamu Alemayehu et al. (2015) noted fertilizer availability mainly for main-season crops, insufficient for irrigated onion production. Diseases and insect pests are significant challenges in Amhara Region's onion production. Agumas Yideg (2019) identified constraints in the Fogera district, highlighting suboptimal fertilizer application rates due to untimely supply and insufficient capital for purchasing the recommended amount.

While Ethiopian agricultural cooperatives historically focused on input marketing, recent shifts include their involvement in imports since 1970's. These cooperatives serve as crucial foundations, supporting smallholder farmers with necessary inputs and mitigating market risks (Thomas Woldu et al., 2013). Despite smallholders contributing 95% of Ethiopia's agricultural output, they face challenges such as restricted market access and low productivity (Gebremedhin et al., 2009; Musa Hasen and Hiwot Mekonnen, 2017), underscoring the need for improved support structures and market integration for enhanced agricultural sustainability and productivity.

Ethiopian cooperatives initially played a crucial role in fertilizer distribution, supplying 56% in 2010 (Matsumoto and Yamano, 2010). By 2008, cooperative unions dominated imports, reaching a 75% market share in 2007/2008 (IFPRI, 2012). However, to achieve economies of scale, the government centralized fertilizer imports through a single entity in 2008,

annually selecting the importer, limiting cooperatives to distribution (World Bank, 2011; Degnet Abebaw and Mekbib Haile, 2013).

The entire chemical fertilizer, and pesticide demand in Ethiopia is met only by importing. In addition, high cost, long lead time, little involvement of farmers in demand estimation, and the mismatch between quantity supplied and demanded are the major ones for accessibility of fertilizers. Due to this, farmers do not access the required amount of time. As illustrated in Fig.3.2.1 (From 1993 to 2022), farmer fertilizer consumption trend in kilograms per hectare of arable land increases significantly. In 1993, 7.6 kg fertilizers were enough for 1 hectare. However, in 2022, 36.2 kg of fertilizer was required per hectare (World Bank, 2022). The increase in the amount of fertilizer applied might be due to the decreasing rate of soil fertility. Moreover, recently, the significant rise in the price of fertilizers and pesticides has posed a great challenge for farmers.

3.2.2.4 Marketing channels

Marketing channels are routes through which agricultural products move from producer to consumer. The length of the channel varies from commodity to commodity, depending on the quantity to be moved, the form of consumer demand, and the degree of regional specialization in production (Kohls and Uhl, 1985; Adnan et al., 2014). According to Kohls and Uhl (1985), the marketing channels start at the farmgate and end at the consumer's front door. Some of the products are processed on their way to the end users while other products reach them without undergoing any form of change. According to Emanu et al. (2017), a significant proportion of onion harvest is meant for sale in various towns within Ethiopia, implying that production of the crop is commercially driven and access to the market is crucial to improve household income. In Ethiopia, there are increasing numbers of onion marketing channels where farmers are selling their products directly to consumers or through a middleman.

Kassa Getu and Ahmed Ibrahim (2018) identified six types of onion marketing channels in the Amhara region in Ethiopia. They were channel one is the producer to consumer, channel two is the producer to retailer to consumer, channel three is the producer to the collector to the wholesaler to retailer to consumer, channel four is producer/broker to collector/broker to wholesaler to retailer to consumer, channel five is the producer to processor to retailer to consumer and channel six is the producer to the collector to wholesaler to the exporter. They also indicated that of the total onion produced, 10–15% of produce was sold by farmers directly to consumers and that farmers that are able to sell directly to the consumer are getting better profit margins.

Emana Bezabih et al. (2017) identified around five marketing channels for onion in the Bora and Dugda districts of Oromia Regional State, Ethiopia. Farmers can sell the product to village collectors, wholesalers, retailers, cooperatives. Consumer sales to wholesalers, however, are the main market channel used, accounting for 95% of the onion sold by the producers. Village collectors and cooperatives buy very small proportions (1–2%) of the produce. Some farmers, especially women, also sell small quantities of onion on the open market to consumers. Six market channels of onion were also identified by Addisu Hailu et al. (2017) in the Ejere district, Oromia national regional state of Ethiopia. They are (1) Producer–Consumer (2) Producer–Rural Collector–Wholesaler–Central Retailer–Consumer (3) Producer–District Retailers–Consumer (4) Producer–Wholesaler–Central Retailer–Consumer (5) Producer–Wholesaler–Processor–Consumer and (6) Producer–Wholesaler–District Retailer–Consumer.

Figure 3.2.1. Fertilizer consumption trend in kilograms per hectare of arable land in Ethiopia (1993–2022) Source; World Bank (2022)

3.2.2.5. Marketing Channels

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3.2.2.6. Hypothetical framework

Elevated onion production costs, as discussed by Agumas Yideg (2019), diminish the likelihood of farmers bringing more products to the market. Our principal hypothesis indicates that production costs, encompassing agricultural inputs like fertilizers, pesticides, and fuel costs, exert a negative influence on onion production.

Alemayehu Derege (2010) highlights the impact of fertilizer usage on crop yields, emphasizing the potential for diminished yields or crop failure with improper application. We posit that judicious use of chemical fertilizers can positively influence onion production, enhancing farmer efficiency. Additionally, our hypothesis suggests a positive correlation between household size and onion production, as family members contribute valuable labor to onion cultivation activities (Abedullah et al., 2009).

Yebirzaf Yesiwas et al. (2023) argued that experienced farmers exhibit enhanced management skills, likely contributing to improved production processes. Therefore, we suggest that as farming experience, their proficiency in farming and yield enhancement may increase. Furthermore, transportation methods, market access, and price information are anticipated to exert positive or negative influences on onion production decisions. Our hypothesis suggests that longer transportation routes may adversely affect onion production, as an extended canal length is likely to diminish returns to producers.

3.2.3. Methodology

3.2.3.1. Study area description

The study encompassed three pivotal onion-producing districts in northwest Amhara: Mecha, Fogera, and Bahir Dar Zuria. Fogera is located at 11°58' N latitude and 37°41' E longitude, with Woreta as its capital. Mecha, in the West Gojjam Administrative Zone, lies 515 km north of Addis Ababa, and its capital, Merawi, connects the main road between Addis Ababa and Bahir Dar. Bahir Dar Zuria is situated around Bahir Dar town, with a mean altitude of 1800 meter above sea level and an annual mean rainfall of 750 mm, experiencing temperatures ranging from 10 to 38 °C.

3.2.3.2. Sampling method and sample size determination

This study employed a structured questionnaire for key informant interviews, direct field observations, and market assessments, following the methodology outlined by Elahi *et al.* (2022). The questionnaire incorporated both open and close-ended questions, with the latter being coded for ease of analysis. Open-ended questions encouraged respondents to freely express their ideas. Prior to interviews, respondents were informed about the study's purpose, granted the right to skip uncomfortable questions, and allowed to replace them with alternative willing respondents (Elahi *et al.*, 2021). Secondary data were gathered through document analysis and systematic literature reviews.

The interview questionnaire, initially prepared in English, was translated into Amharic, the national language, to overcome language barriers. It covered household socio-demographics, onion cultivation methods, raw material access, harvesting, post-harvest handling, distribution methods, and market information access. The study used a multistage sampling technique (Abbas *et al.*, 2022; Elahi *et al.*, 2022; Elahi *et al.*, 2021) at the first stage two potential onion-producing Zones such as South Gonder, and West Gojjam were selected purposely. At the second stage three potential onion-producing districts Fogera, North Mecha and Bahir Dar Zuria districts were selected purposely from major onion-producing zones. At the third stage two highly potential onion-producing *kebeles* were selected purposely from major onion-producing *kebeles*. The selected two *kebeles* have high onion production capacity and have market-linkage with the major onion marketing centers of the country. In the fourth stage, onion-producing households were randomly selected from the two *kebeles* for an interview purpose. Wholesalers, retailers, and consumers at Bahir Dar, Woreta, and Merawi cities were purposely selected based on their capacities. Bahir Dar City, Woreta City, and Merawi City were specifically chosen for wholesalers, retailers, and consumer chains due to their reputation for large-scale onion trade (Regional Agriculture Department, 2021).

Household sample size was determined using Yamane's (1967) sampling formula with 7% accuracy [1].

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where:

n is the required sample size, N is the target population size (total number of onion-producing households), and e is the precision level (7%). A precision of 7% was used to minimize the sample size.

Accordingly, a total of 197 respondents representing onion farmers, 15 wholesalers, 30 local collector, 50 retailers and 20 consumers were surveyed. Additionally, interviews with key informants (farmers, wholesalers, retailers, development agents) were conducted.

The value chain mapping process began with discussions with various stakeholders during the first survey. The final version of the map was then refined and improved using insights gathered from key informant interviews and group discussions. Interlinkages among various activities of the actors in the onion supply chain were observed.

3.2.3.3. Data analysis and supply chain mapping

Collected data were analysed using SPSS 16.0 and Microsoft Excel. Descriptive statistics, including frequency, mean, and percentage, were employed. Food system analysis Van Berkum (2018) mapped the actual supply chain and its linkages. This analysis provided a clear mapping of how different components of the food system are linked, from production to consumption.

Gross marketing, and net marketing margins of the main market actors were estimated using the following equations (Amikuzuno and Donkoh, 2012).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Gross marketing margin} &= \text{Sales price} - \text{Purchase price} \\ \text{Gross marketing margin} &= \text{Gross margin} - \text{Marketing cost} \\ \text{Producer share (\%)} &= \text{Farm price/Retail price} * 100 \end{aligned}$$

3.2.4. Results and discussion

3.2.4.1. Production and marketing of onions

The survey findings indicate an average onion yield of 16 t ha⁻¹ in the study area, which surpasses the average productivity of onion (11.7 t ha⁻¹) in Amhara National Regional State as reported by (CSA, 2018). However, the productivity of onion recorded in this study falls short of the global average of 21.1 t ha⁻¹ (FAO, 2022).

Figure 3.2.2 depicts the trend in area coverage and productivity of onion in the last 20 year (2002-2022). While the area under onion cultivation shows an increasing trend since 2020, onion productivity is declining. Factors limiting productivity include fluctuations in cultivation area and inappropriate agronomic practices, variety, lack of fertilizers, inadequate storage facilities, leading to significant post-harvest losses. The surge in onion cultivation since 2020 highlights the production potential and the robust consumer demand towards onion.

Despite a surplus of onions in the country for two to three months, prices during harvest season remained low. The same harvesting time of onion in the region that increase the supply and decrease the price (1-3 Birr kg⁻¹). On the other hand, during the rainy season there is shortage of supply that increases the price (30-55 Birr kg⁻¹) (Yebirzaf Yeshiwas et al., 2023). Promoting the use of climate-resilient and high-yield onion varieties can enable farmers to produce during unfavorable seasons, mitigating supply shortages during the rainy season. Additionally, enhancing market linkages through digital platforms and farmer cooperatives can connect producers to larger markets, improving their bargaining power and reducing reliance on local traders. Real-time market information systems, can further support informed decision-making. Lastly, encouraging value addition through processing, such as drying, packaging, or pickling, can reduce post-harvest losses and create new

income opportunities for farmers. Implementing these solutions holistically can stabilize prices, reduce losses, and enhance farmer incomes.

Figure 3.2.2. Onion production trend (2002–2021). Source; CSA (2022)

Mode of onion transportation in the supply chain

This study highlights the diverse transportation methods utilized by actors within the onion supply chain. Wholesalers predominantly rely on open trucks, such as FSR and Isuzu models, to transport onions from production areas to marketplaces (Table 3.2.1). In contrast, retailers employ various transport modes, including hand carts (36.7%), wheelbarrows (30%), animal-drawn carts (23.3%), and motorized carts (13.3%). These findings emphasize the adaptability and range of transportation strategies used to ensure efficient onion distribution across the supply chain.

Efficient and appropriate transportation services are essential for fruits and vegetables to deliver the products as quickly as possible with little damages (Rehman *et al.*, 2007; Tesfaye Sebeko, 2015). Yebirzaf Yeshiwas and Esubalew Tadele (2020) found that 55% of respondents in Debre Markos, Ethiopia, used hand-drawn *Gary* for transport. Abera *et al.* (2020) observed that 60.6% of tomato producers in Shewa, Ethiopia, rely on animal-packing carts, while 39.4% use trucks to transport goods to local markets. However, the

transportation method's suitability depends on the stage of the value chain. For instance, while animal-packing carts are commonly used for short-distance transport, trucks may be utilized for longer distances from wholesaler to retailer. It is important to note that the condition of the truck also plays a significant role in transport suitability. While trucks are used, they are often not conditioned to properly handle perishable goods, such as vegetables, which may lead to spoilage during transport. In contrast, human- and animal-drawn carts may offer a more flexible, although less efficient, solution for producers transporting small quantities of vegetables over shorter distances. Therefore, the choice of transport method is influenced by factors such as distance, cost, and the specific requirements of transporting perishable goods, which were not always adequately addressed in the studies cited.

Table 3.2.1. Modes of transportation along the supply chain of onion in the study area

Questions	Wholesalers (N = 15)		Retailers (N = 30)		
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	
Transportation methods used	Open FSR truck	13	86.7		
	Open ISUZU truck	2	13.3		
	Cart/animal-driven			7	23.3
	Hand cart			8	30
	Careta			11	36.7
	Motor			4	13.3

Where, Freq.=frequency; N= number of respondents

3.2.4.3. Value addition activities at the value chain of onion

The perishable nature of onions leads to postharvest losses due to mechanical damages rotting, sprouting, and weight loss at the supply chain. Therefore, the supply chain actors practice different postharvest handling practices including value addition activities to reduce postharvest losses of onion (Appendix Figure 3.2.1) While limited proportion of the respondent farmers practiced curing, most of the retailer practiced sorting and grading as value addition activities. Wholesalers exhibited value addition activities like sorting and grading (Table 3.2.2). Timely harvesting, curing, sorting, grading, and packaging are necessary to enhance the values and storage life of onion bulbs. Moreover, it helps reducing the postharvest losses and maintaining the postharvest quality of onion bulbs. In this regard,

Gizachew Wosene and Wubalem Gobie, (2022) reported that value-addition activities on tomatoes boosting shelf life and the income returns.

Table 3.2.2. Value addition activities in onion supply chain

Variable		Producers (%) (N = 197)	Wholesalers (%) (N = 15)	Retailers (%) (N = 30)
Timely Weeding	Yes	74.5		
Toppling	Yes	50.3		
Curing	Yes	3.6		
Sorting	Yes	15	44	100
Grading	Yes	30	2.5	69
Packaging	Yes	100	100	100
Ventilating	Yes	8.7	100	83.3

3.2.4.4. Onion marketing channel in the study areas

Marketing channels of onion were sketched based on the direction of flow and volume of onion yield transacted. The present study identified seven alternative channels for onion marketing in the study areas as indicated below.

Channel I: Producers–consumers

Channel II: Producer–local collector–wholesaler–consumer

Channel III: Producer–wholesaler–consumer

Channel IV: Producer–wholesaler–retailer–consumer

Channel V: Producers–cooperative–wholesalers–transfer to Central Market AA

Channel VI: Producers–wholesalers–retailer–consumers and Producer -Retailer–consumer

Channel VII: Producers–retailers - consumers

The estimated quantity of onion supplied to the market by the sampled households in the year 2022 production season was about 253.6 quintals. The amount of onion transacted in these market channels was not however the same. The results indicated that the producers sold the majority of their produces (66.15%) to the wholesalers and about 11.81% to the marketing cooperatives. The remaining produce was sold to local collectors (9.85%), retailers (7.9%), and consumers (4.29%) (Figure 3.2.3).

Channel I: Producers–consumers

The producers sell their onions directly to the consumer at the nearest market and farmgate. In this channel onion producers are more benefited from better prices and consumers have the chance to get fresh onion. However, a small volume of onion is transacted through this channel (Figure 3.2.3). The market size for such a shorter channel is small (4.29%) and it cannot absorb all onions produced. Similarly, retailing in local market is time-consuming for producers, especially for those who have more produce.

Channel II: Producer–local collector–wholesaler

In this channel the producers sold their onions to the local collectors (9.85%) while the local collectors sold all of onions to the wholesalers.

Channel III: Producer–wholesaler–consumer

The producers sold 66.15% of onion to wholesalers and then wholesalers sold 20.7% to consumers such as households, cafes, restaurants, and which have the capacity to purchase five kilograms of onion and above. Producers sold their produces to wholesaler without the involvement of brokers. This channel is the most important channel in which the largest volume of farmer`s onion was transacted in the study area.

Channel IV: Producer–wholesaler–retailer

The producer sold 66.15% of the onions to the wholesaler; wholesalers sold 71.26 % of onions to the retailer.

Channel V: Producers–cooperative–wholesalers–transfer (Center Market AA)

The producer sold 11.81% of the onions to the marketing cooperatives. Of which 75% of the onions sold to wholesalers in different parts of the country, and 25% transferred to center market in Addis Ababa.

Channel VI: Producers–wholesalers–retailer–consumers

In this channel the producers were selling their produce to the wholesalers, and the wholesalers sold to retailers who sold the produces to the consumer. It is the longest chain

in terms of market participants (Figure 3.2.3). As the number of actors between producers and consumers increases, the profit margin of the producer will decrease.

Channel VII: producers-retailers-consumers

The producer directly sold 7.9% of the onions to retailers, who in turn sold all (100 %) to consumers (Figure 3.2.3).

Figure 3.2.3. Onion supply chain and volume share of the flows

From the farmers' perspective, the marketing channels reveal both opportunities and challenges. The dominant channel through local collectors (66.15%) is convenient but often

results in lower prices due to intermediary profit margins. Selling directly to cooperatives (11.81%) offers structured market access and potentially fairer prices, yet cooperatives may lack the capacity to handle large volumes efficiently. Accessing wholesalers directly (7.9%) could provide better returns, but logistical barriers, transportation costs, and market competition pose significant challenges. Overall, the existing channels highlight a need for interventions to minimize intermediary dominance, enhance cooperative efficiency, and improve farmer access to profitable markets.

Profit margins

The findings showed that the highest profit margin was obtained by producers and collectors followed by retailers and wholesalers. However, while producers received the largest share of the profit margin (38.38%), this share remains unsatisfactory when compared to the high production costs they incur. Ideally, their share should exceed 70% to reflect their pivotal contribution to the supply chain. The distribution of profit margins in the onion supply chain reveals that producers received the highest share (38.38%), followed by collectors (25.79%), and retailers (18.11%). Additionally, a notable portion of the margin (17.72%) was allocated for the wholesalers in the chain. This breakdown underscores the significant contribution of producers to the profitability of the supply chain, highlighting their pivotal role in the onion marketing (Table 3.2.3).

Table 3.2.3. Margin analysis for the main market actors (N=292) in the value chain of onion (Birr per quintal)

Items	Market actors (N=292)			
	Producers N=197	Collector N=30	Wholesalers N=15	Retailers N=50
Purchase/Production Cost (A) (Birr/Qt)	340	1400	2150	2700
Sell Price (B) birr/Qt	1400	2150	2700	3200
Gross Margin C= (B-A)	1060	750	550	500
Marketing Cost. (D) birr/Qt	85	95	100	40

Net Margin (Net Profit Margin) (C-D)	975	655	450	460
Share of MMP (%)	38.38%	25.79%	17.72%	18.11%

(1 Birr = 0.02 USD, as of January 2021/22). Where; Qt = Quintal, MMP (Marketing Margin Percentage). Onion marketing margin for different channels (Birr/qt); in small unit analysis Sell price: at producer level 14 Birr kg^{-1} , at collector level 21.50 Birr kg^{-1} , at wholesalers' level 27 Birr kg^{-1} and at retailers' level 32 Birr kg^{-1} .

3.2.4.5. Mapping the onion supply chain and role of actors in the chain

The supply chain is a complex network of organizations, activities, and resources facilitating the movement of products from suppliers to customers (Chopra and Meindl, 2010; Felea and Albăstroi, 2013). In the context of onion production, the supply chain encompasses key chain actors such as producers/ farmers, local collectors, brokers, transporters, cooperatives, wholesalers, and consumers, with each stage playing a vital role in ensuring the smooth flow of products to the market (Figure 3.2.4). The current map's significance lies in designing a research framework and identifying barriers across the supply chain. By highlighting inefficiencies and challenges at various stages, it enables targeted interventions to enhance efficiency, reduce post-harvest losses, and ensure fair pricing for farmers. A meticulous two-stage process was employed to develop the final value chain map of the onion production. This approach is pivotal for comprehensively addressing challenges and optimizing the onion supply chain from farmers to consumers.

There were different input suppliers directly or indirectly involved in the onion supply chain in the study area. Input suppliers provided chemical fertilizers (Urea and NPS/B), onion seeds, herbicides, pesticides, and fuel. The majority of fertilizers, accounting for 93.9%, are sourced from a combination of local markets and cooperatives, highlighting their critical role in providing essential agricultural inputs to farmers.

All respondent farmers purchased herbicides and pesticides from the local market. The results of the present findings also indicated problems associated with timely and adequate supply inputs. High price of fertilizers and fuel as well as low quality of pesticides

(sometimes farmers had the possibility to purchase expired pesticides and insecticides) were also reported by respondent farmers.

Producers/farmers: small-scale farmers are the major producers of onion in the study areas. The major functions performed by farmers are land preparation, raising seedlings, transplanting, irrigation, fertilizer application, weeding, cultivation, disease and (Powdery mildew) and insect pest (onion thrips) management, harvesting, implementing post-harvest handling activities, and marketing. The major value-addition activities performed by the onion producers are illustrated in Table 3.2.2.

Local collectors, a type of middleman or wholesaler, play a significant role in the distribution of onions. They are well-informed about areas with surplus onion production, purchasing directly from farmers at the farm and primarily reselling to wholesalers and retailers, with direct sales to consumers occurring only in rare cases.

Brokers/middlemen: they are acting between farmers and wholesalers; they provide market and price information and identify potential producers and link the producers to wholesalers and facilitate the transaction of onion. They collect sample bulbs from the farms for quality evaluation and convincing the purchase of onions by the wholesalers. In addition, they also mediate wholesalers for purchasing of onions. As explained by producers (farmers) brokers sometimes go beyond facilitation and tend to control the selling power of the producers and fix the selling prices of onions.

Wholesalers: they are individuals who purchase onions in large volumes that are either produced by farmers or collected by local collectors. In most cases wholesalers supply onions to retailers and consumers. They are mostly equipped with storage facilities and have better financial capacities and communication access. Wholesalers stored onions usually for a maximum of seven days where the storage facilities were below the standard for onion storage. Moreover, wholesalers performed value-addition activities including sorting

grading and packaging (Table 3.2.2.). In the study area, major onion wholesalers are located in Merawi town, Bahir Dar city, Woreta town, Kudmi rural town, Andassa, and Sabatamit town. About 66.15% (Figure 3.2.4) of the onions produced by the producers in the study area were handled by the wholesalers found in these towns.

Retailers: they are supply chain actors who buy and sell onions in small quantities compared to the wholesalers. They mostly supply the consumers with onion. The value-addition activities performed by retailers are buying onions, transporting, sorting, grading, displaying, and selling to consumers (Table 3.3.2).

Marketing cooperatives: they are legal organizations established by vegetable and fruit producing farmers. The main purpose of these cooperatives is collecting of vegetable and fruits including onions from member farmers and supplying it to wholesalers and institutions like hotels. They have the capacity to transport onions to the central market in Addis Ababa for better price. They have strict quality requirements like attractive colour, marketable size and sorted onion bulbs while purchasing onions from their members. The value addition practices applied by them are spread on the bed and packaging and storage (Figure 3.2.2.). As indicated in Figure 3.2.4, about 11.81% of the onions produced by farmers were handled by the farmer`s marketing cooperatives.

Consumers: they are end-users of onion in the supply chain. Most of the consumers purchase onion from the retailers although some bought onion from producers, and wholesalers. The rural and urban households, cafes, restaurants, and hotels were identified as onion consumers in the study area.

Chain supporters: they are directly or indirectly involved in the onion supply chain. They provide different services including financial services, access to technologies, infrastructure development, and market information. District agricultural offices provide extension services; facilitate the accessibility of inputs and technologies. The research centers provide

improved production technologies for onion production, while non-governmental Organizations (NGOs) provide capacity building trainings and support inputs, like onion seeds, to the producers (Figure 3.2.4).

Chain influencers (Enabling environment): Encompass the policies, institutions, and regulatory frameworks that shape and facilitate the functioning of a supply chain. In the study area, the chain influencers are regulatory frameworks and policymakers, revenue authority, trade and industry office, land administration, environmental protection office, and irrigation development office to intervene in onion marketing (Figure 3.2.4).

Figure 3.2.4. Onion supply chain map

3.2.5. Conclusions and Recommendations

The onion supply chain, from production to consumer delivery, faces critical challenges that hinder its efficiency and productivity. Mapping the supply chain reveals key points impeding proper information flow and highlights inconsistencies in value addition practices, particularly at the producer and intermediary levels. Packaging and sorting activities, although applied, remain inadequate, especially among wholesalers and retailers. Transportation constraints, price volatility, and inefficient use of marketing channels further aggravate the situation, while poor storage facilities contribute to substantial post-harvest losses. Producers mainly sell their yield to wholesalers, followed by cooperatives, with minimal direct transactions with consumers.

Despite an increase in cultivated area post-2020, productivity has been negatively affected due to fluctuating cultivation patterns, insufficient post-harvest technologies, and challenges such as soil fertility issues, improper fertilizer application, pests, and suboptimal agronomic practices. These issues lead to low and inconsistent yields, which undermine the potential of onion production in the region.

Based on the findings, considering the perishability nature of the crop and the existing problems aggravate onion loss after harvest it is recommended to prioritize interventions that enhance onion value addition, including establishing processing industries to mitigate post-harvest losses. Stakeholders and governmental organizations should support onion producers and traders with continuous capacity building, improved extension services, infrastructure enhancement, and better input access for sustainable benefits. Meaningful policy interventions, informed by the identified supply chain dynamics, should be developed and implemented. Additionally, incorporating spatial and temporal data in future studies can provide a more comprehensive understanding for informed decision-making in onion production and handling.

Chapter 4. ENHANCING BULB YIELD THROUGH NITROGEN FERTILIZATION AND THE USE OF HYBRID ONION VARIETIES IN NORTHWEST ETHIOPIA

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Published in PLOS one: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0312394>

Abstract

Onions are among the most important cash crops in developing countries, including Ethiopia. However, its production and productivity are very low, which is associated with inappropriate fertilization and the use of low-yielding varieties. Therefore, the present study was conducted to evaluate the effects of the nitrogen fertilizer rate on the growth, yield, and quality of hybrid onion varieties in northwest Ethiopia. The experiment was conducted at three locations (Koga, Woreta, and Woramit) during the 2021/2022 cropping season under irrigated conditions. The treatments consisted of three hybrid onion varieties (Russet, Jambar, Red Coach) and one open-pollinated onion variety (Bombay Red) and four nitrogen rates (0, 41, 82, and 123 kg ha⁻¹), which were laid out in a randomized complete block design with a factorial arrangement of 4*4 in three replications. The results of the present study revealed that onion growth, yield and quality were influenced by the nitrogen fertilizer rate and onion variety across all locations. Compared with the open pollinated Bombay Red variety, the hybrid varieties (Russet and Jambar) performed well in terms of bulb diameter, bulb weight, total yield, marketable bulb yield, and pungency. Nitrogen fertilizer applied at a rate of 82 kg ha⁻¹ resulted in the highest growth and yield parameters of onion. The Russet and Jambar varieties recorded the highest marketable bulb yields of 26.50 t ha⁻¹ and 24.57 t ha⁻¹, respectively. Onion varieties treated with the highest nitrogen fertilizer dosage of 123 kg ha⁻¹, particularly the Bombay Red variety, exhibited the longest duration to reach maturity. Onion plants supplied with 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen presented the highest marketable bulb yields, with a value of 26.77 t ha⁻¹. Too much nitrogen above 82 kg ha⁻¹ leads to decreased yield; hence, excess nitrogen is lost to the environment.

Furthermore, the Jambar and Russet hybrid varieties and the application of 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen fertilizers provided the highest net benefit. The hybrid varieties Jambar and Russet and the application of 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen fertilizer can be recommended for onion production in the study area and areas with similar agroecosystems. Since this study is the first of its kind, considering other hybrid onion varieties and optimizing agronomic practices such as spacing and phosphorus fertilizer are also recommended in future research.

Keywords; Onion; Hybrid varieties; Nitrogen fertilizer, Growth; Yield, Quality, Net benefit

4.1. Introduction

Onion (*Allium cepa L.*) is a vital vegetable crop worldwide (Cramer, 2000). It can be grown in different climatic zones and is widely cultivated for its edible bulbs and lower stem sections (Mamiro *et al.*, 2014). It was first introduced to the Ethiopian agricultural system in the 1970s by foreigners (Lemma Desalegn and Shimelis Aklilu, 2003). Onions are used to flavor and season a wide variety of dishes and are valued for their medicinal properties in many communities, including potential health benefits to minimize high blood pressure and reduce the risk of cancer, other heart diseases, and diabetes. Onions are rich in essential nutrients such as vitamin C, B6, biotin, chromium, calcium, and dietary fiber. When onions are sliced or crushed, they release an enzyme called alliinase, which leads to tearing or crying eyes (Raemaekers, 2001; Sharma, 2014; Renbomo and Biswas, 2017).

Onions are being grown in more than 130 countries around the world. The annual global production and productivity of onion are 99.97 million tonnes and 19.25 t ha⁻¹, respectively (FAOSTAT, 2020). China is the world's top producer, followed by India and the US. In Africa, Egypt is the leading country, producing 22.08 million tons of onion per year for domestic and international markets, ranking fourth among world producers. Ethiopia ranks as the third largest onion producer on the African continent, trailing behind Egypt and South Africa (FAO, 2022). Onion is mostly produced by small-scale farmers as a cash crop in Ethiopia. Despite the presence of a suitable environment and edaphic conditions, the production and productivity of onion in the country are very low. According to the CSA (2020), the annual production and productivity of onion in Ethiopia are 346048.1 tons and 8.88 t ha⁻¹, respectively. This is

significantly lower than the potential yield of 40 t ha⁻¹ achieved under research station conditions (CSA, 2020). Farmers in Ethiopia use open-pollinated varieties with low yields (Bombay Red and Adama Red). They also practice improper agronomic practices, including inappropriate soil fertility management (Yideg Agumas, 2019; Yebirzaf Yeshiwas *et al.*, 2023). These similar malpractices contribute to the low level of onion productivity and bulb qualities, such as total soluble solids (brix) and pungency, which exist in Ethiopia, affecting market potential and consumer preference.

Successful onion production depends on several factors, including the selection of adaptable high yielder varieties suited to local conditions, the implementation of proper agronomic practices and the reduction of postharvest losses (Habtamu Gudisa, 2017; Yebirzaf Yeshiwas *et al.*, 2023). Compared with open-pollinated varieties, hybrid onion varieties generally boast greater yield potential, offering uniform bulb sizes and enhanced storability, thereby extending shelf-life (Hyde, 2010; Singh and Bhonde, 2011). In the context of improving onion production in northwest Amhara Ethiopia, various hybrid varieties such as Russet, Red Coach, and Jambar have been introduced into the local farming system. These varieties were selected due to their high yield potential and better storability compared to open pollinated varieties. Preliminary trials and research conducted in similar agro-climatic regions have shown that these varieties adapted and perform well under local conditions of northwest Amhara Ethiopia (Yebirzaf Yeshiwas *et al.*, 2023). However, despite their introduction, the full production technologies, particularly regarding their specific nitrogen fertilizer requirements, has not been comprehensively studied and require interventions.

Fertilization should aim to improve onion productivity and quality with respect to nutrient requirements related to optimal yield at a minimum cost and high efficiency of fertilization use (Lee, 2014). Compared with most other crops, onion plants have shallow and unbranched roots, which increase their vulnerability to nutritional deficiencies (Brewster, 1994). Consequently, onions require a relatively high level of nitrogen and respond well to supplemental nitrogen fertilizer (Brewster, 1994; Brewster, 2008). The rate of fertilizer application depends on various factors, such as the crop type, environmental conditions, soil fertility status, method of fertilization, and yield potential of the crop (Yoldas *et al.*, 2011; Agnieszka *et al.*, 2017). Dinega

et al. (2023) reported that intensifying nitrogen fertilizer management can improve yield and bulb quality in onion.

Although exogenous nitrogen application is known to increase onion yield, many researchers have reported that the application of high levels of nitrogen fertilizer leads to a reduction in the storage life of onion bulbs (Khokhar, 2019). Excessively high doses of nitrogen also cause a delay in bulb maturity and encourage bolting, which is an undesirable characteristic (Aliyu *et al.*, 2008). Moreover, according to Khan et al. (2021), a low rate of nitrogen causes a low yield of onions due to a shortage of nitrogen required for the chlorophyll pigment that is responsible for photosynthesis. Excessive nitrogen is hazardous to the environment, weakens foliage and predisposes plants to pathogenic diseases (Geary et al., 2015). The application of the optimal nitrogen fertilizer rate is therefore essential in onion production (Buckland et al., 2013; Dinega et al., 2023). In this context, this study aimed to optimize nitrogen fertilizer rates for the economical production of hybrid onion varieties in northwestern Ethiopia.

4.2. Materials and Methods

4.2.1. Description of the study area

Field experiment was carried out at three locations, namely, the North Mecha (Koga), Fogera (Woreta) and Bahir Dar Zuria (Woramit) districts of the Amhara region (Figure 2.1), during the 2021–2022 irrigation season. The geographical locations, altitudes, average, minimum and maximum temperatures, rainfall, and soil types of the districts are presented in Table 2.1. The average maximum and minimum temperatures of Woreta and Woramit during the experimental period were 29 °C and 17.8 °C and 28 °C and 12.4 °C, respectively. The Koga experimental site had the mean maximum and minimum temperature of 28.8 °C and 9.5 °C, respectively, as indicated in Fig.2.2 (Regional Meteorological Station, 2022).

4.2.2. Experimental materials

Three hybrid F₁ onion varieties, Russet, Red Coach, and Jambar, and one open pollinated Bombay Red variety as local check, were used as treatments in the present study. The seeds of

the hybrid varieties were collected from commercial suppliers (Eshet Agricultural Input Supplier), while the Bombay Red variety seeds were obtained from the Melkassa Agricultural Research Center (MARC). The onion varieties were selected on the basis of the results of the preliminary pilot survey in which the farmers preferred them on the basis of their growth and yield performance. The general characteristics of the selected onion varieties are presented in Table 2.3.

4.2.3. Treatments and experimental design

The treatments consisted of four onion varieties, four levels of nitrogen fertilizer (0 kg ha⁻¹, 41 kg ha⁻¹, 82 kg ha⁻¹, and 123 kg ha⁻¹), at three locations. The treatments were laid out in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) in a 4*4 factorial arrangement with three replications. Each treatment combination was randomly assigned to the experimental units within a block at each location. In total, 16 treatments were used in the experiment. The total plot size of the experiment was 1.6 m × 1.6 m (2.56 m²), while the net plot size was 1.8 m². The blocks were separated by one meter, and the space between each plot within a block was 0.5 m.

4.2.4. Experimental procedures

Seeds of each variety were sown on well-prepared raised beds and mulched with straw. After germination, the mulching material was removed. Watering was done using a fine watering can where the frequency was determined on the basis of climatic conditions. The seedlings were maintained for 55 days after sowing and hardened before being transplanted to the field. This was done by reducing the frequency of watering and making the soil have a low moisture status when the seedlings were ready for field planting.

Healthy and vigorous 12–15 cm tall seedlings were carefully raised for transplanting. The selected seedlings were transplanted in January 2022 with a recommended double row spacing of 40 cm × 20 cm × 10 cm (MoARD., 2004).

All agronomic practices were applied according to the recommendation made for onion (MoARD., 2004). The nitrogen fertilizer based on the rates of the treatments was applied in the

form of urea (46% N) in two equal splits, where the first 50% of the nitrogen was applied 15 days after transplanting, while the remaining 50% was applied one month after transplanting. Triple superphosphate (46% P₂O₅) was used as a source of phosphorus and was applied at a rate of 92 kg ha⁻¹ P₂O₅ at the time of uniform transplantation for all the plots (Nikus Olani and Fekir Mulugeta, 2010).

Irrigation water was applied at four-day intervals via furrow irrigation for the first four weeks and then extended to seven-day intervals until the physiological maturity stage. The application of irrigation water was completely stopped 15 days before harvesting for curing purposes. Onion bulbs were harvested when 70% of the plants in each plot showed neck fall (IPGRI, 2001; MoARD., 2004).

4.2.5. Data collection

Measurements of onion growth, yield, and quality parameters were recorded from the central four rows of the net plot area at the physiological maturity stage and harvesting time. Plant height, leaf number per plant and leaf diameter were measured from ten randomly selected plants from the central four rows in each plot, whereas days to physiological maturity, bulb diameter, average bulb weight, total, marketable, and unmarketable bulb yields were collected in the net plot area.

4.2.6. Data analysis

The collected data were first checked for meeting with all ANOVA assumptions (normality and homogeneity) after the Leven homogeneity test. Data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the PROC GLM model of SAS computer software version 9.0 (SAS Institute Inc., 2008).

Following Leven's homogeneity test, a combined analysis of variance was performed using the SAS PROC MIXED procedure. The nitrogen fertilizer rate and variety were considered as fixed effects, whereas locations were considered as a random effect. Whenever ANOVA was significant ($P < 0.05$), mean separation was carried out using least significant difference (LSD)

tests (Gomez and Gomez., 1984). Multiple regression analysis was conducted to determine nitrogen coefficients to develop the model using the PROC REG procedure for marketable bulb yield. The quadratic fit model was used to estimate the optimum values of nitrogen above which no additional net returns were predicted.

4.2.7. Partial budget analysis

Partial budget analysis following the procedures described by CIMMYT (1988) was performed to evaluate the economics of the treatments. The marketable yield was downscaled by 10% since the experimental yields are usually higher than those of farmers. The gross benefits of the treatments were estimated by multiplying the adjusted marketable bulb yield with the farm-gate price (20.00 Birr kg⁻¹) of onion bulb prevailing in the study area during harvest. The price of urea fertilizer in local marketplaces was 32.50 ETB kg⁻¹. Furthermore, the prices of onion seeds (Russet and Jambar 16,000 ETB kg⁻¹, Red Coach 13,000 kg⁻¹, and Bombay Red 2,500 ETB kg⁻¹) and labor cost (150.00 ETB day⁻¹) for fertilizer application were used to calculate gross incomes and variable costs. Seed cost, labor cost and urea fertilizer cost are considered variable costs that change with the treatment. The sum of these costs was considered as the total variable cost of the treatment. Net benefits from treatments were obtained by deducting total variable costs from gross benefit on a hectare basis, as indicated by CIMMYT (1988).

4.3. Results and Discussion

4.3.1. Effect of nitrogen fertilizer rate on the phenology and vegetative traits of onion varieties

The main effects of variety and nitrogen rate significantly ($P < 0.01$) influenced days to physiological maturity, plant height, and leaf number plant⁻¹. However, the two-way interactions between variety and nitrogen did not influence ($p > 0.05$) the number of days needed for the physiological maturity of the onion (Appendix Table 4.1).

The Russet onion variety matured earlier (94.7 days), whereas Bombay Red took the longest number of days (108.47) to achieve physiological maturity across the three locations (Table

4.1). The variation in the days required to reach maturity between onion varieties could be due to their genetic differences. Different scholars have reported similar results, where varieties differ in the number of days required to reach physiological maturity (Yemane Kahsay *et al.*, 2014; Gebremedhn *et al.*, 2018; Fikre *et al.*, 2021). The application of fertilizer also significantly extended the physiological maturity of onion across locations.

Compared with those in the other treatments, onion plants supplied with 123 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen required the longest days (104.22 days) to reach physiological maturity, whereas onion plants without nitrogen fertilizer matured earlier (100.13 days) (Table 4.1). This could be attributed to the effects of nitrogen, which extends the vegetative growth period, which in turn delays the physiological maturity of onion plants. Nitrogen fertilizer also increases vegetative growth, which increases the interception of solar radiation and consequently prolongs the number of days needed to reach physiological maturity (Krshnappa, 1989). The results of the present study are in agreement with the findings of different scholars who reported excessive vegetative growth and delayed onion maturity with the application of relatively high levels of nitrogen fertilizer (Brewster, 1994; Sorensen and Grevsen, 2001 and Abdissa Yohanes *et al.*, 2011). Similarly, Kebede (2003) reported that shallot plants were influenced by nutrients and that increased nitrogen fertilizer rates enhanced vegetative growth, delayed maturity, and reduced bulblet size.

The results of the main effects indicated that the Jambar variety, Bombay Red, and Red Coach presented the highest and statistically similar plant heights, with measurement values of 51.12 cm, 51.42 cm, and 50.17 cm, respectively. However, the Russet variety (48.14 cm) recorded the lowest plant height (Table 4.1). The differences in plant height among the varieties could be attributed to genotypic differences, which is in line with previous findings (Ibrahim, 2010, Ahmed *et al.*, 2013; Azoom *et al.*, 2014; Gebremedhn *et al.*, 2018; Awoke Ali *et al.*, 2021). The authors reported significant differences in plant height between onion cultivars because of their genetic variations. Compared with the hybrid Russet variety, the open-pollinated Bombay Red variety presented the longest plant height. This could be attributed to the specific breeding goals in which hybrids are prioritized for improved bulb yield rather than excessive vegetative growth compared with certain open-pollinated varieties (Cramer, 1999; Cramer, 2018).

The onion plants supplied with 123 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen recorded the longest plant height, which was statistically similar to the heights recorded with the application of 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen. The lowest mean plant height (46.48 cm) was recorded for the plants grown without nitrogen fertilizer (Table 4.1). The application of 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen increased the plant height by approximately 11.9% compared with that of the plants grown without nitrogen. However, a further increase in the nitrogen rate did not significantly affect the height of the plant. The application of nitrogen plays a crucial role in cell division, elongation, and improvement of vegetative growth through increased photosynthetic areas of plants, including onions. The improvement in onion plant height through the application of nitrogen fertilizer has also been reported by different scholars (Rizk *et al.*, 2012; Al-Fraihat, 2009; Kokobe *et al.*, 2012; Weldemariam Seifu *et al.*, 2015; Nasreen *et al.*, 2007; Morsy *et al.*, 2012; Simon *et al.*, 2014).

The analysis revealed that the highest average leaf number per plant was recorded for the Bombay Red and Jambar varieties, with values of 9.69 and 9.44, respectively, which were statistically similar to each other. On the other hand, the lowest number of leaves per plant (9.0) was recorded from the Red Coach variety at the three locations, as indicated in Table 4.1. The difference in the number of leaves per plant could be due to the difference in the inherent genetic makeup of the onion varieties. The present findings align with previous results that reported differences in genetic makeup as the cause of variations in leaf number between onion varieties (Boukary *et al.*, 2012; Ijoyah *et al.*, 2008; Bedada and Dechassa, 2014).

The application of 123 kg ha⁻¹ and 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen resulted in the highest number of leaves per plant (9.82 and 9.61, respectively), whereas plants without nitrogen fertilizer produced the lowest number of leaves per plant (8.63), as indicated in Table 4.1. Nitrogen is an important nutrient necessary for the synthesis of different protein components that are required for leaf development. In this context, studies by Kokobe *et al.* (2012) have revealed the positive impact of nitrogen on promoting the production of new shoots during the vegetative growth of plants, which may help increase onion leaf number. The application of nitrogen fertilizer also increased the leaf number of onion plants in different studies (Abdissa Yohanes *et al.*, 2011; Ibrahim, 2010; Guesh Tekle, 2015; Gebregwergis Fitsum *et al.*, 2016; Alebachew Merawi *et al.*, 2019).

Table 4.1. Effects of variety, nitrogen fertilizer on maturity and growth of the onion across the locations

Variety	Days to physiological maturity (Days)	Plant height (cm)	Leaf number plant⁻¹
Russet	94.69 ^c	48.42b	9.02bc
Jambar	100.97 ^b	50.17a	9c
Red Coach	101.72 ^b	51.12a	9.44ab
Bombay Red	108.47 ^a	51.42a	9.69a
P values	**	**	**
LSD _{0.05}	3.27	1.70	0.41
Nitrogen (kg ha⁻¹)			
0	100.13 ^b	46.48c	8.63c
41	100.55 ^b	50.23b	9.09b
82	100.94 ^b	52.03a	9.61a
123	104.22 ^a	51.42a	9.82a
P values	**	**	**
LSD _{0.05}	2.7	3.66	0.41
CV (%)	5.6	15.61	11.95

Where; ***= $p < 0.001$; ** = $P < 0.01$; and $Ns = P > 0.05$. Means followed by the same letter within the same column are not significantly different at the 5% probability level; $LSD_{0.05}$ = least significant difference at the 5% probability level; and CV = coefficient of variation

4.3.2. Influences of variety and nitrogen fertilizer on bulb yield and quality

The results of the combined analysis indicated that the bulb diameter, average bulb weight, total bulb yield, marketable bulb yield and unmarketable bulb yield were influenced by the main effects of variety and nitrogen rate. However, the interaction effect of variety and nitrogen rate was not significant (Appendix Table 4.1)

The widest diameter of the onion bulb was recorded from the Russet (69.54 cm) and Jambar (68.53 cm) varieties, whereas the lowest diameter of the bulb (64.56 cm) was recorded from the Bombay Red variety (Table 4.2).

The widest diameter of the onion bulb was recorded from plots that received 82 kg ha⁻¹ (73.4 cm) and 123 kg ha⁻¹ (70.66 cm) onion bulb. On the other hand, the lowest bulb width of 60.44 cm was recorded from the control plot without nitrogen fertilizer. Compared with the control

treatment without nitrogen, the application of nitrogen at a rate of 82 kg ha⁻¹ increased the mean bulb diameter by 21.5% (Table 4.2). However, a further increase in the nitrogen rate above 82 kg ha⁻¹ did not affect the mean bulb diameter of the onion. The diameter of the bulb is one of the most important yield components that indicates the yield potential of onion varieties. The parameter is influenced by the genetic makeup of the variety. The greater bulb diameter recorded from the hybrid varieties than from the open pollinated Bombay Red variety in the present study could therefore be attributed to the differences in the genetic makeup of the varieties (Jilani *et al.*, 2009; Rageb *et al.*, 2018). Similar findings were also reported by Mekdes (2012), where the open-pollinated Bombay Red variety presented the lowest bulb diameter. The increase in bulb diameter due to the application of nitrogen fertilizer is clearly associated with the growth-promoting effects of nitrogen, which improve dry matter production in onion plants. An increase in bulb size through the application of nitrogen has also been reported by different researchers (Abdissa Yohanes *et al.*, 2011; Guesh, 2015; Muluneh Bekele *et al.*, 2018; Tekeste *et al.*, 2018; Khan *et al.*, 2019; Teklay Tesfay and Selamawit Girmay, 2020; Piri and Naserin, 2020 and Shura *et al.*, 2022).

The hybrid varieties Jambar (94.28 g), Russet (93.12 g) and Red Coach (91.16 g) produced the heaviest bulbs, whereas Bombay Red (81.7 g), an open pollinated variety, as indicated in Table 4.2.

Similarly, the application of 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen resulted in the highest bulb weight of onion, whereas the lowest bulb weight was recorded for plants without nitrogen fertilizer. The bulb weight is an important parameter that indicates the yield potential of a given onion variety. In this sense, the hybrid varieties in the present study produced relatively larger bulbs than did the open pollinated variety, which may be associated with their genetic makeup. The results of the present study are consistent with the findings of other researchers who reported that hybrid varieties produced relatively larger bulbs and thus higher bulb yields than did open pollinated onion varieties (Cramer, 2018). Compared with the control without nitrogen, nitrogen supplied at a rate of 82 kg ha⁻¹ increased the bulb weight by 27%. However, additional applications of nitrogen beyond 82 kg ha⁻¹ did not result in any significant changes in bulb weight.

Table 4.2. Influence of variety and nitrogen rate on onion bulb size at three locations

Onion varieties	Bulb diameter (cm)	Average bulb weight (g)
Russet	69.54a	93.12a
Red Coach	65.85b	91.16a
Jambar	68.53ab	94.28a
Bombay Red	64.56c	81.7b
P values	**	**
LSD _{0.05}	3.82	3.68
Nitrogen (kg ha⁻¹)		
0	60.44b	79.84d
41	63.99b	85.87c
82	73.4a	101.18a
123	70.66a	93.38b
P values	***	**
LSD _{0.05}	3.82	3.19
CV (%)	12.22	8.74

where; ***= $p < 0.001$; ** = $P < 0.01$; and Ns = $P > 0.05$. Means followed by the same letter within the same column are not significantly different at the 5% probability level: LSD_{0.05}= Least significant difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation

The Russet (26.93 t ha⁻¹) and Jambar (25.08 t ha⁻¹) varieties presented the highest total bulb yields, whereas the Red Coach (25.08 t ha⁻¹) and Bombay Red (20.45 t ha⁻¹) varieties presented the lowest total bulb yields across the three locations.

The application of 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen recorded the highest total bulb yield (26.26 t ha⁻¹), whereas plants without nitrogen fertilizer recorded the lowest total bulb yield (24.97 t ha⁻¹), as indicated in Table 4.3. High doses of nitrogen result in excessive vegetative growth, which can cause self-shading and a reduction in photosynthesis activities, which in turn reduces the development of storage organs (Khan *et al.*, 2011; Wang *et al.*, 2020). In contrast, a low level of nitrogen causes a reduction in photosynthetic activity associated with a reduction in chlorophyll content (Girarden *et al.*, 1985). In this context, the application of nitrogen at an appropriate rate is necessary to enhance the leaf area and chlorophyll content and thus increase photosynthetic activity and yield, as indicated in the present study. Compared with the control treatment without nitrogen fertilizer, the application of 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen in the present study increased the total onion bulb yield by 38.5%. However, a further increase in the nitrogen rate did not significantly affect the total bulb yield. The yield potential of onion varieties depends

on the genetic potential, environmental conditions, and management activities implemented (Mnzava *et al.*, 2013 and Singh *et al.*, 2015). In this sense, the differences in total bulb yield observed in the present study could be attributed to their genetic potential. The highest total bulb yield observed for the Russet and Jambar varieties could be associated with the relatively larger bulbs of the varieties observed in the present study. These findings indicate that these varieties have high nutrient utilization capacity, better adaptability, and high yield performance than do the other onion varieties. These results are in agreement with the findings of other scholars who reported that total bulb yield differences between onion varieties could be attributed to variations in nitrogen fertilizer response and genetic makeup, as well as in the interaction of genotypes and environmental effects (Yemane Kahsay *et al.*, 2013; Rageb *et al.*, 2018; Tegebew Walle *et al.*, 2018). According to Simon *et al.* (2014), proper nutrient management positively contributes to onion production and productivity improvement, especially in areas where nutrient deficiency is critical.

The highest marketable bulb yield was obtained from the Russet (26.50 t ha⁻¹) and Jambar varieties (24.57 t ha⁻¹). However, the lowest marketable bulb yield was recorded for the Bombay Red variety (19.86 t ha⁻¹), which was statistically similar to that of the Red Coach variety.

The onion plants supplied with 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen produced the highest marketable yield (26.77 t ha⁻¹), whereas the plants without nitrogen fertilizer produced the lowest marketable bulb yield (19.09 t ha⁻¹) (Table 4.3). The increased marketable yield of hybrid onion varieties (Russet and Jambar) observed in the present study is clearly due to their genetic potential, as indicated by different scholars who reported marketable bulb yield differences between onion varieties (Geremew Awas *et al.*, 2010; Hailu Dinka *et al.*, 2015; Gebremedhn Gebretsadkan *et al.*, 2018; Alemu Direbsa *et al.*, 2022). Jilani *et al.* (2004) and Yemane Kahsay *et al.* (2013) also reported that different onion varieties of the same species produced different yields because of their genetic makeup. Nitrogen fertilizer obviously influences crop yield, including onion yield. The marketable bulb yield of onion varies with the nitrogen fertilizer rate (Kiros Gebretsadik and Nigussie Dechassa, 2018). As illustrated in Fig 4.1, the marketable yield of onion in the present study generally tended to increase and reached a plateau at the 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen rate, which was found to be optimal for onion production at the study sites. However, a further increase in

the nitrogen rate beyond 82 kg ha⁻¹ did not significantly influence the marketable bulb yield; rather, it resulted in a decreasing trend in the marketable yield.

Figure 4 1.Effect of nitrogen rate on the marketable bulb yield of onion varieties

There was a decreasing trend and negative relationship between marketable bulb yield and plant height (Fig. 4.2a), while an increasing trend and positive slope between marketable bulb yield bulb diameter (Fig. 4.2b), and average bulb weight (Figure. 4.2c).

Figure 4 2. Relationship between marketable yield and traits (a) plant height, (b) bulb diameter (c) average bulb weight

The Bombay Red onion variety presented the highest unmarketable bulb yield per hectare (0.59 t ha⁻¹), whereas the hybrid onion varieties generally produced the lowest unmarketable bulb yield per hectare. Compared with the plots supplied with nitrogen fertilizer, the unfertilized plot also presented the highest unmarketable bulb yield (Table 4.3), which could be attributed to the application of a suboptimal nitrogen supply that produced poor-quality bulbs that contributed to a higher unmarketable onion yield. This result agrees with the findings of Zeleke *et al.* (2021), who reported the highest unmarketable bulb yield from unfertilized plots.

The Bombay Red onion variety had the highest unmarketable bulb yield per hectare (0.59 t ha⁻¹), while the hybrid onion varieties generally produced the lowest unmarketable bulb yield per hectare. The unfertilized plot also produced the highest unmarketable bulb yield compared to the nitrogen fertilizer-supplied plots (Table 4.3), which could be attributed to the application of a suboptimal nitrogen supply that produced poor quality bulbs that contributed to a higher unmarketable onion yield. This result agrees with the findings of Awoke Ali *et al.* (2021), who reported the highest unmarketable bulb yield from unfertilized plots.

Table 4.3. Effects of variety and nitrogen on onion bulb yield

Onion varieties	Marketable bulb yield (t ha⁻¹)	Unmarketable bulb yield (t ha⁻¹)	Total dry bulb yield (t ha⁻¹)
Russet	26.50a	0.43c	26.93a
Red Coach	21.84b	0.50b	22.35b
Jambar	24.57a	0.51b	25.09a
Bombay Red	19.86b	0.59a	20.453b
P values	***	***	***
LSD _{0.05}	2.25	0.43	2.24
Nitrogen rate (kg ha⁻¹)			
0	19.09c	0.58a	19.68c
41	22.39b	0.51b	22.91b
82	26.77a	0.48b	27.26a
123	24.51b	0.46b	24.97b
P values	***	***	***
LSD _{0.05}	2.25	0.05	2.24
CV (%)	20.76	21.43	20.22

Where; ***= $p < 0.001$; ** = $P < 0.01$; and Ns = $P > 0.05$. Means followed by the same letter within the same column are not significantly different at the 5% probability level; LSD_{0.05}= least significant difference at the 5% probability level; and CV = coefficient of variation

4.3.3. Influence of nitrogen fertilizer on the bulb quality of onion varieties

The analysis of variance revealed that the main effects, as well as the two-way interaction effects of variety and nitrogen, had highly significant ($p < 0.01$) effects on the solid soluble content of onion bulbs. Onion pungency was influenced ($p < 0.001$) by the main effects of variety and nitrogen rate. However, the two-way interaction of nitrogen*variety did not significantly ($p > 0.05$) influence (Appendix Table 4.1).

In terms of the interaction effect, the Bombay Red variety received 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen and 123 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen, resulting in the highest TSS levels of 12.36 °Brix and 12.16 °Brix, respectively (Table 4.4). Increasing the nitrogen rate improves plant growth and development through increased photosynthetic activities and dry matter production (Brady, 1985), which could also be the case in the present study. In this context, Al-Fraihat (2009) reported that increasing the nitrogen fertilizer rate from 100 kg N ha⁻¹ to 200 kg N ha⁻¹ increased the TSS from 13.75% to 14.70%. Morsy *et al.* (2012) also reported that the application of 120 kg ha⁻¹ N led to the highest values of TSS, whereas the application of 90 kg nitrogen ha⁻¹ resulted in the lowest value of TSS. On the other hand, the differences in the TSS values observed in the present study could be attributed to the genetic makeup of onion varieties, as indicated by Chope *et al.* (2007). Generally, high-yield varieties with larger bulb sizes (higher bulb weights) have lower TSS contents than varieties with small bulbs and lower yields Mallor *et al.* (2010), which is the case for the Bombay Red variety in the present study.

Table 4.4. Variety and nitrogen effect on onion bulb pungency combined in the three locations

Treatment	TSS (%)	Pungency (μ mol./g)
Russet	9.25b	10.04 ^b
Red Coach	8.15c	8.82 ^c
Jambar	11.59a	8.541 ^c
Bombay Red	7.50d	10.71 ^a
Significance level	***	***
LSD _{0.05}	0.38	0.35
Nitrogen rate (kg ha⁻¹)		
0	8.51c	9.45 ^b
41	9.15b	9.45 ^b
82	9.15b	9.52 ^{ab}

123	9.67a	9.71 ^a
Significance level	***	**
LSD _{0.05}	0.33	0.34
CV (%)	9.00	9.8

Where; *** = very highly significant at $p < 0.001$; ** = highly significant at $p < 0.01$; * = significant at $p < 0.05$; ns = non-significance means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; LSD_{0.05} = Least significant difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation

Table 4.5. The TSS of onion varieties influenced by the interaction of variety and nitrogen combined in the three locations

Varieties	Nitrogen rate (kg ha ⁻¹)	TSS (°Brix)
Russet	0	6.86 ^g
	41	7.98 ^{ef}
	82	7.44 ^{fg}
	123	7.70 ^{fg}
Red Coach	0	7.66 ^{fg}
	41	7.90 ^{efg}
	82	8.10 ^{ef}
	123	8.93 ^{de}
Jambar	0	8.16 ^{ef}
	41	9.63 ^d
	82	9.30 ^d
	123	9.90 ^{cd}
Bombay Red	0	10.76 ^{bc}
	41	11.07 ^b
	82	12.36 ^a
	123	12.16 ^a
Significance level		**
LSD _{0.05}		1.06
CV(%)		9.00

Where; *** = very highly significant at $p < 0.001$; ** = highly significant at $p < 0.01$; * = significant at $p < 0.05$; ns = non-significance means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; LSD_{0.05} = Least significant difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation

The highest value of pungency measured as pyruvic acid (10.71 $\mu\text{mol/g}$) was recorded for the Bombay Red variety, followed by the Russet variety (10.04 $\mu\text{mol/g}$), whereas the lowest value of pungency was recorded for the Jambar variety (8.541 $\mu\text{mol/g}$), as indicated in Table 4.4.

Among the nitrogen fertilizers, the application of 123 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen resulted in the highest values of pungency (9.71 µmol/g), which was statistically similar to the results of the application of 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen (9.51 µmol/g). The bulbs produced without nitrogen fertilizer presented the lowest level (9.45 µmol/g) of pungency (Table 4.4.).

Pungency is one of the most important quality parameters of onion bulbs and is associated with the content of sulfur compounds. Pungency is influenced by onion variety, environmental conditions, and the management practices implemented (Da Silva *et al.*, 2022), which is in agreement with the findings of the present study. Like in the present study, Randle (2000) reported an increased level of bulb pungency with the application of nitrogen fertilizer, which could be explained by the synthesis and accumulation of sulfur-containing amino acids, which are precursors of flavoring compounds and pyruvate. According to Yoo *et al.* (2006) and Gallina *et al.* (2012), the pyruvic acid content is influenced by the environment, growing conditions and storage periods. Like in the present study, da Silva *et al.* (2022) reported that onion pungency was affected by variety, the growing season and the nitrogen fertilizer rate.

4.3.4. Economic analysis of onion as influenced by variety and nitrogen fertilizer rate

The partial budget analysis indicated that the application of 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen fertilizer (474,745 ETB ha⁻¹) and Russet (413,000 ETB ha⁻¹) and Jambar (378,260 ETB ha⁻¹) varieties across the three locations resulted in relatively high net benefits (Table 4.6). As shown in Figure 4.1, the application of 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen resulted in the highest bulb yield and the highest net return (Figure 4.3). An additional increase in the nitrogen rate beyond 82 kg ha⁻¹ reduced the net return of onion (Figure 4.3), which could be considered optimal for onion production in the study area.

Table 4.6. Partial budget analysis for onion production as influenced by variety and nitrogen fertilizer level across the three locations

Treatments	MY (t ha ⁻¹)	AMY (t ha ⁻¹)	GB (Birr/ha)	TVC (Birr/ha)	Net benefit (Birr/ha)	Dominance analysis	MRR (%)
Variety							

Bombay Red	19.86	17.874	357480	18000	339480	-	-
Jambar	24.57	22.113	442260	64000	378260		84.3
Russet	26.5	23.85	477000	64000	413000		159.83
Red Coach	21.84	19.656	393120	64000	329120	D	-
Nitrogen rate							
(kg ha⁻¹)							
0	19.09	17.181	343620	0	343620	-	-
41	22.39	20.151	403020	3557.6	399462		1569.665
82	26.77	24.093	481860	7115.2	474745		2116.101
123	24.51	22.059	441180	10672.8	430507	D	-

Note: MY = marketable yield; AMY = adjusted marketable yield; GB = gross benefit, TVC=total variable cost, NB = net benefit; D = dominated and MRR = marginal rate of return.

Figure 4.3. Polynomial curve fit and regression equation illustrating the relationship between nitrogen rate (kg ha⁻¹) and net benefit (Birr ha⁻¹)

4.4. Conclusions and Recommendations

The onion growth and yield parameters were influenced by the nitrogen fertilizer rate and variety across the three locations. Compared with the open pollinated Bombay Red variety, the hybrid varieties (Russet and Jambar) performed well in terms of bulb diameter, bulb weight, total yield, and marketable bulb yield parameters. In general, the highest growth and yield

parameters of onion were recorded when nitrogen fertilizer was supplied at a rate of 82 kg ha⁻¹. The onion plants supplied with 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen recorded the highest marketable bulb yield of 26.77. The experiment indicated that too much N (above 82 kg ha⁻¹) leads to decreased yield; hence, excess N is lost to the environment.

The Russet and Jambar varieties recorded the highest marketable bulb yields, with values of 26.50 t ha⁻¹ and 24.57 t ha⁻¹, respectively. The Russet and Jambar varieties and the 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen rate also recorded the greatest net benefit across all three locations. Given the significant economic benefits associated with their higher marketable yields, Russet and Jambar are recommended for production, particularly in northwest Amhara, where yield is prioritized. Therefore, Jambar and Russet varieties and the application of 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen fertilizer, are recommended for the economical production of onions in areas of the study area with similar agroecology. Since this study was the first of its kind in the study area, other hybrid onion varieties should be considered, and agronomic practices such as spacing and phosphorous fertilizer should be optimized in future research. In addition, further research is required to enhance the quality characteristics of the high yielding varieties.

Chapter 5: INFLUENCE OF CULTIVAR AND PLANT DENSITY ON THE GROWTH, YIELD AND QUALITY OF ONION (*Allium cepa*)

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Published by Springer Nature, Journal of Scientific Reports

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-79490-0>

Abstract

Onion is the most important and widely cultivated cash-generating crop in Ethiopia. Onion production is limited by several factors, and its production and productivity are low. Among the many contributing factors, a lack of improved cultivars and improper plant density are the major limiting factors. This study was focused on the impacts of planting density and onion varieties on growth, bulb yield and quality of onion. Three hybrid onion cultivars and one open-pollinated onion cultivar were evaluated at three testing sites (Koga, Woramit and Woreta) under irrigation conditions in 2021/2022 via a randomized complete block design with three replications. The results of the present study revealed that the growth and yield of onion plants were influenced by the main effects of plant density and onion cultivar across locations. The Russet and Jambar hybrid cultivar, which had a relatively high plant density, exhibited superior performance across all locations. They consistently presented the highest values of bulb diameter, average bulb weight, harvest index, firmness, total bulb yield and marketable bulb yield across all locations. The marketable bulb yield was positively correlated with the bulb weight and bulb diameter of the onion. The Russet (28.09 t ha⁻¹) and Jambar (26.61 t ha⁻¹) cultivars presented the highest marketable bulb yields and were generally superior in terms of most of the growth, yield and quality parameters. The highest marketable bulb yield (28.42 t ha⁻¹) was recorded for the onion cultivars in the higher plant population (666,666 plants ha⁻¹), in which the spacing was 5 cm × 20 cm × 40 cm between plants, rows and double rows.

Accordingly, the use of hybrid onion cultivars (Russet and Jambar) along with higher plant populations (5 cm between plants × 20 cm between rows × 40 cm between double rows) is recommended in the study area and areas with similar agroecology. Since this study was the first of its kind in the study area, it is advisable to consider other hybrid onion cultivars with relatively high plant densities.

Keywords: Hybrid onion cultivar, Marketable bulb yield, Plant density, Russet cultivar

5.1. Introduction

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is a highly valuable bulb crop in the *Allium* genus of the Alliaceae family. Onion is believed to have originated in Iran, western Pakistan and Central Asia (Brewster, 2008). Onion is a cool-season bulb crop that adapts to diverse environmental conditions, and thrives at altitudes between 500 and 2400 m.a.s.l., with an optimal range of 700–2200 m.a.s.l. The ideal growing temperature for onions falls between 15 °C and 24 °C. Moreover, the crop is highly influenced by photoperiods like short-day and long-day cultivars. Only short-day cultivars are grown in Ethiopia (Shimeles Aklilu, 1997). Onion prefers well-drained sandy loam soil with a high content of organic matter and a pH ranging from 6.2 to 7.0 (Lemma Dessalegn and Shimelis Aklilu, 2003; MoARD, 2019).

Ethiopia ranks as the third largest onion producer in Africa, next to Egypt and South Africa, yet its global contribution is only 2.7% (FAOSTAT, 2020). In the growing season 2021/2022, an average of 38,952.58 ha of land was covered by onions, with an average productivity of 11.70 tons ha⁻¹, notably below the world average of 21.1 tons ha⁻¹ (CSA, 2020; FAOSTAT, 2022). Despite a 59.7% increase in onion cultivation area between 2015 and 2020, productivity declined by 25.7% (CSA, 2020).

The Amhara region, which has diverse agroecology and fertile soil, is conducive to vegetable production. However, challenges, such as lack of improved cultivars, improper planting density, inappropriate agronomic practices, climatic fluctuations, poor handling, poor seed quality, and high postharvest losses, hinder the vegetable sector, particularly onion cultivation

(Kassa Getu and Ahmed Ibrahim, 2018; Addisu Hailu *et al.*, 2017; Agidew Abebe., 2018; Almaz Giziew, 2018; Taye Melese *et al.*, 2018; Muluneh Bekele *et al.*, 2019). In particular, Kassa Getu and Ahmed Ibrahim (2018) emphasized the crucial role of improved cultivars and proper agronomic practices in addressing these challenges.

Agricultural research institute in Ethiopia have introduced 28 onion cultivars, including 10 improved open-pollinated cultivars and 18 hybrid types, aiming to increase onion production (Lemma Dessalegn and Shimelis Aklilu, 2003; MoARD, 2019). Despite these achievements, additional research is needed to optimize the agronomic practices to complete the production packages, particularly for hybrid onion cultivars.

Evaluation and use of high-yielding onion cultivars is the best strategy for improving onion productivity (Ahmed *et al.*, 2013). In Ethiopia, many farmers, especially in the Amhara Region, traditionally use open-pollinated cultivars such as Bombay Red and Adama Red which have narrow intrarow spacing. However, in recent years, hybrid onion cultivars with different practices of spacing have been introduced; some adhere to outdated recommendations for open-pollinated cultivars 10 cm between plants and 20 cm between rows, while others use undefined spacing (Gebremedhn Gebretsadkan *et al.*, 2018; Yebirzaf Yeshiwas *et al.*, 2023).

Plant spacing is a critical factor influenced by cultivar, the growing environment, and the production system (Lemma Dessalegn and Shimelis Aklilu, 2003). Optimization of the plant population, considering cultivar, environmental conditions and soil fertility, significantly impacts onion bulb characteristics, yield, and quality (Brewster, 1994; Chang *et al.*, 2015; Alemu Direbsa, 2022). Wider spacing enhances yield per plant, whereas closer spacing increases yield per unit area up to a certain point (Abubaker, 2008; Bhuiyan *et al.*, 2012; Alemu Direbsa *et al.*, 2022).

Proper plant spacing minimizes competition among plants for essential growth factors, optimizing light, water, and nutrient utilization (Candian *et al.*, 2017). Efficient land use without wastage is achieved through optimal plant populations per unit area, a crucial factor in enhancing onion productivity (Geremew Awas *et al.*, 2010; Zubelidia and Gases, 1977).

Ongoing and future researches should be focused on improving agronomic practices to fully realize the potential of hybrid onion cultivars and improve overall onion productivity in Ethiopia. Therefore, the present study aimed to investigate the effect of population density and cultivar on the productivity of onion in northern Amhara, Ethiopia.

5.1.1. Hypotheses testing

The hypotheses in the present study are as follows:

Null Hypothesis (H0) There is no significant difference in onion growth, yield, and quality traits, among plant population density and onion cultivars.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1) There are significant differences in onion growth, yield, and quality traits, due to plant population density and onion cultivars

5.2. Materials and Methods

5.2.1. Description of the study area

Field experiments were carried out at three potential onion-producing locations Yebirzaf Yeshiwas et al. (2024a), namely, the North Mecha (Koga), Fogera (Woreta) and Bahir Dar Zuria (Woramit) districts of the Amhara region (Figure 2.1), during the 2021/2022 irrigation season. The geographical locations, altitudes, average, minimum and maximum temperatures, rainfall, and soil types of the districts are presented in Table 2.1. The average maximum and minimum temperatures of Woreta and Woramit during the experimental period were 29 °C and 17.8 °C and 28 °C and 12.4 °C, respectively. The Koga experimental site had mean maximum and minimum temperatures of 28.8 °C and 9.5 °C, respectively, as indicated in Fig. 2.2 (Regional Meteorological Station, 2022).

5.2.2. Experimental materials

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) plants was used in this study. The seeds of hybrid onion varieties such as onion varieties and were used from commercial suppliers (Eshet Agricultural Input Supplier, Bahir Dar, Ethiopia), while the seeds of an open pollinated Bombay Red variety were collected from Melkassa Agricultural Research Center (MARC), Melkassa Ethiopia.

Hybrid F₁ onion varieties such as Russet, Red Coach, and Jambar, and an open-pollinated Bombay Red variety as the local check, were used as a test crop. These onion varieties were selected based on the results of the preliminary pilot survey in which farmers preferred them due to their growth and yield performance (Yebirzaf Yeshiwas *et al.*, 2023). The general characteristic of the selected onion varieties is presented in Table 2.3

5.2.3 Experimental treatments and design

The experiments consisted of four onion cultivars and three levels of intra row spacing (5, 10, 15 cm), with plant populations of high (666,666), medium (333,333) and low (222,222) plants ha⁻¹. The treatments were laid out in the randomized complete block design (RCBD) with 4 × 3 factorial arrangements and three replications. Each treatment combination was randomly assigned to experimental units within a block at each location. The gross plot size was 1.6 m × 1.6 m (2.56 m²). The blocks were separated by one meter, while the space between each plot within a block was 0.5 m.

5.2.4. Experimental procedures and agronomic management

The seeds of each variety were seeded on well-prepared raised beds and mulched with straw. After germination, the mulching material was removed. Watering was carried out using a fine watering can, and the frequency of watering was determined according to the climatic conditions. The seedlings were maintained for 55 days after sowing and hardened before being transplanted to the field. This was done by reducing the frequency of watering and leaving the soil at a low moisture level when the seedlings were ready to be planted in the field.

Healthy and vigorous seedlings of 12–15 cm height were carefully uprooted and transplanted in to the experimental plots with the recommended double row planting system: 40 cm between irrigation furrows, 20 cm spacing between rows, and 5 cm, 10 cm, and 15 cm intra-row spacing with a population of high, medium and low plants per hectare, respectively. In each plot, there were three double rows (MoARD., 2019).

All other agronomic practices were applied uniformly for all the treatments according to the recommendation for onions (MoARD., 2004). Nitrogen fertilizer was applied at a rate of 82 kg

ha⁻¹, using urea (which contains 46% nitrogen) (Yebirzaf Yesiwas et al., 2024b). This application was split into two equal parts: the first half was applied 15 days after transplanting, once the seedlings had established, and the second half was applied during the vegetative growth stage. Phosphorus fertilizer, in the form of triple superphosphate (46% P₂O₅), was applied at a rate of 92 g ha⁻¹. The entire quantity of phosphorus fertilizer was incorporated into the soil at the time of transplanting (Nikus Olani and Fekir Mulugeta, 2010).

Irrigation water was applied using a furrow irrigation system at four-day intervals for the first four weeks and then extended to seven-day intervals until the crops reached the physiological maturity stage. Water application was stopped 15 days before harvest (IPGRI, 2001; MoARD., 2004).

5.2.5. Data collection

The growth, yield and quality parameters of the onion were collected from central rows with net plot areas of 1.86 m², 1.8 m², and 1.74 m² at 5, 10, 15 cm intra row spacing, respectively. Parameters were collected using the standard procedures described under section 2.5. Onion bulbs were harvest when 70% of the plants in each plot experienced neck fall (MoARD, 2004; MoARD, 2016).

5.2.6. Data analysis

The collected data were initially checked to meet all ANOVA assumptions (normality, homogeneity and residual) after Levene`s homogeneity test. The data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the PROC MIXED procedure of SAS computer software version 9.0. Plant density and onion cultivar were considered fixed effects, and location was considered as a random effect. When ANOVA revealed significant differences ($P < 0.05$), the mean separation was carried out using Tukey`s Honestly significant difference (THSD) test.

5.3. Results and Discussion

5.3.1. Effects of plant density on the phenology and vegetative traits of onion cultivars

Days to physiological maturity

The number of days required to reach physiological maturity was significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced by the main effects of onion cultivar, and density. The two-way interaction of cultivar density did not influence the physiological maturity of onion (Appendix Table 5.1).

The Russet onion cultivar reached maturity earlier than Bomby Red cultivar, with differences of 13 days, as indicated in (Table 5.1). Previous studies have shown differences in maturity among onion cultivars (Hannachi et al., 2014; Zeleke et al., 2021). Variations in physiological maturity also reflect genotypic differences in onion cultivars in the length of growth period and maturity, which affects the transfer of photosynthetic materials from leaves to bulbs and the improvement of the growth rate, thus early bulb initiation and maturity (Pardeshi and Waskar, 2012).

The physiological maturity of the hybrid cultivars is generally earlier than that of the open-pollinated cultivars due to heterosis and genetic uniformity. These plants also exhibit increased photosynthetic efficiency and the breeding is targeted for early maturity, ensuring timely harvests and multiple cropping cycles (Labro et al., 2021). Similar results were reported where significant variations in days to maturity among onion cultivars were observed (Fikre and Mensa, 2021; Alemu Diribsa *et al.*, 2022)

Furthermore, the Russet onion cultivar showed early in physiological maturity due to its ideal leaf number of leaves per plant (9). These findings are in line with the findings of Kebede (2003) and Cramer (2001), and Birhanu and Tilahun (2023), who claimed that hybrid onion cultivars matured earlier than open-pollinated ones. With respect to plant density, a significant delay in maturity was observed as the plant population decreased. Early maturity was recorded at the highest plant density, while onion plants planted at low plant population required longer days to mature across the three locations (Table 5.1). The early maturity of a high-density plant population may be caused by an inadequate supply of water and nutrients to prolong growth and metabolic processes. Plant density also influences physiological maturity by intensifying competition for abiotic factors such as light, water, and nutrients, which ultimately accelerate

maturity as plants allocate more resources to reproduction (Chapepa et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021). These results are consistent with the findings of Hidayatullah and Jillani (2018), who reported that plants grown at greater density had the shortest time to mature. Similar findings have been reported in where plants grown at the lowest density took longer time to reach maturity while those at the highest density matured earlier (Habtamu Tegen *et al.*, 2016; Dasash Atalay *et al.*, 2022).

Table 5.1. Effects of cultivar and plant density on the number of days to physiological maturity of onion plants

Onion cultivars	Days to physiological maturity
Russet	93.7c
Red Coach	99.4b
Jambar	98.8b
Bombay Red	105.2a
THSD _{0.05}	4.3
Density	
Low (222,222)	99.7a
Medium (333,333)	99.2a
High (666,666)	96.2b
THSD _{0.05}	3.4
Cultivar	***
Density	**
Cul. x Den.	ns
CV (%)	6.09

where; *** = very highly significant at $p < 0.001$; ** = highly significant at $p < 0.01$; * = significant at $p < 0.05$; ns = nonsignificance means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; THSD_{0.05} = Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation.

Plant height

The combined analysis across locations revealed that onion plant height was influenced ($p < 0.001$) by cultivar and density. However, the interactions between cultivar and density did not influence onion plant height (Appendix Table 5.1).

The highest plant height was recorded for the Bombay Red cultivar, which was not significantly different from that of Red Coach and Jambar, while the lowest plant height was recorded for Russet cultivar. Onion seedlings transplanted at the lowest density of 222,222 and 333,333

plants ha⁻¹ showed the longest plants with a height of 52.56 cm and 51.8 cm, respectively, while high density plants had the shortest plant height Figure 5.1.

Scholars have also observed significant differences in plant height between onion cultivars (Geremew Awas, 2010; Gebretsadkan Gebremedhn *et al.*, 2018 and Wassie Wubetie *et al.*, 2022). Plant height is directly influenced by the availability of growth factors and their capacity to compete for these factors within a plant population. In densely populated plants, there is strong competition for water, nutrients, and light that leads to the production of short plants. However, in less populated plants, plants can fulfill their requirements for growth and development, thus leading to the production of longer plants. These findings are in line with the results of Alemu Diribsa *et al.* (2022) and Wassie Wubetie *et al.* (2022), which who observed tallest onion plants at the lowest plant densities.

Figure 5.1. Effects of cultivar and density on the diameter of the onion bulb neck at the three locations

Leaf number per plant

The number of leaves per onion plant was highly significantly ($p < 0.001$) influenced by cultivar and plant density. However, the two-way interaction of cultivar and density did not influence the number of onion leaf per plant (Appendix Table 5.1). Consequently, the highest mean leaf number was obtained for the Bombay Red cultivar which was significantly statistically similar

to that of Jambar. The densest onion plants produced the lowest number of leaves per plant (8.27), while the less populated plants produced the highest number of plants, as indicated in Table 5.2.

These results are in agreement with the findings of other scholars who reported significant differences in leaf number between onion cultivars (Ayam et al., 2014; Bindu and Podikunju, 2015; Kokobe and Hirut, 2021). In this regard, Steer (1980) reported that Bombay Red bulbs produced more splitter bulbs/shoots from multiple growing points, which facilitated the production of more leaves per plant as indicated in the present study.

As indicated in the present study, the planting density and the number of leaves are inversely related. As the population of the plant increased, the number of leaves per onion plant decreased. The lowest number of leaves observed at the highest plant density was probably attributed to the increased competition between plants for nutrients and moisture. Brewster (2008), suggested that onion plants with approximately 6 to 8 fully expanded leaves are capable of sustaining optimal photosynthetic activity. Researchers also reported similar results in which more leaves per plant were recorded at the lowest plant density, while fewer leaves were produced on highly populated onion plants (Nasir *et al.*, 2007; Mekdes Atakelt, 2012; Alemu Deribsa *et al.*, 2022). Akoun (2005) also observed that the plant population significantly influenced different onion parameters including the number of leaves produced per plant, leaf area, bulb diameter, and yield.

Leaf diameter (cm)

The combined analysis of variance showed that the main effects were highly significantly ($p < 0.001$) influenced the diameter of the onion leaf. On the other hand, the interactions between cultivar and density did not influence onion leaf diameter ($p > 0.05$) (Appendix Table 5.1).

The greatest mean leaf diameter was recorded for the Russet and Jambar cultivars. Similarly, plants grown at the lowest population density had the greatest leaf diameter, while the lowest leaf diameter was recorded from plants grown at the highest plant density (Table 5.2).

Generally, the leaves of hybrid onion cultivars (Russet and Jambar) were wider than those of the open pollinated Bombay Red cultivar. Cramer (2001) and Chen and Chen (2013) reported that hybrid onion cultivars tend to produce wider leaves than open-pollinated cultivars. Breeders intentionally select wider leaf traits from parental lines to develop hybrids with enhanced qualities, yield, disease resistance, and adaptability to diverse environmental conditions.

The wider leaf diameter recorded at the lowest plant density might be due to the presence of sufficient light in the wider-spaced plants, which is essential for photosynthesis and nutrient uptake compared to those of the closely spaced plants. These results are in agreement with the findings of many authors who also reported significant variation in leaf diameter due to differences in plant density (Yemane Kahsay, 2011; Seid and Fikirte, 2014; Guesh Tekle, 2015; Demisie and Tolessa, 2018).

Table 5.2. Effects of onion cultivar and plant density on leaf number and diameter across three locations

Onion cultivars	Leaf number per plant	Leaf diameter
Russet	8.5c	8.7a
Red Coach	9.1bc	7.4b
Jambar	9.0b	9.1a
Bombay Red	10.0a	7.2b
THSD _{0.05}	0.57	0.9
Density		
Low (222,222)	10.0a	8.6a
Medium (333,333)	9.1b	8.2ab
High (666,666)	8.2c	7.6b
THSD _{0.05}	0.4	0.7
Cultivar	***	***
Density	***	**
Cul. x Den.	ns	ns
CV (%)	8.81	15.05

Where; *** = very highly significant at $p < 0.001$; ** = highly significant at $p < 0.01$; * = significant at $p < 0.05$; ns = non-significance means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; THSD_{0.05} = Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation.

5.3.2. Effects of plant population on bulb yield and yield-related traits

Bulb neck diameter (cm)

The results of analysis of the variance indicate that the diameter of the onion bulb neck was significantly ($P < 0.01$) influenced by the main effects of density and cultivar. However, the two-way interaction of cultivar and density did not significantly influence onion bulb neck diameter ($p > 0.05$) (Appendix Table 5.1).

The Bombay Red cultivar had the widest neck diameter which was statistically similar to that of the Red Coach, while the lowest bulb neck diameter was obtained from Russet, which was statistically similar to that of the Jambar cultivar. On the other hand, the highest bulb neck diameter was recorded from the lowest (222,222 ha⁻¹ plants) plant density while the highest plant density (666,666 plant ha⁻¹) recorded the lowest bulb neck diameter (Figure 5.2).

The genetic composition and inherent traits of onion cultivars contribute to the differences in bulb neck diameters as reported by (Fery and Eissa, 2002), which could also be the case in the present study. The findings by Gautam *et al.* (2019) also indicated varying bulb neck diameter in different onion genotypes.

The wider bulb neck diameter observed in plants grown with a wider plant spacing (lowest plant density) is associated with less competition from plants for growth factors. Under these circumstances, the vegetative growth of the plants is enhanced which in turn leads to wider bulb neck diameter, as indicated in the present study. On the other hand, high plant populations may have exerted pressure on the scarcity of growth factors such as light, space, moisture, and nutrients, leading to reduced vegetative growth and narrow bulb neck diameter (Khan *et al.*, 2003). According to Wubetie (2022), planting onions at higher densities can lead to smaller bulbs and reduced neck diameters, as plants compete for growth resources, while lower planting densities can promote better bulb growth and potentially result in larger neck diameters.

Figure 5.2. Effects of cultivar and density on the diameter of the onion bulb neck at the three locations

Average bulb diameter (cm) and bulb weight (g)

The results of analysis of variance indicated a highly significant difference ($P < 0.01$) among the cultivars and plant densities for the diameter of the onion bulb. However, the effects of the cultivar-density interaction did not influence the diameter of the onion bulb (Appendix Table 5.1). The average bulb weight of onions was influenced ($p < 0.001$) by the main effects of cultivar and density. The interactions between cultivar and density did not have a significant impact on onion bulb weight ($p > 0.05$) as shown in Appendix Table 5.1.

Hybrid onion cultivars produced bulbs with the largest diameter and weight, which were statistically comparable to each other. In contrast, the Bombay Red cultivar exhibited the smallest diameter and weight (Table 5.3). The higher plant density resulted in smaller bulb diameters and lighter weights than lower plant density did (Table 5.3).

The diameter and weight of the bulb signify the potential for onion yield. These hybrid cultivars excel compared to the local open pollinated Bombay Red cultivar due to inherent differences.

This finding aligns with the findings of Kokobe and Hirut (2021), who noted significant variations in onion cultivar for length, diameter, and weight.

Intense competition for resources negatively impacts overall onion plant performance and reduces bulb diameter and weight. Densely populated onion plants experience restricted nutrient availability, limited sunlight interception, decreased photosynthetic activity, and water stress, which hinder bulb expansion. Previous researches conducted by Brewster (2008), Alemu Direbsa et al. (2022), and Yldrm and Ciftci (2011), support the findings of the present study. Furthermore, studies by Jilani et al. (2009), Sikder et al. (2010), Muhammad et al. (2011) confirmed that decreasing plant density results in increased weight and size of individual onion bulbs.

Table 5.3. The main effects of cultivar and density on onion average bulb diameter and bulb weight across the three locations

Onion cultivars	Bulb diameter (cm)	Bulb weight (g)	Harvest index
Russet	67.2a	102.2a	87.3a
Red Coach	65.8ab	102.2a	83.5b
Jambar	68.3a	100.9a	86.2ab
Bombay Red	62.6b	84.9b	80.1c
THSD _{0.05}	4.4	9.0	34.29
Density			
Low (222,222)	68.5a	104.7a	83.6
Medium(333,333)	66.1ab	99.8a	85.7
High (666,666)	63.3b	88.2b	83.6
THSD _{0.05}	3.4	7.1	3.4
Cultivar	**	***	**
Density	**	***	ns
Cul. x Den.	ns	ns	ns
CV (%)	9.36	12.91	7.11

Where; *** = very highly significant at $p < 0.001$; ** = highly significant at $p < 0.01$; * = significant at $p < 0.05$; ns = non-significance means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; THSD_{0.05} = Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation

Total bulb yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$)

The combined analysis of variance showed that cultivar and plant density significantly influenced the total bulb yield ($p < 0.0001$). The two-way interaction of cultivar and density did not affect total bulb yield (Appendix Table 5.1).

Russet had the highest bulb yield, which was statistically similar to that of Jambar, while Bombay Red had the lowest yield. Increasing the plant density to 666,666 plants ha⁻¹ Table 5.4, increased the total bulb yield. The different plant densities contributed to 42.43% of the yield variation. This underscores the importance of cultivar and planting density in optimizing the onion yield.

The yield of onions depends on cultivar, environmental conditions, and agronomic practices and is influenced by the genetic makeup and the interaction of the genotype and environment (Jilani and Ghaffoor, 2003; Yemane Kahsay et al., 2014; Bindu and Bindu, 2015; Das et al., 2015; Tegbew Walle et al., 2018; Gautam, et al., 2019). Hybrid onion cultivars consistently outperformed open-pollinated Bombay Red cultivar, which also align with the findings in tomato cultivation (Islam *et al.*, 2012; Devkota *et al.*, 2018). An increase in plant density also correlates with the increase in garlic bulb yield as supported by Hemla and Hosmani (2003), and Fikreyohannes Gedamu (2005). This highlights the impact of genetic factors and planting density on improving onion and garlic productivity.

The plant population, the number of plants per unit area, directly affects the yield of onion bulbs. Similar to the results of the present study Geremew Awas (2010), Kantona et al. (2003), AVRDC (2004), Sara Belay (2015), and Yohannes Gebremichael et al. (2019) reported that increasing the plant population from 222,222 to 666,666 plants ha⁻¹ led to a 42.4% increase in total bulb yield. Kantona et al. (2003) also observed an increase in onion yield from 17.4 to 39.5 t ha⁻¹ with an increase in plant population from 50 to 150 plants per square meter. However, the higher population density resulted reduction in the diameter and weight of individual onion bulbs (Table 5.3), which is consistent with the findings of other researchers (Sikder et al., 2010). According to Zobelida and Gases (1977), optimizing plant populations prevents intense competition between plants for growth factors and helps efficient utilization of available cropland. He et al. (2022); AL-Naggar et al. (2021) reported that high plant density resulted in the highest grain yield for hybrid maize cultivars, which reflects that hybrids exhibit greater density tolerance, contributing to their superior performance in terms of grain yield.

Marketable bulb yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$)

Analysis of variance revealed that cultivar and plant density influenced ($p < 0.001$) the marketable bulb yield of onion, while the two-way interactions did not influence the marketable bulb yield of onion (Appendix Table 5.1).

The highest marketable bulb yield across the three locations was obtained from the Russet and Jambar cultivars, where the yields were statistically similar. However, the lowest marketable bulb yield was recorded for the cultivar Bombay Red. Onion plants grown at the highest plant density produced the highest marketable bulb yield followed by those grown at the medium plant density. The plants grown in the lowest plant population produced the lowest marketable bulb yield as shown in Table 5.4.

The marketable yield of onion generally showed an increasing trend and reached a plateau at higher densities, which was found to be optimal for onion production across all locations. However, a further increase in the plant population reduced the marketable bulb yield, as shown in Figure 5.3. The marketable yield increased with increasing plant density due to the accommodation of more plants per unit area, which in turn increased the bulb yield per unit area. However, this increase in bulb yield depends on the availability of enough nutrients and other growth factors. In this regard, Khan et al. (2003) and Yemane Kahsay et al. (2013) indicated that as the plant density decreased from 666,666 plants ha^{-1} to 333,333 plants ha^{-1} , the marketable bulb yield decreased from 34.49 $t\ ha^{-1}$ to 28.10 $t\ ha^{-1}$. Similarly, Kantona et al. (2003) also reported an increase in the number of marketable bulb yields with the increased onion plant density. Therefore, plant density is the determining factor of marketable yield at varying locations (Kim and Park, 2023).

As indicated in Fig. 5.4a and 5.4b, marketable yield of onion has a positive relationship with diameter and weight of onion bulbs. On the other hand, bulb weight has a negative relationship with days to physiological maturity (Figure. 5.4c).

The highest marketable yields observed by Russet and Jambar in the present study were attributed to the increase in the diameter and weight of onion bulbs as indicated in Table 5.3. The difference in yield potential is associated with the genetic variation of the cultivars as reported by various researchers where marketable bulb yield variations were observed between onion cultivars (Geremew Awas *et al.*, 2010; Hailu Dinka *et al.*, 2015; Gebremedhn Gebretsadkan *et al.*, 2018, and Alemu *et al.*, 2022). In recent meta-analyses conducted by Garcia and Nguyen (2023), onion cultivar had a significant impact on marketable bulb yield. The analysis revealed that specific cultivars consistently outperformed others, regardless of the planting density or specific environmental conditions.

Figure 5.3. Trends in marketable onion bulb yield are influenced by plant density across locations

Unmarketable bulb yield (%)

The analysis of variance indicated that the cultivar influenced ($P < 0.0001$) the unmarketable bulb yield of onion, while the density and the two-way interactions did not influence the unmarketable bulb yield (Appendix Table 5.1).

The highest percentage of unmarketable bulb yield was obtained from the Bombay Red and Red Coach cultivars, while the lowest percentage of unmarketable bulb yield was recorded from the Russet and Jambar cultivars (Table 5.4). The difference in unmarketable yield could be attributed to the genetic variation of the onion cultivars. Fikre and Mensa (2021) reported

similar results, in which variations in unmarketable bulb yield were observed between different onion cultivars. Wubetie Adnew *et al.* (2022) indicated that the unmarketable bulb yield of onion cultivars was not significantly affected by density and the interaction of cultivar and density.

Table 5.4. Responses of onion bulb yield to cultivar and plant population across the three locations

Cultivars	Marketable yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Unmarketable yield (%)	Total yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Russet	28.1a	0.9b	28.5a
Red Coach	23.1b	1.8a	24.5b
Jambar	26.6a	0.9b	27.2ab
Bombay Red	18.8c	1.9a	19.4c
THSD _{0.05}	4.4	0.2	4.4
Density			
Low (222,222)	20.5c	1.3	20.9c
Medium (333,333)	23.5b	1.4	23.8b
High (666,666)	28.4a	1.3	29.8a
THSD _{0.05}	3.4	0.2	3.4
Cultivar	***	***	***
Density	***	ns	***
Cul. x Den.	ns	ns	ns
CV%	25.86	30.85	28.81

Where; *** = very highly significant at $p < 0.001$; ** = highly significant at $p < 0.01$; * = significant at $p < 0.05$; ns = nonsignificance means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; THSD_{0.05} = Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation

Figure 5.4. Trends in marketable bulb yield influenced by (a), bulb diameter; (b), bulb weight; and (c) bulb weight as related to days to physiological maturity across plant density and locations

Harvest index

Analysis of variance revealed that cultivar influenced ($P < 0.001$) the onion harvest index, while plant population and two-way interactions did not influence the onion harvest index (Appendix Table 5.1).

The highest mean harvest index was recorded for the Russet cultivar, which was statistically similar to that of the Jambar cultivar, while the lowest harvest index was recorded for the Bombay Red cultivar as indicated in Table 5.3. The harvest index is a measure of the success of the partitioning of photosynthetic assimilates. The harvest index is variable and calculated to reflect the crop performance (Gemechu Asefa, 2019). In this sense, the greater harvest index of the Russet and Jambar onion cultivars observed in the present study could be attributed to the higher average bulb weight of the cultivars, as indicated in Table 5.3. These results are in agreement with the findings of Tegbew Walle et al. (2018) who reported significant variations in the harvest index between onion varieties.

5.3.3. Marketable bulb yield distribution

The combined analysis of variance revealed that cultivar and plant population/density influenced ($p < 0.001$) the percentage of small, medium and large bulbs of onion. The two-way density–cultivar interaction significantly ($p < 0.001$) influenced the percentages of medium and large bulbs (Appendix Table 5.1).

Increasing the density of the plant significantly increased the percentage of small bulb yield. The highest small bulb percentages were recorded for the Bombay Red cultivar and the highest planting density, respectively (Table 5.5). In the interaction effect the highest percentage of medium-sized bulbs was recorded by the treatment combination of Russet x high population density, Jamber x high population density and Bombay Red x medium population density, which were statistically similar when compared each other. Similarly, Russet and Jamber combined with high plant density recorded the highest percentage of large-sized bulbs (Table 5.6).

Increasing the density of the plant significantly increased the percentage of small bulbs, but decreased the percentage of large bulbs of onion cultivars as indicated in Figure 5.5. This could be due to resource constraints at high densities that encourage the growth of smaller bulbs to ensure survival and reproduction even in the face of scarce supplies. According to Uddin et al. (2012), high plant population causes a larger proportion of small bulbs in the total output. Several scholars have reported similar results in which increasing the plant density decreased onion bulb sizes (Jilani *et al.*, 2009; Yemane Kahsay *et al.*, 2013). According to Yemane et al. (2013), decreasing the plant population from 666,666 plants ha⁻¹ to 333,333 plants ha⁻¹ increased the percentage of large bulbs from 9.3 to 20.3%. On the other hand, planting onion plants at higher densities results in the formation of smaller bulbs (Yohannes Gelaye et al., 2024).

All onion cultivars grown at a medium planting density produced the highest percentage of medium-sized bulb yield (Table 5.6). Onion bulbs of Russet and Jambar grown at the highest plant density produced significantly greater percentage of medium-sized bulbs than bulbs grown at a lower plant density. This might be due to proper utilization of resources for all onions compared to lower densities (Uddin *et al.*, 2012).

These results are in agreement with the findings of Rumpel et al. (2000), who reported that the yield of medium bulbs increased with increased density while the yield of large bulbs decreased. Similarly, Nasir et al. (2007) and Rumpel et al. (2000) reported that maximum weights of medium-sized bulbs were obtained at higher planting densities.

Table 5.5. Effects of cultivar and density on percentage of small bulbs across the three locations

Cultivars	Small-sized bulb (%)
Russet	24.4b
Red Coach	28.9b
Jambar	25.9b
Bombay Red	40.5a
THSD _{0.05}	8.5
Density	
Low (222,222)	40.4a
Medium (333,333)	25.4b
High (666,666)	23.9b
THSD _{0.05}	6.5
Cultivar	**
Density	**
Cul. x Den.	ns
CV (%)	29.92

Where; ** = highly significant at $p < 0.01$; * = significant at $p < 0.05$; ns = non-significance means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; THSD_{0.05} = Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation

Table 5.6. Onion size distribution affected by cultivar-density interaction across locations

Cultivars	Density	Medium bulb (%)	Large bulb (%)
Russet	Low (222,222)	35.3c	18.7cd
	Medium (333,333)	49.1ab	28.0abcd
	High (666,666)	51.5a	44.2ab
Red Coach	Low (222,222)	38.5bc	25.9abcd
	Medium (333,333)	43.8abc	29.3abc
	High (666,666)	39.1bc	36.7abc
Jambar	Low (222,222)	34.2c	12.4d
	Medium (333,333)	42.1abc	32.7abc
	High (666,666)	51.6a	49.0a
Bombay Red	Low (222,222)	38.2bc	3.8d
	Medium (333,333)	51.3a	19.5bcd
	High (666,666)	45.4abcd	20.5bcd
Significance level		**	*
THSD _{0.05}		17.0	25.3
CV (%)		29.14	30.89

Where; ** = highly significant at $p < 0.01$; * = significant at $p < 0.05$; ns = nonsignificance means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; THSD_{0.05} = Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation

Figure 5.5. Trends in the distribution of bulb size as affected by plant density across the three locations

5.3.4. Quality parameters of onion

Total soluble solid (°Brix)

The combined analysis of variance showed that cultivar, plant density, and their two-way interactions influenced ($p < 0.01$) the total soluble solid (TSS) of the onion plants (Appendix Table 5.1). Bombay Red, which was grown at the lowest density followed by Jambar had the highest total soluble solids, while the Red Coach cultivar recorded the lowest TSS. Onion bulbs harvested from plants grown in the lowest plant population recorded the highest TSS, while those harvested from highly populated plants recorded the lowest TSS (Table 5.7).

Total soluble solids are the amounts of soluble solids in liquid. The TSS affects the taste of a given product and is dominated by the total sugar content and a small portion of soluble proteins, amino acids, and other organic materials. Therefore, the level of sweetness of a product is proportional to its TSS content as indicated by Kusumiyati *et al.* (2020), which could

be affected by the cultivar, growing environment, and agronomic practices. The reduced TSS of bulbs produced from densely populated onion plants is apparently due to the strong competition of plants for growth factors that lead to the production of low-soluble solids and thus lowers TSS in the bulbs.

Firmness of the bulb (Newton)

The firmness of the bulb was influenced ($p < 0.01$) by the main effects, as well as the two-way interaction (Appendix Table 5.1).

Bulbs of the Russet cultivar had the highest firmness, which is at par with that of the Jamber cultivar, while the bulbs of the Bombay Red cultivar had the lowest firmness. Firmer bulbs were also obtained from plants grown at the lowest plant density while bulbs from the highest and medium plant densities were less firm (Table 5.7). This could be attributed to the fact that fewer planting density allows individual onion plants to get more water and nutrients from the soil than they would in congested areas. Firmer bulbs may resulted from higher cellulose deposition and thicker cell wall growth, which are facilitated by better resource intake (Wubetie et al., 2022). These findings agree with those of Lancaster et al. (2001), and Larsen *et al.* (2009), who reported significant variation among onion cultivars concerning bulb firmness.

Table 5.7. Onion quality parameters as influenced by the interaction effect of cultivar and plant density for onion across

Cultivars	Density	TSS (%)	Firmness (Newton)
Russet	Low (222,222)	9.3cde	9.2a
	Medium (333,333)	8.3e	8.6cd
	High (666,666)	8.2e	8.72abc
Red Coach	Low (222,222)	8.3e	8.8ab
	Medium (333,333)	8.2e	8.6abc
	High (666,666)	8.2e	8.46d
Jambar	Low (222,222)	10.6bc	9.0ab
	Medium (333,333)	9.5cde	8.6abc
	High (666,666)	9.0de	8.0cde
Bombay Red	Low (222,222)	12.3a	8.5cd
	Medium (333,333)	12.1ab	7.7de
	High (666,666)	9.9cde	7.4e
Significance level		***	***

THSD _{0.05}	1.52	0.73
CV (%)	5.34	9.28

Where; *** = very highly significant at $p < 0.001$; means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; THSD_{0.05} = Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation

5.4. Conclusions and Recommendations

In conclusion, this comprehensive study demonstrated the significant influence of plant density and variety on the growth and yield parameters of onion in three diverse locations. The hybrid (Russet and Jambar) cultivars exhibited early maturation, producing firmer bulbs with superior length, diameter, and weight, resulting in the highest marketable bulb yield compared to open-pollinated cultivar (Bombay Red). Increasing the population of the plant improved key attributes of the onion bulb, such as diameter, weight, total yield, and marketable yield. In particular, the use of hybrid onion cultivars such as Russet (28.54 t ha⁻¹) and Jambar (26.61 t ha⁻¹) has emerged as a promising strategy for improving onion productivity in the study area and agroecologically similar regions.

Furthermore, the study recommends the use of a higher plant density (666,666 plants ha⁻¹) with the spacing of 5 cm between plants, 10 cm between rows and 40 cm between double rows to optimize onion productivity (28.42 t ha⁻¹).

This is the first study of its kind, it underscores the need for further exploration, particularly to evaluate various hybrid onion cultivars at elevated plant density levels in multilocation. These insights offer valuable guidance for onion growers, contributing to sustainable and improved production and productivity of onion in Ethiopia, where temperatures are different than the prescribed optimal conditions for the cultivation of onions.

Chapter 6: EFFECTS OF HYBRID VARIETIES, NITROGEN FERTILIZER, AND PACKAGING ON POST-HARVEST QUALITY OF ONION IN NORTHWEST ETHIOPIA

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Abstract

Production seasonality and perishable nature of the crop cause fluctuation in the market supply of onions and the incomes of farmers. On the other hand, the storage potential, quality and shelf life of onions depends on the agronomic practices including fertilizer application, choice of cultivars and packaging materials. The study was therefore initiated with the aim of evaluating onion storage materials (sack, shelf and floor) on postharvest quality of onion varieties that were grown in different environments (Koga, Woramit and Woreta) with the application of different levels of nitrogen fertilizer (0, 41, 82, and 123 kg ha⁻¹). The combination of variety, nitrogen fertilizer and storage material were arranged in a factorial arrangement in the randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications. The results indicated that the quality attributes of onion after harvest, particularly the shelf life of onion, were greatly influenced by onion varieties, packaging materials and nitrogen fertilization across the three locations. The study showed that hybrid onion bulbs with proper handling can be stored for one month without significant postharvest losses, regardless of packaging materials. Bulbs of Jambar and Russet varieties that were stored on shelves and grown with 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen fertilizer sprouted relatively late, recorded the lowest decay percentage and weight loss, better firm and the highest percentage of marketable bulb after four months storage period. Bombay Red variety recorded the highest storage loss; highest percentage of sprouting, decay, weight loss, and the lowest percentage of marketable bulbs after four months storage. Storing hybrid varieties of Jambar and Russet on well-ventilated shelves prolonged the shelf-life onion bulbs by reducing postharvest losses. Varietal selection, proper storage practices, and nutrient management are vital in maintaining quality, extending shelf life, mitigating postharvest losses and ensuring sustainable onion supply.

Keywords; Onion, Post-harvest, Shelf life, Storage period, Packaging material

6.1. Introduction

Increasing food availability is achieved not only by increasing crop productivity, but also by reducing post-harvest losses (Kader, 2005). Unfortunately, a substantial amount of food and products are not reached to consumers due to postharvest losses that occurred in the food value chain from harvesting to consumption. About 40 to 50% of the food and products produced worldwide is lost in this manner (Kitinoja and Julie, 2015; Reardon and Bart, 2016).

Postharvest losses can result in multiple adverse outcomes, including seed loss, financial loss, food loss, and damage to reputation, all of which negatively impact marketing efforts (Gross et al., 2000; FAO and World Bank, 2010). Onions, being highly susceptible to sprouting, rotting, and weight loss, face significant challenges. These challenges are often exacerbated by various factors such as agronomic practices (e.g., plant nutrition and cultivar selection) and postharvest handling methods, including storage types and techniques (Adamicki, 2005; Ullah et al., 2008; Downes et al., 2010; Ebad et al., 2010).

Onions are highly perishable and require proper storage conditions to maintain quality and reduce postharvest losses. Proper storage has proven effective in minimizing sprouting, rotting, and weight loss, thereby prolonging shelf life. However, despite recognizing the importance of such storage solutions, Ethiopian onion producers face significant losses, with estimates suggesting that between 13% and 36% of onions are lost annually (Daniels and Fors, 2015). In the northwest region alone, nearly 30% of the onion harvest is wasted due to improper handling and inadequate postharvest management practices (Yebirzaf Yeshiwas et al., 2023).

The storage life of onions is influenced by factors such as variety, agronomic practices, and packaging materials (Hurst et al., 2006). In Ethiopia, one of the major challenges is the lack of accessible and affordable cold storage infrastructure. As a result, many farmers depend on traditional storage methods, such as using burlap sacks or storing onions directly on the floor at room temperature (Yebirzaf Yeshiwas et al., 2023). This lack of modern storage solutions forces farmers to sell surplus produce at low prices during peak production periods, leading to significant financial losses and discouragement. On the other hand, during the rainy season,

when onion production is limited, market scarcity causes prices to spike, making onions unaffordable for many consumers. This cyclical issue highlights the urgent need for improved storage infrastructure to stabilize the market and support both farmers and consumers.

The storage life of onions is significantly influenced by the variety of onion. Studies have shown significant variations among onion cultivars regarding yield, components, and storage capacity (Hurst et al., 2006; Msuya et al., 2005; Omar et al., 2005). Hybrid varieties often outperform open-pollinated varieties in terms of both yield and storage capacity (Li et al., 2020; Patel et al., 2020; Gupta et al., 2021).

Agronomic practices also play a critical role. For instance, the application of nitrogen fertilizers enhances growth, yield, and bulb quality. However, excessive nitrogen can reduce storage life by increasing decay rates and premature sprouting (Sebsebe Woldetsadik and Seyoum Workneh, 2010; Wang et al., 2019; Gupta, 2021). Furthermore, the choice of packaging materials affects storage duration. Packaging that minimizes physical damage and moisture loss while preventing sprouting and decay is crucial for extending onion shelf life (Fatideh and Asil, 2012; Khan et al., 2021).

The lack of proper storage infrastructure is also one of the major challenges faced by farmers in Ethiopia. Many farmers rely on traditional storage methods, such as using burlap sacks or storing onions directly on the floor at room temperature. However, the effects of these practices on onion bulbs are not well studied (Endalew et al., 2015; Yebirzaf Yesheiwias et al., 2023). In response to these challenges, this study aims to identify the effects of different onion varieties, nitrogen fertilizer rates, and packaging materials on the postharvest quality of onions.

6.2. Materials and Methods

6.2.1. Description of the study area

The field experiment was conducted during 2022/2023 irrigation season as described under section 2.1. The storage experiment was carried out in the storage room of the Bahir Dar University College of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences (Zenzelima Campus) under

ambient conditions. Zenzelma is geographically located between 11°35'N and 11°40'N latitude 37°24'E and 3°29' E longitude with the altitude of 1917 above mean sea level (Shiferaw *et al.*, 2022). The average maximum and minimum temperatures during storage period were 35.3 °C and 16.3 °C, respectively. The minimum and maximum relative humidity of the storage atmosphere was observed as 40% and 92.6%, respectively (Figure 6 1a and 6.1b).

Figure 6.1.a. Temperature variations in storage room of onion in 2023; b. Average relative humidity and temperature variations in storage room of onion in 2023

6.2.2. Sources of bulbs for the experiment

Sample onion bulbs of Russet, Red Coach and Jambar hybrid varieties and Bombay Red an open pollinated variety, which were grown at different rates of nitrogen fertilizer in Koga, Woramit, and Woreta locations were used in the present study. Bulbs were harvested at 70% physiological maturity (70% of bulb neck fall) and cured for five days before the onset of the experiment.

6.2.3 Experimental design and treatments

The treatments consisted of bulbs of four onion varieties (Russet, Red Coach, Jambar, and Bombay Red) produced with the application of four nitrogen fertilizer rates (0 kg ha⁻¹, 41 kg ha⁻¹, 82 kg ha⁻¹ and 123 kg ha⁻¹) and three types of storage materials (burlap sack, wooden shelves, and floor). The treatments were arranged in a factorial arrangement in the randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications.

6.2.4. Experimental procedures

Sample onion bulbs at proper maturity stage were collected from the Koga, Woramit and Woreta areas produced during the 2022 irrigation season. Onion bulbs were harvested at the physiological maturity stage. The bulbs were sorted according to uniformity and as marketable bulb size in the absence of defects. The bulbs were cured for five days in partial shade conditions. The selected bulbs were stored in naturally ventilated houses constructed from corrugated iron sheet roofing. Five-kilogram sample onion bulbs were used for storage. The air temperature and relative humidity of the storage rooms were continuously recorded throughout the storage period (from the beginning of May to the end of August) using a digital psychrometer.

6.2.5. Data collection

Data collection methods were described under sections 2.5.

6.2.6. Data analysis

The combined analysis of variance across locations was calculated for the parameters that showed homogeneous variance and subjected to the analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the PROC MIXED procedure of SAS version 9.0 computer software (SAS Institute Inc., 2008). The storage condition, nitrogen fertilizer rate, and varieties were considered fixed effects, while location was considered a random effect. When the analysis showed significant ($p < 0.05$), the mean separation was carried out using DMRT (Duncan's multiple range test) at a significance level of 5% (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

6.3. Results and Discussion

6.3.1. Days to first sprouting

The combined analysis of variance across the locations indicated that days to first sprouting of onion bulbs in storage were significantly ($p < 0.01$) influenced by the main effects of variety, packaging material, and nitrogen fertilizer rate. However, all possible interaction effects did not influence ($p > 0.05$) the first days of bulb sprouting (Appendix Table 6.1).

The variety Jambar sprouted relatively late at 75.94 days of storage, while the local check variety; Bombay Red; sprouted early at 37.93 days of storage (Table 6.1). Similarly, bulbs stored on the shelf sprouted late at 62.97 days of storage, followed by bulbs stored in burlap sacks (59.98 days) and the floor (60.99 days). The nitrogen fertilizer rate also had impacted the onion bulb sprouting. Bulbs grown with the application of 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen exhibited delayed sprouting compared to those bulbs grown with the supplement of 123 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen (60.25 days) as indicated in Table 6.1.

The present findings indicated that onion bulb sprouting did not occur until 37 days of storage across location. The first visible sprout initiation was observed at the 37th day of storage on Bombay Red bulbs while the bulbs of hybrid variety Jambar did not show sprouting until the 75th days of storage (Table 6.1). This indicates the presence of physiological rest period (dormancy) of onion bulbs in this storage environment. Furthermore, the results also indicate that open pollinated variety can be stored for 4 weeks while hybrid varieties can be stored for

about 6-10 weeks regardless of the storage materials used, fertilizer rates applied and production site by harvesting at proper maturity stage, curing, and regular inspection during storage.

The difference of varieties towards sprout initiation can be attributed to their variations in the genetic makeup that leads to differences in the time required to break dormancy. Sprouting of stored onion bulbs is a result of physiological changes and is highly affected by storage conditions. Onion sprouting is detrimental as it results in the transfer of dry matter and water from edible fleshy scales to sprouts, leading to shrinking and loss of appearance, ultimately affecting marketability (Getenesh Nega *et al.*, 2015). The delayed sprout initiation on bulbs stored on shelves could be associated with proper ventilation that dissipates hot air, which in turn reduces the respiration rate and metabolic processes. On the other hand, microenvironment in burlap sacks is poorly ventilated that increases transpiration and metabolic process, which may enhance earlier sprout initiation of bulbs as indicated in the present study. In this regard, Hayma (2003) reported that higher temperatures promote sprouting and increase respiration leading to heat production. The present study aligns with the findings of Bongiwari and Shirsat (2000) who reported variation of onion bulb sprouting stored in different packaging materials. According to Gupta and Patel (2020), storing bulbs on shelves provides more temperature control compared to storing them directly on the floor, where temperature fluctuations are more frequent.

Excessive nitrogen availability potentially accelerates the sprouting processes and negatively affects the bulb quality as indicated in the present, which is in line with the reports of Etana *et al.* (2019).

6.3.2. Bulb sprouting percentage

The combined analysis of variance (ANOVA) over locations revealed that the sprouting percentage of onion bulbs was highly significantly ($p < 0.001$) influenced by the main effects of variety and packaging material. However, nitrogen levels and any interactions between them significantly influenced ($p > 0.05$) this parameter of onion bulbs (Appendix Table 6.1).

The highest percentage of sprouting (68.7%) was observed on bulbs of Bombay Red variety followed by Red Coach variety (60.80%). On the contrary, Bulbs of Russet (43.93%) and Jambar varieties (56.17%) recorded the lowest percentage of sprouting after five months of storage period. Bulbs packed in burlap sacks recorded the lowest sprouting percentage (54.50%) while bulbs stored on shelves (58.87%) and floors (58.83%) showed the highest sprouting percentage across the locations (Table 6.1).

Contrary to the previous findings, the nitrogen fertilizer rate did not significantly affect the sprouting percentage of bulbs. Benti (2017) reported a significant influence of nitrogen fertilizer on sprouting, while Smith *et al.* (2020) and Patel and Gupta (2019) indicate the limited impact of nitrogen fertilizer on the actual sprouting percentage of onion bulbs during storage. The observed varietal differences in onion sprouting highlight their genetic difference, which is in line with findings of other scholars (Adamicki, 2005, Benti, 2017 Gateri, 2019).

Sprouting and rotting are considered as main causes of storage losses that decreased the quality of stored onion bulbs (Adamicki, 2005). Dormancy plays a crucial role in onion bulb storage, longevity, and sprout suppression (D'Angelo and Goldman, 2019). The length of dormancy depends on genotype and storage conditions (Chávez-Mendoza *et al.*, 2016). Storing onion in fully ventilated storage structures reduces sprouting percentage of onion bulbs (Selam Getachew, 2020). Changes of growth regulators during postharvest storage can also influence the onion bulb sprouting, with cytokinins inducing sprouting by reducing the concentrations of abscisic acid and stress factors (Qadir *et al.*, 2007, Chope *et al.*, 2012).

6.3.3. Decay percentage

The combined analysis of variance indicated that decay percentage of onion bulbs was influenced ($p < 0.01$) by the main effects of variety, storage material, nitrogen as well as the two-way interaction of packaging material-variety. However, the other two-way and three-way interactions did not influence ($p > 0.05$) decay percentage (Appendix Table 6.1).

The highest decay percentage (9.49%) was observed on the variety Bombay Red, while the hybrid variety Russet (6.94%) and Jambar (7.54%) recorded relatively the lowest decay

percentages after a five-month storage period. Onion bulbs stored on shelves had the lowest decay percentage (4.78%), whereas bulbs stored in the sack had the highest decay percentage (10.99%), followed by those stored on the floor (8.6%) (Table 6.1). Onion bulbs supplied with nitrogen at the rate of 123 kg ha⁻¹ (8.66%) and 0 kg ha⁻¹ (8.18%) exhibited the highest decay percentage, while bulbs produced with nitrogen supplement of 82 kg ha⁻¹ (7.41%) recorded the lowest decay percentage. Regarding the interaction effect over locations, Bulbs of Bombay Red variety stored in burlap sack packaging material exhibited the highest decay percentage (13.43%), while bulbs of Jambar (3.3%) and Russet (4.4%) stored on the shelf showed the lowest decay percentage (Figure 6.2).

Decay of bulbs is primarily caused by microbial infections, which include bacteria, fungi, and molds. The extent of decay depends on the variety, mechanical damages, storage environment and freedom from diseases and insect pests. In the present study, hybrid varieties generally showed lower decay percentages compared to the open-pollinated variety, which could be associated with the genetic makeup. Hybrid onion varieties stored better due to their thicker skins, better storage physiology and enhanced resistance mechanisms against decay-causing organisms (Singh *et al.* 2015; Mota *et al.*, 2019; Jones *et al.*; 2021; Randhawa *et al.*, 2022). Varietal differences in decay percentage during storage are also observed by Diaz-Perez *et al.* (2003) and Benti (2017).

Excessive application of nitrogen fertilizer experiences overstimulated vegetative growth, which can result in tissue softening and making bulbs more susceptible to mechanical damages and decay during storage (Etana *et al.* 2019; Smith *et al.*, 2020), which is in agreement with the results of the present study. On the contrary, bulbs that are grown without the use of nitrogen fertilizers may have inadequate levels of vital nutrients needed for optimal development and defence against decaying pathogens that may increase vulnerability to spoilage during storage (Patel and Gupta, 2019).

Storage materials also influence the postharvest life of onion bulbs including sprouting and decays percentage storage life as indicated in the present study. Packaging materials with the provision of ventilation is quite necessary to reduce postharvest losses. In this regard, Selam

Getachew (2020) reported that onion producers and traders in the North West Amhara region stored their bulbs in burlap sacks without proper aeration, which can potentially increase bulb rotting. Proper drying and reduction of moisture content reduces the occurrence of rotting on stored onion bulbs (Mota *et al.*, 2019; Patel and Gupta, 2020; Smith *et al.*, 2021; Rahman *et al.*, 2022). Benti (2017) reported that the percent of rotten bulbs was not significantly influenced by nitrogen at 60 days after storage. Furthermore, Debnath and Hemavathy (2016) found that higher rotting was recorded in netlon bags compared to hessian cloth bags under ambient storage conditions.

Table 6 1. Effects of variety, packaging material, and nitrogen fertilizer rate combined over growing locations on selected postharvest parameters of onion bulbs

Packaging material	Days to first sprouting	Bulb sprouting percentage	Decay percentage
Shelf	62.97a	58.87a	4.78c
Burlap sack	59.98b	54.50b	10.99a
Floor	60.99b	58.83a	8.6b
p-value	**	**	***
Variety			
Russet	71.39b	43.93d	6.94c
Red Coach	59.99 ^c	60.80b	8.62b
Jambar	75.94a	56.17c	7.54c
Bombay Red	37.93d	68.70a	9.49a
p-value	***	***	***
Nitrogen Rate (kg ha⁻¹)			
0	60.01 ^c	58.28	8.18a
41	61.21 ^b	57.35	7.91b
82	63.77a	56.82	7.41c
123	60.25c	57.15	8.66a
p-value	**	ns	*
CV (%)	13.65	26.01	27.34
SE	0.81	0.86	0.17

Where; *** = very highly significant at $p < 0.001$; ** = highly significant at $p < 0.01$; * = significant at $p < 0.05$; ns = non-significance; Means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; $LSD_{0.05}$ = Least significant difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation

Figure 6.2. Interaction effect of variety and packaging materials on the decay percentage of onion bulbs combined over the three locations

6.3.4. Percentage of weight loss

Weight loss of onion bulbs was influenced by the main effects of the packaging material, nitrogen rate and variety ($P < 0.001$). However, the two-way, and three-way interactions, did not significantly influence ($p > 0.05$) the percentage of weight loss of onion after five months of storage (Appendix Table 6.1).

Bulbs stored on shelves recorded the lowest percentage of weight loss throughout the storage period, while bulbs stored in sacks and on the floor recorded the highest weight loss. Similarly, applying 82 kg ha^{-1} of nitrogen resulted in the lowest percentage of weight loss, a result that was statistically similar to the application of 123 kg ha^{-1} nitrogen. Conversely, the highest weight loss was observed with applications of 0 and 41 kg ha^{-1} of nitrogen (Figure 6.3). The higher weight loss observed from low nitrogen level might be attributed to insufficient nitrogen which may due to the development of weaker cell wall and lower carbohydrate reserves, making bulbs more susceptible to dehydration during storage. Low nitrogen also limits the formation of amino acids and proteins, essential for maintaining cell turgor and structural integrity. On the other hand, adequate nitrogen, enhances the synthesis of proteins and structural compounds that

strengthen cell walls, improving the bulb's resistance to physical damage and weight loss (Brewster, 2008).

Weight loss is one of the postharvest losses occurred in vegetable crops including onion. It is resulting from moisture loss and is generally known to occur due to dehydration, transpiration, respiration, rotting, sprouting, etc. Weight loss is generally increased with the prevailing temperature and low humidity in the environment. During storage period, the occurrence of sprouting and decay apparently occurs through an increase in the rate of respiration (Shippers, 1968). Benti (2017) found that throughout the storage period there was an increase in the percent weight loss under ambient storage conditions. Furthermore, Chala *et al.* (2019) reported that a high percentage of weight loss is observed when tubers are stored for more than 20 days, while Ctripathi (2008) observed 40 to 50% weight loss when bulbs were stored for more than 20 days.

Regarding varieties, in the current study, the highest percentage of weight loss was recorded from the Bombay Red variety, while the lowest percentage of weight loss was recorded for the Jambar and Russet varieties after five months of storage. Variation in percentage weight loss was significantly influenced by variety throughout the storage period. As indicated in Figure 6.3, hybrid varieties exhibited relatively low water loss percentage compared to the open pollinated variety (Bombay Red), which could be due to their thicker skin that may help to reduce the loss of water from the bulb surface and due to their genetic variation. These findings align with the previous findings of Hygrotech (2010), who reported that onion varieties exhibit different storage potential due to their genetic composition. According to Gebremedhn Gebretsadkan *et al.* (2018), Bombay Red variety recorded a weight loss of 97% in five months of storage duration.

Figure 6.3. Effects of packaging material and variety on weight loss percentage of onion after five months storage duration combined over the three locations

6.3.5. Percentage of marketable bulbs

The combined analysis of variance indicated that the main effect variety and the packaging material had a highly significant effect ($P < 0.001$) on marketable bulbs after four months storage duration. Similarly, the interaction between storage material and variety significantly ($P < 0.01$) influenced the percentage marketable of onion bulb throughout storage duration. However, the two-way interaction between nitrogen and variety, and the three-way interactions did not influence ($p > 0.05$) the percentage of marketable bulbs of onion at the specified storage periods (Appendix Table 6.1).

Russet variety maintained the highest percentage of marketable bulbs (56.73%), followed by Jambar (44%) and Red Coach (44.09%). On the other hand, Bombay Red variety recorded the lowest percentage of marketable bulb (32.52%) after 16 weeks of storage duration. The highest proportion of marketable bulbs from hybrid varieties like Jambar and Russet compared to open pollinated Bombay Red variety which is obviously attributed to their better storability potential

controlled by the genetic makeup of the crop. The level of nitrogen fertilizer did not have a significant influence on the marketable bulbs of onion (Table 6.2).

Onion sprouting began after five weeks of storage period and persisted throughout the four-month period. After four months of storage, the highest percentage of marketable onion bulbs (47.87%) was maintained from bulbs stored on shelves followed by those stored in burlap bag (44.34%) and on the floor (40.79%). Tripathi and Lawande (2016) similarly highlighted that a storage duration of three months resulted in 76% marketable bulbs, highlighting the efficacy of fully ventilated structures as ideal packaging materials for onions.

In the interaction effect, Russet and Jambar varieties stored on shelves had highest proportion of marketable bulb consistently during the four months of storage period. On the other hand, the lowest percentage of marketable bulbs was observed in the Bombay Red variety stored on the floor as indicated in Table 6.3.

The marketable percentage of bulbs generally decreased with the increased storage period and reached its lowest level at the end of the storage due to bulb aging and sustainability to sprouting and rotting (Hatem *et al.*, 2014). This scenario is in line with the findings of the present study (Table 6.3). Extended availability of a greater quantity of healthy and acceptable bulbs at the end of the storage period is of paramount important to reduce postharvest loss and meet the consumer demand as well as to enhance the income of farmers out of it. According to Smith *et al.* (2020) hybrid varieties are specifically bred to exhibit better storage traits, including thicker skins, better disease resistance, and enhanced physiological characteristics that contribute to better bulb quality during storage. Singh *et al.* (2015) also observed low storage loss of marketable bulbs that were stored in well-ventilated storage materials compared to less ventilated bags, which is in line with the results of the present study.

Table 6.2. Effects of variety, packaging material, and nitrogen fertilizer after four months storage duration on marketability of onion bulbs: across locations

Packaging material	Marketable bulbs (%)
Shelf	47.87a
Burlap sack	44.34b

Floor	40.79c
p-value	**
Variety	
Russet	56.73a
Red Coach	44.09b
Jambar	44.00b
Bombay Red	32.52c
p-value	**
Nitrogen rate (kg ha⁻¹)	
0	44.37
41	44.81
82	43.83
123	44.32
p-value	ns
CV (%)	12.5
SE	

Where; ** = highly significant at $p < 0.01$; * = significant at $p < 0.05$; ns = non-significance means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; $LSD_{0.05}$ = Least significant difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation

Table 6 3. Proportion of marketable onion bulbs in different weeks of storage as influenced by the interaction effect of variety and storage materials combined over the three locations

Variety	Packaging material	Marketability (%)		
		8 weeks	12 weeks	16 weeks
Russet	Shelf	90.74ab	83.95a	60.44a
	Burlap sack	90.27ab	77.31bc	54.08ab
	Floor	89.04b	73.14cd	38.73def
Red Coach	Shelf	75.30cd	47.68g	43.55cd
	Burlap sack	73.30cde	55.70ef	47.99bc
	Floor	71.75de	46.14g	40.74de
Jambar	Shelf	94.75a	84.25a	55.0a
	Burlap sack	92.59ab	80.24ab	54.73a
	Floor	89.35b	69.72d	39.19def
Bombay Red	Shelf	77.77c	60.64e	35.648ef
	Burlap sack	70.06e	50.30fg	33.42fg
	Floor	70.83de	50.61fg	28.48g
Significance level		**	**	**
CV (%)		16.6	19	21
SE		0.78	1.02	0.83

Where; *** = very highly significant at $p < 0.001$; ** = highly significant at $p < 0.01$; * = significant at $p < 0.05$; ns = non-significance means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; $LSD_{0.05}$ = Least significant difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation

3.6.6. Total soluble solid (%)

The combined analysis of variance indicated that total soluble solids (TSS) were highly significantly ($p < 0.001$) influenced by the main effects variety, packaging material, and nitrogen fertilizer rate, along with their two-way and three-way interactions, after four months storage periods. However, three-way interactions did not have a significant influence ($p > 0.05$) on TSS throughout the storage period (Appendix Table 6.1).

Onion bulbs stored on shelves maintained significantly better their TSS levels throughout the storage period compared to other storage conditions, while onion bulbs stored on the floor exhibited the lowest TSS. Bombay Red variety recording the highest TSS and Russet variety showing the lowest, while the lowest TSS was recorded from Russet variety. Furthermore, onion TSS levels were significantly influenced by nitrogen fertilizer rates, with the highest TSS recorded from the application of 123 kg ha^{-1} , followed by 82 kg ha^{-1} . On the other hand, the lowest TSS was recorded from the application of the nil nitrogen rate (Figure 6.4). The floor storage condition resulted in the lowest TSS for onion bulbs throughout the storage period. The onion bulbs stored in these storages were subjected to the highest percentage of weight loss during storage periods, as indicated in Figure 6.4. The lowest TSS in the bulb stored on the floor can be attributed to factors such as ventilation, temperature, and humidity, which affect bulb respiration and biochemical changes that lead to TSS variation. The present finding aligns with the previous findings conducted by Berno *et al.* (2014).

The interaction effect between variety, nitrogen rate, and packaging material on Total Soluble Solids shows significant findings. The highest TSS values were recorded in the Bombay Red variety, mainly when stored on shelves and applied with higher nitrogen rates (82 and 123 kg ha^{-1}). Jambar variety also showed high TSS, specifically with shelf storage and higher nitrogen rates, while Russet and Red Coach exhibited moderate TSS improvements under similar conditions (Table 6.4).

Studies by Singh and Dhankar (1989) showed that TSS of onion varieties stored in different storage materials slightly increased up to four weeks of storage period and then consistently

decreased throughout the storage period. According to Benklebia *et al.* (2005), the sugar metabolism is closely linked to the dormancy and sprouting rate of onion and its quantitative variations are the most important biochemical change during long periods of conservation. On the other hand, Chope *et al.* (2012) suggested a different mechanism, namely, respiration and remobilization of carbohydrates to provide energy for the initiation of sprouts. This could explain the sudden reduction in TSS observed in onions after six months of conservation since they presented internal sprouts in one hundred percent of bulbs tested at the end of storage.

The total soluble solid content during storage period varies with genotypic differences (Benti, 2017) and the packaging materials (Berno *et al.*, 2014) as observed in the present study. Onion varieties may have genetically different levels of TSS content (Patel *et al.*, 2020) as observed in the present study (Figure 6.4a). Packaging also have different provision of ventilations, which influence the temperature and humidity in the package that affects bulb respiration and biochemical processes leading to TSS variation.

Onion varieties (Bombay Red) with the highest TSS also exhibited higher percentage of sprouting and decay and higher percentage of weight loss in the present study (Figure 6.3). According to Lee and Kim (2019), onion varieties with higher level of sugar content (TSS) might result in a higher weight loss during storage due to increased sugar respiration rate, which is in agreement with the findings of the present study. On the other hand, Patel *et al.* (2020) reported that in some varieties, higher TSS may correlate with better storage characteristics, while others might have lower TSS but possess traits that contribute to improved storability. The results of the present study contradict the findings other scholars who associated higher TSS content with better preservation of bulb quality (Yemane, 2013; Devendrappa, 2015; Chávez-Mendoza *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 6.4. Effects of variety, packaging material, and nitrogen fertilizer on the TSS content of stored onion bulbs for four months: across locations

Table 6 4. Interaction effect of variety, packaging material, and nitrogen fertilizer on the TSS content of stored onion bulbs across locations

Variety	Packaging material	TSS N kg ha ⁻¹			
		0	41	82	123
Russet	Shelf	5.92nopqrst	6.42lmnopqrs	6.81ijklmno	6.60jklmnopq
	Floor	5.1t	6.28lmnopqrs	6.26lmnopqrs	6.036mnopqrs
	Sack	5.62pqrst	6.36lmnopqrs	6.6367 jklmnop	6.27lmnopqrs
Jambar	Shelf	6.76ijklmno	7.69defgh	8.03defg	7.18fghijk
	Floor	5.82opqrst	7.04hijklm	6.58jklmnopq	6.62jklmnop
	Sack	6.23mnopqrs	6.4lmnopqrs	6.94hijklmn	6.60klmnopq
Red Coach	Shelf	6.96hijklmn	6.33klmnopqrs	6.96hijklmn	7.18fghijk
	Floor	5.53rst	5.43st	5.96mopqrst	6.20lmnopqrs
	Sack	5.56qrst	5.94nopqrst	5.85opqrst	6.56lmnopqr
Bombay Red	Shelf	8.61bcde	8.91bcd	10.30a	9.37ab
	Floor	7.53fghij	7.86defgh	9.09bc	7.56efghij
	Sack	8.10cdef	7.37fghijk	9.51ab	8.60bcde
Significance level		***			
CV (%)		1.49			

Where; *** = very highly significant at $p < 0.001$; ** = highly significant at $p < 0.01$; * = significant at $p < 0.05$; ns = non-significance means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; $LSD_{0.05}$ = Least significant difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation

Bulb firmness

The combined analysis of variance showed that the main effects variety, packaging material, and nitrogen fertilizer rate, as well as the interaction of two ways, and three-way were highly significantly ($p < 0.001$) influenced bulb firmness after 12 weeks storage period (Appendix Table 6.1)

The Russet and Jambar varieties showed the highest bulb firmness, while the lowest firmness was recorded for the Bombay Red variety throughout the storage period (Figure 6.5). The difference in firmness among onion varieties could be attributed to genotypic differences. The highest firmness of onion from hybrid varieties might be due to different cell wall structures where hybrid onion varieties have naturally firmer cell walls than open-pollinated varieties. Such thicker cell walls make hybrid varieties more resistant to bruising, damages and spoilage compared to open-pollinated varieties (Coolong *et al.*, 2008; Yuan *et al.*, 2021). In line to this, Russet and Jambar varieties in the present study showed the lowest spoilage during the storage period as indicated in (Table 6.1).

Bulb firmness was also influenced by nitrogen fertilizer where bulbs produced by the application of 82 kg ha⁻¹ N recorded the highest firmness while those produced by the application of 123 kg ha⁻¹ were less firm throughout the storage period indicated in Fig. 6.5. The firmness of onion bulbs is an attribute that is directly related to the freshness and crispness index of the vegetable (González *et al.*, 2012). The decrease in bulb firmness at the highest nitrogen rate application could be attributed to the fact that nitrogen is an essential element of the amino acids that build the structure of onion cell walls. Therefore, when onions are fertilized with high nitrogen, the amount of amino acids in the cell walls will be increased that make the cell walls of onion bulbs weaker and more susceptible to softening. Similar results were reported by other scholars where high nitrogen fertilizer rates influence the internal tissue of an onion (Zhang *et al.*, 2017; Singh *et al.*, 2021).

Regarding packaging materials, onion bulbs stored on shelves maintained better firmness as indicated in Figure 6.5. The reason for the hardness of bulbs stored on shelves may be due to

the fact that shelf storage leads to surface drying of onions, resulting in rigidity and firmness of the bulbs outer skin.

In the interaction effect, bulbs of Russet and Jambar varieties that were stored on shelves maintained higher firmness, whereas the bulbs of Bombay Red variety stored in burlap bags showed the lowest firmness throughout the storage period (Table 6.4). Generally, bulb firmness decreased as the storage period increased, which could be associated with cell wall degradation during the process of ripening and senescence of horticultural products through biochemical reactions (Melo et al., 2012; Chávez-Mendoza et al., 2016).

Parameters like weight loss percentage, sprouting percentage, date of sprouting, decay percentage, and proportion of marketable bulb and bulb firmness serve as crucial indicators for shelf life of onion bulbs. According to the results indicated above the use of hybrid varieties (Russet and Jambar), storing bulbs on shelves and application of 82 kg ha⁻¹ N maintained the shelf-life of onion bulbs better compared to other treatments.

Figure 6.5. Effects of variety, packaging material and nitrogen fertilizer on bulb firmness of onion combined over three locations

Table 6.5. Interaction effect of variety and packaging materials on firmness (Newton) of onion bulb combined over the three locations

Variety	Packaging material	Firmness			
		Storage duration (weeks)			
		0 (initial)	4	8	12
Russet	Shelf	9.85a	8.74ab	8.13a	7.86a
	Floor	8.78de	9.12a	7.96abc	7.69abc
	Burlap sack	9.18dc	8.26cd	7.84abcd	7.57abcd
Jambar	Shelf	9.52ab	8.98ab	8.20a	7.93a
	Floor	9.3bc	8.83ab	8.11ab	7.84ab
	Burlap sack	9.12cd	8.63bc	8.10ab	7.83ab
Red Coach	Shelf	8.86de	8.04de	7.50de	7.23de
	Floor	8.54e	7.96de	7.48de	7.2de
	Burlap sack	9.06cd	7.85ef	7.35ef	7.08e
Bombay Red	Shelf	8.93cde	8.10de	7.63cde	7.30cde
	Floor	9.06cd	8.27cd	7.69bcde	7.42bcde
	Burlap sack	8.98cd	7.49f	6.98f	6.63f
Significance level = ***					
CV (%)		3.21	3.70	2.89	3.19

Where; *** = very highly significant at $p < 0.001$; means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; $LSD_{0.05}$ = Least significant difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation

6.4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Postharvest life of onion bulbs was significantly influenced by onion variety, packaging material, and nitrogen fertilization rate combined over the three locations. They affected the initiation of sprouting, the percentage of decay, the percentage of marketable bulbs, the weight loss, the total content of soluble solids, and the firmness of the bulb during storage. The bulbs of Jambar and Russet varieties and the application of nitrogen fertilizer at the rate of 82 kg ha^{-1} and storing onion bulbs on shelves recorded prolonged sprouting initiation, reduced decay percentage and weight loss, better firmness of bulbs as well as highest percentage of marketable bulbs during the four months storage period. The highest storage loss of onion bulbs (highest sprouting percentage, decay percentage, weight loss percentage, and low marketable bulbs) was observed from Bombay Red variety. The longer shelf life (lower sprouting percentage, decay percentage, weight loss percentage and higher percentage of marketable bulbs) was observed from Jambar and Russet varieties, which were stored on the shelves. Hybrid onion varieties (Russet and Jambar) had a longer shelf-life compared to open-pollinated variety (Bombay Red). Packaging materials also played a significant role in influencing the postharvest quality of onion

bulbs where storing bulbs on shelves better maintained the shelf life of compared to storing in burlap sacks or directly on the floor. Similarly, application of optimum rates of nitrogen fertilizer is necessary to maintain the quality of onion bulbs in storage. The use of hybrid varieties (Russet and Jamber), storing onion bulbs on well-ventilated shelves constructed from locally available materials and the use of optimum rate of nitrogen fertilizer are recommended to extend the shelf life and reduce the postharvest losses of onion bulbs.

Chapter 7: INFLUENCE OF PRE-HARVEST TREATMENTS ON POST HARVEST QUALITY AND SHELF LIFE OF ONION (*Allium cepa* L.) VARIETIES IN BAHIR DAR ZURIA DISTRICT, AMHARA REGION

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Abstract

Onion is the most important and widely cultivated bulb vegetable in Ethiopia. High postharvest loss during storage is one of the main challenges of onion production and productivity. The present study was therefore conducted with the aim of evaluating the effects of selected pre-harvest treatments on shelf life and postharvest quality of onion varieties stored in diffused light storage structure. Bulbs of three hybrid (Red Coach, Russet, Jambar) and one open-pollinated (Bombay Red) varieties were used, which were produced in Woramit Research Site of ARARI during the 2022/2023 irrigation season using uniform and standard agronomic practices. The pre-harvest treatments were toppling at 70% neck fall with (easy of pulling up) and without irrigation, toppling at 90% neck fall, and harvesting at 70% neck fall without toppling. The treatments were arranged with 4*4*3 factorial combination in RCBD with three replications. Based on the treatment setup, bulbs were stored in ventilated storage room in Zenzelema campus of Bahir Dar University for three months. Data on postharvest quality parameters were collected in monthly intervals and analysed using a SAS (version 9.0) software. The results revealed that variety, pre-harvest treatment and storage duration influenced most of the tested parameters of onion in the storage. Similarly, the interaction of variety and pre-harvest treatments significantly influenced decay percentage, sprouting percentage, bulb firmness, total soluble solid of onion bulb, weight loss percentage, and marketable bulbs percentage throughout the storage duration. The varieties Jambar and Russet and the practice of toppling at 90% maturity recorded the lowest sprouting and weight loss percentage of onion bulbs in the

storage and highest proportion of marketable bulbs and highest bulb firmness. On the other hand Bombay Red variety, topped at 70% maturity with irrigation recorded the highest sprouting, decay percentage, bulb weight loss and the lowest bulb firmness. It is concluded that the use of Jambar and Russet varieties with the practice of toppling at 90% maturity are therefore suggested to maintain the quality and reduce postharvest losses of onion bulbs in the storage. As the study is limited to single location and season, it is recommended to repeat the study in multiplications and seasons. Additionally, evaluating the impact of plant growth hormones to extend shelf life is recommended.

Key words: Onion, Hybrid varieties, Pre-harvest treatments, Onion varieties, Toppling, Storage duration, Shelf life, Postharvest quality

7.1. Introduction

Onion production plays a significant role in Northwest Ethiopia, contributing to the livelihoods of farmers and the regional economy. As one of the principal cash crops cultivated in the region, onions substantially enhance agricultural income, food security, and economic and health outcomes for both smallholder farmers and large-scale commercial enterprises (Habtamu Mossie, 2020).

Despite its economic and agricultural importance, onion production and productivity in Ethiopia, particularly in the study area, remain low. This is attributed to several factors, including poor-quality seeds, inappropriate cultural practices, and inadequate pre- and postharvest handling methods (Melkamu Alemayehu et al., 2015; Nikus Olani and Fikre Mulugeta, 2010). These limitations lead to high postharvest losses, which significantly affect farmers' incomes. The widespread use of open-pollinated onion varieties in the region, which are characterized by low yield potential and poor storability, exacerbates this problem. As noted by Rahman et al. (2007), postharvest losses and short shelf lives in open-pollinated onion varieties can reach up to 100%. Farmers are often forced to sell their produce immediately after harvest at low prices due to surplus production, further impacting their livelihoods (Yebirzaf Yeshiwas et al., 2023).

The postharvest life of onions is influenced by factors such as the choice of variety, agronomic practices like curing, toppling, and irrigation management. Farmers in the study area predominantly grow open-pollinated onion varieties, which are known for their limited storability. Hybrid onion varieties, on the other hand, are reported to have better postharvest qualities and longer shelf lives (Rahman et al., 2007).

Toppling, or the bending of onion plants, is a pre-harvest practice aimed at facilitating bulb-neck drying before harvest. Farmers in Ethiopia, including those in Bahir Dar Zuria district, typically practice toppling by bending onion plants manually or using tools such as wooden planks (Alemu Melaku, 2015). This process helps accelerate bulb curing, reducing the neck's moisture content and minimizing the risk of microbial infections during storage. However, improper or prolonged toppling can expose bulbs to adverse environmental conditions, such as sunburn or pest infestations, potentially compromising postharvest quality (Yebirzaf Yeshiwas et al., 2023). Research is needed to optimize the timing and method of toppling to balance its benefits and potential risks.

Irrigation practices during the harvest period are critical for maintaining onion quality. Excessive irrigation close to harvest increases the moisture content of bulbs, making them prone to decay and reducing their shelf-life (Patil et al., 2018; Yebirzaf Yeshiwas et al., 2023). Conversely, reduced irrigation frequency can promote bulb maturation and improve storability. In the study area, some farmers irrigate their onion fields just before harvest to ease manual pulling, while others adjust irrigation schedules to promote bulb quality. This variation highlights the need for guidance on optimal irrigation practices during the harvest period.

Farmers in the study area exhibit diverse practices regarding toppling and irrigation management. While some use manual or tool-assisted toppling to facilitate bulb curing, others irrigate their fields immediately before harvest to simplify the pulling process (Alemu Melaku, 2015). The timing of these practices varies widely, with some farmers toppling their plants for extended durations. The effects of these agronomic practices on the postharvest loss and shelf life of onion bulbs are however not well studied. Therefore, this study was initiated to;

- To identify the appropriate pre-harvest treatments, such as toppling timing and irrigation management, for maintaining the quality and shelf life of onion bulbs.
- To identify variety/ies with prolonged shelf life and better postharvest quality.

7.2. Materials and Methods

7.2.1. Description of the study area

The field experiment was conducted in 2022/2023 at the Woramit horticultural crops training and testing site in Bahir Dar Zuria district under irrigated conditions (Figure 2.1). The storage experiment was carried out in the storage room of under ambient conditions. Zenzelma is one of the kebeles in the Bahir Dar Zuria district, Amhara Region, Ethiopia. The experiment was done in storage house constructed at Zenzelma campus using locally available materials. This area is geographically located between 11°35'N and 11°40'N latitude and 37°24'E and 3°29'E longitude, with an altitude of 1,917 meters above sea level (Mekuanint Lewoyehu et al., 2022) (Figure7.1).

Source; Mekuanint Lewoyehu et al. (2022)

Figure 7.1. Maps of field experimental (Zenzelma campus).

7.2.1.1. Temperature and relative humidity in onion storage structure

Air temperatures and relative humidity of the storage rooms were recorded using a thermo hygrometer. The readings were taken daily interval. The recorded atmospheric conditions in the storage facility exhibit some variability throughout the storage period. The average atmospheric temperature and relative humidity in the ventilated storage structure during the storage period of onion are presented in Figure 7.2. The maximum and minimum temperatures recorded were 27.82 °C in May and 23.5 °C in August, respectively. The average temperature throughout the storage period ranged from 23.5 °C to 19.72 °C. Relative humidity levels also vary, with the minimum of 33.7% in May indicating relatively dry conditions, while the maximum of 86.65% in August suggests higher humidity levels

Figure 7.2. Average atmospheric temperature and relative humidity in storage structure during storage period in 2023

7.2.2. Sources of bulbs and their preparation for storage

Bulbs of four onion varieties, three hybrids (Red Coach, Russet and Jambar) and one open-pollinated (Bombay Red) grown during the 2023 irrigation season at Woramit Horticultural Crops Training and Testing Site were used, which were grown following the standard agronomic practices of onion crop (MoARD, 2019). Best performing plant density (40 cmx20 cmx5 cm between double rows, rows and plants respectively) and nitrogen fertilizer rate at 82 kg ha⁻¹, from the first-year study were used (Yebirzaf Yeshiwas et al., 2024 a, b). Before bulb-harvesting onion plants were treated with four pre-harvest treatments such as toppling at 70% plant fall followed by irrigation 3 days before harvesting, toppling at 70% neck fall without irrigation, toppling at 90% plant fall, Control (un-toppled, un-irrigated and harvested at 70% neck fall).

Irrigation water was applied at a four-day interval for the 1st four weeks and then extended to seven days' intervals until the physiological maturity stage. When 15 days were left for harvest application of irrigation water was stopped completely based on the treatments. Harvesting of onion bulbs were done depending on nature of the treatments. Except, the control plots harvested at plot 70% of plants in each plot show neck fall, while the remaining treatments were harvested after 7 days after the application of toppling.

In all cases, irrigation ceased a week prior to implementing the toppling procedure, except for the plots toppled at 70% neck fall and receiving irrigation three days before harvesting. Harvesting took place seven days after the implementation of the toppling treatment. Toppling was done manually by trampling the plants and harvesting was done by pulling the plants at onion neck. After harvest, bulbs were cured for five days under shade and ambient temperature (26.75 °C). After curing the onion tops were removed. A total of 40 uniform and marketable bulb samples from each experimental plot and treatment that weighed 5 kg were selected for storage. Onion bulbs were put on shelves constructed from dried wood. Onion bulbs were stored for three months where data were collected in a monthly interval depending on the parameters collected. In addition to 40 sample bulbs, ten tagged bulbs were designated for destructive data collection of firmness and TSS. Air temperatures and relative humidity of the storage rooms were recorded using a thermo hygrometer daily.

7.2.3 Treatments and experimental design

The storage experiment consisted of four onion varieties (Bombay Red, Red Coach, Russet and Jambar), four pre-harvest treatments: - (Toppling at 70% maturity/neck fall with irrigation, toppling at 70% neck fall without irrigation. toppling at 90% necks fall without irrigation and harvesting at 70% plant fall with no toppling and no irrigation (control) and three storage durations. The experimental treatments in the storage room were arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) in 4*4*3 factorial arrangements with three replications. Field experimental treatments were arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) in 4*4 factorial arrangements with three replications.

7.2.5. Data collection

Data collection methods were described under sections 2.5.

7.2.7. Data analysis

Data were subjected to the analysis of variance (ANOVA) by using ROC GLM procedure of the SAS version 9.0 computer software. The collected data was initially checked to meet all ANOVA assumptions (normality and homogeneity). When ANOVA showed significant differences ($P < 0.05$), the mean separation was carried out using the least significant difference (LSD) (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

7.3. Results and Discussion

Bulb sprouting percentage

The analysis of variance showed that the main effects of variety, pre-harvest treatment and storage duration as well as two-way interactions of variety x storage duration and storage duration x pre-harvest treatments influenced ($P < 0.001$) bulb sprouting percentage of onion. Conversely, the three-way interaction of variety x pre-harvest treatments x storage duration did not influence ($P > 0.05$) this parameter (Appendix Table 7.1). Bombay Red variety recorded the highest sprouting percentage (27.22%) followed by the variety Red Coach (21.94%), while the

lowest was recorded from the Russet (18.24%) and Jambar (19.16%) varieties during three months storage period (Figure 7.2). The difference between varieties for sprouting percentage is obviously associated with the genetic variations of the varieties on their dormancy characteristics. Variation in sprouting potential of onion varieties was also reported by other researchers (Adamicki, 2005; Gebisa Bededa, 2017; Gateri, 2019).

Bulbs that were toppled at 90% plant fall recorded the lowest sprouting percentage (14.53%) while those bulbs harvested at 70% plant fall (control), and toppled at 70% plant fall and irrigated three days before recorded the highest sprouting percentages of 25.46% and 27.03% respectively (Figure 7.2). Toppling is an important cultural practice of onion production, which facilitates the drying of outer skin of onion bulbs and thus reduces the risk of sprouting during storage. Toppling at 90% and 70% neck fall of onion plants reduced bulb sprouting by 42.93% and 23.29% compared to the 70% neck fall without toppling(control) (Figure 7.3).

As the storage duration increases, there is a linear increase in the sprouting percentage of onion varieties. Specifically, the highest sprouting percentage (43.05%) was observed from Bombay Red variety stored for 12 weeks, followed by Red Coach variety (35.55%) stored 12 weeks. The increase of sprouting as the storage period extend may caused by the rise of relative humidity and reduction of temperature in storage room during storage period (Table 7.1; Figure7.1).

Similar to the present findings, different researchers also reported that proper toppling reduces bulb sprouting during storage (Bizuyehu Desta *et al.*, 2021; Seid Hussen, 2022). On the other hand, toppling of onion plants at early developmental stages might lead to the production of bulbs that are not fully matured, which may potentially more susceptible to premature sprouting during storage (Khire *et al.*, 2019). Application of irrigation at late stage of onion increases bulb moisture content, which creates conducive environment for sprouting during storage as indicated in the present study and other researchers (Gorreapti *et al.*, 2017, Tasisa Temesgen, 2021). Generally, physiological weight loss, rotting, and sprouting, increase the postharvest losses and ultimately reduce the shelf life of onion (Bizuyehu Desta *et al.*, 2021).

Figure 7.2. Sprouting percentage as influenced by varieties under different pre-harvest treatments and storage durations

Means followed by similar letter/s in each parameter are statistically similar at 5% significant levels
 CV = coefficient of variation; LSD = least significant difference.

Table 7 1. Spouting percentage of onion as affected by variety – storage period interaction

Onion Varieties	4 week	8 week	12 week
Russet	7.77g	18.05e	28.88cd
Jambar	7.77g	18.88e	30.83c
Red Coach	9.16fg	21.11e	35.55b
Bombay Red	11.94f	26.66d	43.05a
P-values	**		
LSD _{0.05}	1.77		
CV (%)	16.11		

Where; ** = highly significant at $p < 0.001$ means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; LSD_{0.05}= least significant difference at 5% level; CV = coefficient of variation

Decay percentage

The analysis of variance showed that the main effects of variety, pre-harvest treatment and storage duration as well as their two-way interaction significantly ($P < 0.01$) influenced the bulb decay percentage of onion in the storage, whereas the three-way interactions did not influence this parameter (Appendix Table 7.1).

The highest decay percentage (23.51%) was observed from variety Bombay Red followed by variety Red Coach (18.05%), while the lowest was observed from variety Russet (15.27%) and Jamber (16.01%) during the three-month storage period (Figure 7.3). The present results indicate that hybrid onion varieties generally have relative higher storability compared to open-pollinated variety like Bombay Red. In this regard, Diaz-Perez et al. (2003) reported that hybrid onion varieties often have a longer shelf life than open-pollinated onions due to their thicker and dried skins, which help them to protect the bulbs from mechanical damages during handling and storage that intern reduce the incidence of disease infection. Differences in decay percentage observed in the present study are obviously associated with the genetic makeup of varieties. Differences among onion varieties towards spoilage/decay percentage were also observed by various researchers (Singh et al., 2015; Gebisa Bededa; 2017; Mota et al., 2019; Randhawa et al., 2022).

Among pre-harvest treatments, the lowest decay percentage (14.07%) was recorded from bulbs, which were toppled at 90% maturity followed (16.66%) by toppling at 70% maturity and irrigated. On the other hand, the highest decay percentage (22.12%) was recorded from bulbs harvested at 70% maturity(control). As the storage duration increases, a linear increase in the onion decay percentage was observed in bulbs stored for 12 weeks (Figure 7.3). This could be attributed to the increase of relative humidity and decrease in temperature in the storage room during storage period, which leads to condensation and can promote mold, fungi growth and leads to sprouting, decay and rotting of onion bulbs (Figure 7.2).

Toppling at the right time of maturity is an important agronomic practice that helps to facilitate the drying of the outer skin of bulbs leading to reduced decay, shrinking and sprouting in the storage as indicated in the present study. Toppling at 90 and 70% maturity reduced the bulb decay percentage by 53% and 39% respectively compared to un-toppled 70% maturity (Figure 7.4). Similarly, regulated irrigation, especially at the time of maturity is also critical to reduce the moisture content of the bulbs (Seid Hussien, 2022). Irrigation on toppled and harvested at 70% maturity in the present study increased the decay by 24% compared to non-irrigated and

but toppled at 70% maturity (Figure 7.4). Harvesting the bulbs too early may also lead to more decay in the storage due to un-matured bulbs.

The impact of storage duration on decay percentage varies depending on the onion variety. Russet and Jambar varieties show consistently lower decay percentages across all storage durations. This indicates these varieties are more resistant to decay and have better storage quality. On the other hand, Bombay Red variety exhibits significantly higher decay percentages at each storage duration, making it less suitable for long-term storage (Table 7.2). The increasing trend of decay with the storage length can be attributed as initially, onions may undergo physiological changes and metabolic activities that make them more susceptible to decay during the early stages of storage (Coolong., 2008).

Maintaining an appropriate moisture level in bulbs, particularly during storage, is essential to prevent favorable conditions for fungal growth and decay (Khire *et al.*, 2019; Tasisa Temesgen, 2021). The lowest decay percentage on bulbs toppled at 90% maturity in the present study is therefore obviously associated with drying of the outer skin of the bulbs that leads to the reduced disease infection in storage (Getenesh Nega *et al.*, 2015). Generally, toppling at different stages of maturity contribute to the reduction of onion bulb decay during post-harvest handling and storage. Proper handling techniques, including careful sorting and regular inspection, can also help minimize damage and prolong the shelf life of onions.

Figure 7.3. Decay percentage of onion bulbs as influenced by pre-harvest treatment, variety and storage duration

Table 7.2. Interaction effects of variety and storage duration on bulb decay percentage

Onion Varieties	4 weeks	8 weeks	12 weeks
Russet	7.77h	16.38f	21.66cd
Jambar	6.94h	17.22ef	23.88bc
Red Coach	8.61h	19.44de	26.11b
Bombay Red	12.22g	25.00b	33.33a
P-values	***		
LSD _{0.05}	2.91		
CV (%)	15.4		

Where; *** =very highly significant at $p < 0.001$ means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; LSD_{0.05} = least significant difference at 5% level; CV = coefficient of variation

Total Soluble Solid

Onion variety ($P < 0.0001$) and its interaction with pre-harvest treatment ($p < 0.0001$) influenced the total soluble solids (TSS) content of the stored onion bulbs. Similarly, the main effect of pre-harvest treatment and storage duration significantly influenced ($p < 0.001$) the TSS of the

stored onion bulbs. However, the interactions between pre-harvest treatment x storage duration, variety x storage duration and pre-harvest treatment x storage duration x variety did not show any influence the (TSS of stored onion bulbs) (Appendix Table 7.1). Bombay Red variety recorded the highest TSS value compared to the tested hybrid onion varieties throughout the storage period (Figure 7.4). Similarly, Bombay Red variety topped at 90% recorded the highest TSS value (Table 7.3). The differences among varieties for TSS may be due to the variations on the genetic makeup. In this regard, Chope *et al.* (2007), Mohammed and Gaafar (2005) reported variations in the TSS content of onion varieties, which was attributed to their genetic variations.

Extended maturation periods allow prolonged accumulation and conversion of starches into sugars, resulting in higher TSS levels at harvest (Brewster, 2008). which is observed in Bombay Red variety in the present study (Table 4.1; Table 5.1). In addition, low-yielder onion varieties possess genetic traits that favor the accumulation of sugars or other soluble solids in the bulb. These genetic factors may influence metabolic pathways involved in sugar synthesis, transport, and storage within the plant tissues (Fait *et al.*, 2008; Kader, 2008). Similar with the results of the present study, Mallor and Sales (2012) indicated that varieties with higher bulb yields have lower TSS content compared with varieties with the lowest yields due to the production of small-sized bulbs. Relatively higher TSS was reported in open-pollinated tomato varieties compared to the hybrid once, as hybrid varieties could be bred for specific traits such as better storability, yield potential, and uniformity rather than higher TSS (Giovannoni, 2004; Dwivedi *et al.*, 2013; Berno *et al.*, 2014). Lee and Kim (2014), on their studies concluded that onions with a higher sugar content might result in a higher weight loss during storage as a result of increased respiration rates. A higher level of TSS could result in more active metabolic processes, resulting in greater weight loss as sugars are used during respiration, which could lead to weight loss. Furthermore, Patel *et al.* (2020) indicated that different onion varieties display various levels of TSS. Furthermore, some varieties genetically have higher TSS, which might correlate with better storage characteristics, while others might have lower TSS but possess traits that contribute to improved storability.

In general, there was gradual decreasing trend of TSS till as the storage period extended (Figure 7.5). The decrease in TSS can be attributed to proportional rise in carbohydrate metabolism and respiration rate leads to. According to Chávez-Mendoza *et al.* (2016) the sugar metabolism is closely linked to the braking of dormancy and the start of sprouting of onion. Similarly, Chope *et al.* (2012) reported that changes during storage are related to respiration and re-mobilization of carbohydrates to provide energy for the development of sprouts, which is associated with the sudden reduction of TSS.

Figure 7.4. Total Soluble Solid (TSS) of onion bulbs as influenced by pre-harvest treatments, variety and storage period

Bulb firmness

The analysis of variance showed that the main effects of variety, storage duration and pre-harvest treatment had showed a highly significant ($p < 0.0001$) effect on bulb firmness. In addition, the interaction of variety x pre-harvest treatment showed highly significant ($p < 0.001$) effect on bulb firmness across storage durations. However, the other two way and three-way interactions did not influence ($p > 0.05$) the bulb firmness (Appendix Table 7.1). Bulb firmness was generally decreased as the storage period extends. Bulbs of (9.48 Newton) and Russet (9.32 Newton) varieties had relatively higher firmness during the storage period compared to other varieties. Similarly, bulbs from plants topped at 90% neck fall recorded the highest firmness

(8.90 Newton) compared to other pre-harvest treatments (Figure 7.5). Likewise, Jambar and Russet show the highest firmness under toppling at 90% neck fall, with Jambar reaching 9.74 Newton and Russet at 9.63 Newton, whereas Bombay Red tends to have lower firmness across pre-harvest treatments, especially under Toppling at 70% neck fall with irrigation (6.83 Newton)(Table 7.3).

Bulb firmness is an important feature that enhances the shelf life of a given onion varieties, which could be associated with the genetic makeup of the varieties (Smith *et al.*, 2020). In this regard, Romo and Maria (2021) reported that different onion varieties possess distinct genetic characteristics that can influence bulb firmness as indicated in the present study.

Khire *et al.* (2019) reported that different toppling stages also affect bulb maturity and dry matter accumulation. Bulbs harvested at 90% maturity stages might have higher dry matter content with more completed bulb maturity and reduced moisture content, which contributes for increased bulb firmness. On the other hand, irrigation after toppling increases the bulb moisture content that affects the bulb firmness as indicated in the present study (toppling at 70% and irrigated). Such excessive moisture could potentially lead to softer bulbs (Tasisa Temesgen, 2021). The decrease in firmness during storage is related to biochemical reactions of cell wall degradation (Chávez-Mendoza *et al.*, 2016) that reduces. The structural integrity and firmness resulting moisture losses through transpiration and respiration processes in onion bulbs. As the moisture levels decrease, the cells in the onion bulbs lose turgor pressure, leading to softening of the tissues leading in firmness losses. In addition, enzymatic activities such as cell wall degrading enzymes (e.g., pectinases) contribute to the breakdown of cell walls and other structural components, resulting in softer bulbs over time (Adams and Hicks, 2005; Kader, 2008).

Figure 7.5. Main effects variety and pre-harvest treatment on firmness of onion bulb

Table 7 3. Interaction effects of variety and pre-harvest treatment on the total soluble solid and firmness of onion bulbs over storage duration

Pre-harvest treatment	Variety	TSS	Firmness
Toppling at 70% neck fall with irrigation	Russet	7.03def	7.71cde
	Jambar	7.14def	7.20def
	Red Coach	7.62cde	6.96ef
	Bombay Red	11.05b	6.83f
Toppling at 70 % neck fall, without irrigation	Russet	8.19cd	8.60b
	Jambar	8.17cd	8.76b
	Red Coach	8.40c	7.35def
	Bombay Red	6.87ef	7.64cde
Toppling at 90 % neck fall	Russet	7.95cde	9.63a
	Jambar	8.18cd	9.74a
	Red Coach	8.66c	8.58b
	Bombay Red	12.98a	7.70cde
Control (un toppling, un irrigated)	Russet	6.36f	7.75cd
	Jambar	8.52c	8.34bc
	Red Coach	7.03def	7.56def
	Bombay Red	10.95b	7.05def
P-values		***	**
LSD _{0.05}		1.21	0.77
CV (%)		16.2	12.8

Where; *** = very highly significant at $p < 0.001$; ** = highly significant at $p < 0.01$; * = significant at $p < 0.05$; ns = non-significance means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; $LSD_{0.05}$ = Least significant difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation

Percent bulb weight loss

The analysis of variance showed that the main effects of variety, storage duration and pre-harvest treatment influenced ($p < 0.001$) the bulb weight loss. The two-way interaction between variety and storage duration also highly significantly ($p < 0.001$) influenced the bulb weight loss. However, the interaction of the variety x pre-harvest treatment, pre-harvest treatment x storage duration and variety x pre-harvest treatment x storage duration did not affect ($p > 0.05$) weight loss percentage of onion (Appendix Table 7.1). Weight loss generally increased as the storage period increased where bulbs of Jember and Russet varieties generally recorded the lowest weight loss compared to other varieties. Throughout the storage duration there was an increase in weight loss which would be associated with higher respiration rate. Similarly, bulbs from plants topped at 90% neck fall recorded the lowest weight loss compared to other pre-treatments (Figure 7.6).

In addition, Russet under toppling at 90% neck fall shows the lowest weight loss percentage (3.25%) which is statically similar with Jember (3.36%), while Bombay Red under control conditions shows the highest weight loss (8.21%). Overall, control (Un-topped, Un-irrigated) shows the highest negative impact on onion weight loss, especially for Bombay Red variety, whereas toppling at 90% neck fall consistently shows the lowest weight loss across all varieties (Table 7.4). This indicates it as a preferable treatment to reduce post-harvest issues.

Weight loss is among other the major postharvest losses in onion that lead to the economic losses of smallholder farmers. Choosing appropriate varieties that have high storability is therefore necessary to reduce postharvest losses in onion storage. In this regard, bulbs of hybrid varieties, Jember and Russet, recorded the lowest weight loss percentage throughout storage duration, which could be related to their genetic makeup. Hybrid varieties of onion are mainly bred to have thicker skins, which help protect onion bulbs from mechanical damages and associated water loss leading to reduced weight loss. Therefore, hybrid onion varieties often have longer shelf life than open-pollinated onions (Cramer *et al.*, 2018).

Generally, weight loss of onion bulbs increased over a three-month storage duration, which

differ with varieties and pre-harvest treatments (Figure 7.6). Toppling facilitates the drying of outer skin of bulbs that in turn reduces water and weight losses. The reduced weight loss on onions from plants toppled at 90% neck fall could be therefore associated with lower moisture content of the bulbs due to extended physiological maturity. Similar to the present findings, Khire *et al.* (2019) found that bulbs harvested at 90% maturity stages recorded reduced weight losses in storage. Researches also observed low incidence of skin rot, lower weight loss, and more marketable grades of bulbs, reduced post-harvest diseases and strong outer skins when onions were harvested at 80-100% leaf fall (Sebsebe Woldetsadik and Seyoum Workneh, 2010).

Irrigation practices before harvesting favours sprouting and weight loss of onion bulbs in the storage (Figure 7.2 and Figure 7.6). This is obviously attributed with rehydrating of the matured onion bulbs reading to increased moisture content that initiate regrowth and weight losses in the storage conditions. The results are in agreement with the findings of Patel *et al.*, (2020) who observed that onions irrigated close to harvesting have excess initial moisture leading to higher weight loss compared to un-irrigated bulbs during storage. A combination of appropriate toppling techniques that initiate bulb drying and controlled irrigation practices generally help achieving the optimal moisture content in bulbs, reducing weight loss and sprouting during storage Seid Hussen, (2022), which is in line with the results of the present study.

Figure 7.6. Main effects varieties and pre-harvest treatments on firmness of onion bulb at different storage duration

Table 7 4. Interaction effects of varieties and storage duration on bulb weight loss percentage

Onion Varieties	Toppling at 70% neck fall with irrigation	Toppling at 70% neck fall, without irrigation	Toppling at 90% neck fall	Control (un toppling, un irrigated): harvested at 70% maturity
Russet	3.54fgh	4.18defgh	3.25h	5.193cd
Jambar	3.57efgh	3.45fgh	3.36gh	4.56def
Red Coach	5.34cd	5.29cd	3.8efgh	4.81cde
Bombay Red	6.75b	5.75bc	4.52defg	8.21a
P-values	**			
LSD _{0.05}	1.17			
CV (%)	16.27			

Where; ** = highly significant at $p < 0.01$; means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; $LSD_{0.05}$ = Least significant difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation

Marketable bulb percentage

The percentage of marketable bulbs was influenced ($P < 0.001$) by main effects of variety, storage duration and pre-harvest treatment and the interactions of variety x pre-harvest treatments. Whereas the interaction between variety x storage duration, pre-harvest treatment x storage period and variety x pre-harvest treatment x storage duration did not influence this parameter (Appendix Table 7.1).

Among onion varieties, Russet and Jambar maintained the highest (74.9% and 73.98%) marketable bulb respectively throughout the storage duration. On the other hand, the lowest marketable bulb (62.31%) was observed from variety Bombay Red (Figure 7.7). Among the pre-harvest treatments Toppling at 90% neck fall resulted in the highest marketable bulb percentage (77.96%), whereas control conditions (Un-toppled, Un-irrigated and 70% neckfall without toppling + irrigation) consistently showed lower marketable bulb percentages (64.53% and 66.03%) respectively (Figure 7.7).

The interaction effect result indicates that toppling at 90% neck fall generally resulted in the highest marketable bulb percentages across all varieties, with Jambar (84.83%) and Russet (80.84%) showing the best performance. In contrast, the control treatment (untoppling, unirrigated, harvested at 70% neck fall) resulted in the lowest marketable bulb percentages, particularly for the Bombay Red variety (Table 7.5).

Sprouting, a crucial indicator of onion bulb marketability, began after four weeks of storage period and continued until the end of the three-month. The highest marketable bulbs from hybrid varieties like Jambar and Russet, compared to open pollinated variety Bombay Red throughout the storage duration can be due to the genetic makeup of the crop. The results of the present study underscore the importance of careful selection of onion varieties in reducing the postharvest losses of onion in storage. Onion can be generally stored for four weeks and above with relatively low postharvest losses if appropriate variety is used and appropriate toppling practices are implemented.

Figure 7.7. Main effects of varieties and pre-harvest treatments on marketable bulb percentage

Table 7 5. Interaction effects of variety and pre-harvest treatments on marketable bulb percentage

Onion Varieties	Toppling at 70% neck fall with irrigation	Toppling at 70% neck fall, without irrigation	Toppling at 90 % neck fall	Control (un toppling, un irrigation): harvested at 70% maturity
Russet	71.11d	77.40bc	80.94ab	70.3d
Jambar	69.25de	76.66c	84.81a	65.18f
Red Coach	74.44ef	69.25de	75.92c	69.25de
Bombay Red	57.7g	67.77def	70.37d	53.33h
P-values	***			
LSD (0.05)	3.54			
CV (%)	0.95			
SE±	1.02			

Where; *** = very highly significant at $p < 0.001$; ** = highly significant at $p < 0.01$; * = significant at $p < 0.05$; ns = non-significance means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; $LSD_{0.05}$ = Least significant difference at 5%; and CV = coefficient of variation

7.4. Conclusions and Recommendations

The results of the present study clearly showed that variety and pre-harvest treatment influenced the quality and shelf life of onion bulbs throughout the storage duration. Jambar and Russet varieties sprouted relatively late and recorded the lowest losses in bulb weight and decay percentage compared to Bombay Red and Red Coach varieties. Moreover, the bulbs of these varieties were relatively firm and recorded the highest proportion of marketable bulbs after three months of storage. Similarly, toppling of onion plants positively influenced the quality and shelf life of onion bulbs in storage while irrigation some days before harvesting negatively influenced these parameters. Bulbs from plants toppled at 90% neck fall sprouted late, showed reduced decay percentage and weight loss and were relatively firm and had relatively high total soluble solids and proportion of marketable bulbs in three months of storage. Selection of suitable onion variety and implementation of appropriate pre-harvest treatments is necessary to reduce the postharvest losses of onion bulbs in the storage. Based on the results of the present study, toppling and harvesting onion plants at 90% neck fall and the use of Jambar and Russet hybrid onion varieties help to store onion for four weeks in Defused Light Storage without a significant postharvest loss of bulbs, which can be recommended for Bahir Dar Zuria district and areas with similar agro-ecology. As the work is limited to one season and location, it is also recommended to repeat the study in multilocation and season.

Chapter 8: GENERAL SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS RECOMMENDATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

8.1. Summary/ Synthesis

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is a highly valuable bulb crop in the *Allium* genus of the Alliaceae family. However, its production faces challenges, such as a lack of improved cultivars, improper planting density, inappropriate agronomic practices, climatic fluctuations, poor handling, poor seed quality, and high postharvest losses, hindering the vegetable sector, particularly onion cultivation. Improved varieties, proper plant density and soil fertility management practices, as well as correct postharvest handling practices, irrigation management, stages of maturity, and toppling of onion plants before harvesting, significantly to increase onion productivity, shelf-life, and postharvest quality. The studies aimed to understand farmers' knowledge, and management practices, identifying major constraints in the onion supply chains in in northwestern Ethiopia. Additionally, this study aimed to enhance agronomic practices and packaging materials, pre-harvest treatment for prolonged shelf life and quality by investigating the effects of variables such as onion variety, plant density, and nitrogen fertilizer rates on the growth, yield, and quality attributes of onion. Furthermore, this study aimed to identify appropriate pre-harvest treatments/practices for prolonging the shelf-life and quality of hybrid onion varieties. A survey study and field experiments were conducted in North Mecha (Koga), Bahir Dar Zuria (Woramit), and Fogera (Woreta) districts. The experiments were conducted using a factorial arrangement laid out in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications. Measurements of onion growth, yield, and postharvest quality parameters were taken at the physiological maturity stage and harvesting time.

8.2. Conclusions

Onion production and marketing in North Mecha (Koga), Bahir Dar Zuria (Woramit), and Fogera (Woreta) districts were dominated by adults and large household sizes, which significantly influenced the production quantity and handling of onion. Inadequate input

supplies, high costs, long lead times, limited farmer involvement in demand estimation, mismatches in input quantities, and high post-harvest losses are challenges faced onion produces. Six alternative onion marketing channels were identified where farmers, local collectors, brokers, transporters, wholesalers, retailers, and consumers were the main chain actors.

Experimental results indicate that the growth, yield and postharvest quality of onion bulbs were influenced by the main effects of planting density, nitrogen fertilizer, and onion varieties across three locations. The highest bulb diameter, bulb weight, total bulb yield (t ha^{-1}), and marketable bulb yield (t ha^{-1}) were recorded from the Russet, Jambar, and Red Coach varieties when nitrogen fertilizer was applied at 82 kg ha^{-1} . Onion plants supplied with 82 kg N ha^{-1} produced the highest marketable bulb yields of 26.77 t ha^{-1} , with Jambar and Russet providing the greatest net benefit. Furthermore, a plant density of $666,666 \text{ plants ha}^{-1}$ (spacing of $5 \text{ cm} \times 20 \text{ cm} \times 40 \text{ cm}$ for plants, rows, and double rows, respectively) resulted in the highest marketable bulb yield of 28.42 t ha^{-1} .

Onion postharvest quality is influenced by packaging materials, nitrogen fertilizer, and variety across locations. Proper handling allows onion bulbs to be stored for one month, irrespective of packaging materials or production location. Variety Jambar and Russet bulbs stored on shelves and nitrogen fertilizer rate (82 kg ha^{-1}) took the longest date to begin sprouting, low percentage of decay, highest percentage of marketable, low loss in weight bulbs and better firmness. The highest storage loss (higher percentage of sprouting, decay, weight loss, and lower marketable bulbs) of onion was observed from Bombay Red variety followed by Red Coach. The longer shelf life was observed in the Jambar and Russet variety stored on shelves. varietal selection, proper storage practices, and nutrient management are vital in maintaining onion quality, extending shelf life, to mitigate postharvest losses and ensuring sustainable onion supply.

Varietal selection, proper storage practices, and implementation of appropriate pre-harvest treatments are vital in maintaining onion quality, extending shelf life, mitigating postharvest losses, and ensuring sustainable onion supply. Using hybrid onion varieties like Jambar and Russet, as well as practicing topping at 90% maturity reduced the percentage of decay and

weight loss and sprouting, prolonged the shelf life and increased the proportion of marketable bulbs in storage, while using open-pollinated (Bombay Red) variety and topping at 70% maturity followed by irrigation increased sprouting, decay, and, weight loss and reduced bulb firmness and the proportion of marketable bulbs.

8.3. Recommendations

Comprehensive tailored trainings for stakeholders across the supply chain on the management and handling practices of onion coupled with the improvement of infrastructures are recommended to enhance the production and productivity and reduce the postharvest losses of onion. Furthermore, strengthening marketing cooperatives working on onion postharvest handling and marketing systems is quit necessary to ensure continuous supply of the crop to the market. Thus, meaningful interventions in the development and implementation of policy on sustainable production, handling practices, and supply of onion should be designed.

The study also recommends the use of hybrid onion varieties like Russet and Jambar at the spacing 5 cm between plants 10 cm between rows and 40 cm between double rows (666,666 plants ha⁻¹) to improve the productivity of onion in the Mecha, Bahir Dar Zuria, and Fogera districts and areas with similar agro-ecology. Moreover, the growing of Jambar and Russet varieties and the application of 82 kg ha⁻¹ nitrogen fertilizer are recommended for the economical production of onions in Mecha, Bahir Dar Zuria, and Fogera districts with similar agroecology.

The selection of suitable varieties, application of optimal nitrogen fertilizer rates, and use of proper packaging materials are crucial to reducing postharvest losses, increasing the proportion of marketable bulbs, and extending the shelf life of onion bulbs. Accordingly, using Russet and Jambar varieties and storing bulbs on shelves constructed from locally available materials are recommended to maintain the quality and reduce the postharvest losses of onion in storage and thus to enhance the economic benefit and food security of onion growers. Similarly, adoption of agronomic practices like topping at 90% neck fall of onion plants combined with the use of Jambar and Russet hybrid onion varieties are recommended to maintain the quality and minimize the postharvest losses of onion bulbs in the storage, thereby to ensure food security of farmers

and economic sustainability of onion production. These recommendations collectively underscore the requirement of multifaceted approach to optimize onion production, handling, and storage practices, thereby ultimately ensuring the benefits of producers, traders, and consumers.

8.4. Future Research Directions

The present study provides valuable insights into a holistic approach that integrates key factors affecting both onion production and postharvest losses. Building upon this foundation, several avenues for future research are suggested to further enhance onion cultivation and postharvest management. The following suggestions are forwarded to further enhance the onion cultivation and postharvest management.

1. Studying the evaluation of additional hybrid onion varieties and optimization of phosphorous fertilizer in the study area for maximizing crop productivity.
2. This study represents a pioneering effort in the area, future research could focus on evaluating various hybrid onion varieties combined with higher plant densities to optimize yield and quality onion bulbs.
3. It is also advisable to consider the evaluation of different storage structures and storage environments in multiple locations and seasons to validate findings under diverse agro-climatic conditions.

These future research directions hold significant promise for advancing onion production and postharvest management, ultimately contributing to improved agricultural practices and food security.

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1. Vegetable production only
 2. Cereals production
 3. Livestock production
 4. Mixed
 5. Other sources _____
4. Comparative income source from vegetables?
 1. Onion
 2. Tomato
 3. Potato
 4. Cabbage
 5. Pepper
 6. _____
 5. Total land holding of the household? _____ ha
 6. Area/land covered by onion? _____ ha
 7. Amount harvested from land covered? _____ Q
 8. Means of land acquisitions
 1. Owned
 2. Gift
 3. Family
 4. Rented
 5. Inherited
 9. How many times per year you produce onion?
 1. Once
 2. Twice
 3. Other (specify) _____
 10. At what stage you transplant your seedlings?
 11. Did you trim your seedlings?
 1. Yes
 2. No
 - 10.1. If yes at what stage and why? _____
 12. What is the planting distance you use? _____ cm between irrigation furrows _____ cm between plants and _____ cm between rows
 13. Did you use irrigation?
 1. Yes
 2. No
 14. How frequent do you irrigate your onion? _____ times/week
 15. Do you have sufficient source of water for irrigation?
 1. Yes
 2. No
 - 14.1. If yes, what is the source for irrigation you most frequently use? Name of the river or pond _____
 - 14.2. If not, what are the reasons behind? _____
 16. How many times do you produce onion per annual by using irrigation?
 1. Once
 2. Twice
 3. Other (specify) _____
 17. What are the problems frequently you encounter in relation with use of irrigation? _____

III - Questions on access for production inputs

Hybrid seed varieties supply

18. Have you ever grown hybrid onion seed varieties?
 1. Yes
 2. No
 - 17.1. If yes, for how long _____ and name of cultivars _____

No.	Name of hybrid Varieties	Years of 1 st grown	Under production or stopped	When stopped, production	Reasons for left prodn. High seed cost, unavailability of seeds, lack of, others...

- 17.2. If no why?
 1. Shortage of capital to purchase
 2. Lack of water pumps
 3. Lack of extension advice
 4. High cost of production
 5. Lack of experience
 6. Others (specify) _____
19. Which hybrid onion variety you prefer? _____
 - 18.1. Reasons for preference
 1. Better yield advantage
 2. Long period of storage
 3. Higher market demand
 4. Easy accessibility
 5. Low cost of purchase
 6. Other (Specify)

20. Do you have sufficient access for hybrid seed varieties? 1. Yes 2.No

19.1. If yes, who are your sources of hybrid onion seed variety?

Source of hybrid seed supply	Way of getting seeds through	Remark
1. Market	1. Purchase	1.
2. MoA/BoA	2. On credit base	2.
3. Research centers	3. Gift	3.
4. NGOs	4. Exchange	4.
5. Others (specify)	5. Other(specify)	5.

19.2. If No for Q.17, what is the reason behind?

1. Cash shortage 3. Being too expensive 5. Lack of knowledge
2. Absence of credit access 4. other (specify)_____

Fertilizer and pesticide supply

21. Do you use fertilize in onion farm? 1. Yes 2. No

20.1. If yes, what type of fertilizer do you use?

1. DAP 2. NPS/B 3. Urea 4. Organic 5. Other, specify _____

20.2. What is the amount of fertilizer you applied to produce onion? kg/ha

1. DAP_____ 2. NPS/B_____ 3. Urea_____ 4. Organic_____ 5. Other,

22. Method and time of your fertilizer application? _____

23. Which of the following inputs do you frequently use for onion production?

No	Types of	Name	Sources (Local market, MoA/BoA, Research centers, NGO, Cooperative, Other Source)	Quantity used(kg/ha)	Remark
1.	Fertilizer	1. DAP	1. .	1.	1.
		2. UREA	2.	2.	2.
		3. NPS/B	3.	3.	3.
2.	Pesticide	1. Herbicide	4.	4.	4.
		2. Fungicide		5.	5.

24. Do you properly apply the recommended fertilizer rate? 1. Yes 2. No

23.1. If no why? _____

25. What factors you face on recommended rate fertilizer and pesticide application? _____

26. How do you see the above inputs purchase cost for onion production?

Inputs	Price situation				
	Very expensive	Expensive	Medium	Less expensive	Not expensive
Hybrid seeds					
Fertilizer					
Pesticide					
Others					

27. Do you get fertilizer timely and adequately? 1. Yes 2. No

26.1. If no, why?

1. Cash shortage 2. High cost purchase 3. Lack of knowledge 4. Other (Specify)_____

26.2. What are your alternatives to solve this problem? _____

Production

28. Do you face any constraints in onion production? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____

27.1 If yes explain major onion production constraints by rank

Constraints	Rank	Alterative solution taken
1.		
2.		
3.		
4.		

29. How is the production trend of the volume of onion production for the past five years (qt/ha)? 1. Increasing 2. Decreasing

Production costs

30. Indicate the average costs you incur for each production cost components and rate them in their descending order

Production cost components	Average cost incurred	Remark
1. Cost of fertilizer		
2. Cost of seeds		
3. Cost of chemicals (fungicides, herbicides, pesticides)		
4. Cost of fuel for water pumps(irrigation)		
5. Land preparation		
6. Sawing and transplanting		
7. Cultivation		
8. Harvesting		
9. Labour		

Disease and Insect pest

31. What kind of disease protection chemicals is used?

32. Do you use safety clothes during chemical spraying?

Price

33. What was the market price of onion per quintal at its pick harvesting season in 2013? _____

34. What was the market price of onion per quintal at its off season (summer) in 2013? _____

35. How do you evaluate the price you received for two seasons comparatively?

1. Increasing 2. Decreasing

31.1.If the price is increasing, are you benefited from the increased price?

1.Yes 2. No

31.2. If no why? _____

36. Who decides your selling price? 1. Yourself 2 Buyers 3. Brokers 4 Market demand and supply 5. By negotiation 6. Others (specify) _____

37. What do you expect about the marketing problems with regard to onion price?

1. Low selling price 2. High input price 3. Exploitation by middle men 4. Inaccessibility of market (long distance) 5. Other (specify)

38. Are there brokers in your nearest area? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____

39. What is their role for you with regard to selling price? _____.

40. What are the problems created by brokers with regard to onion market?

1. Took to limited client 2. Charged high brokerage 3. Cheating scaling (weighing)

4. Wrong price (market) information 5. Others (specify) _____

Access to credit

41. Did you buy farm inputs in cash? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____
 42. If no, what was the reason?
 1. Lack of cash 2. Lack of access for credit 3. Bureaucracy 4. Other (specify) _____
 43. Have you ever received credit? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____

IV. Questions on Harvesting and Post-harvest handling

44. What is (are) your criterion to harvest onion? 1. Maturity 2. Market price 3. Other factors (mention) _____
 45. At what stage do you harvest onion? _____
 46. At what time of the day do you harvest onion?
 1. Morning 2. Afternoon 3. Evening 4. Any time
 47. For how long you cure onion bulbs? _____
 48. What practice you apply before harvesting? _____
 Why? _____
 49. When does you remove the top of the bulb?
 1. Before harvesting 2. Immediately after harvesting 3. Others (number of days from harvesting) _____
 50. What type of harvesting method you are practicing?
 1 Pulling by hand 2. Digging by hoe 3. Others
 51. How far is your farm from the local market? _____ walking minutes.
 52. How do you transport onion bulbs to the market?
 1. Using animal driven cart 2. Using men’s shoulder 3. Using women’s back 4. Others, specify _____
 53. How much produce are taking to the market? _____
 54. Do you face market problems with regard to onion price?
 55. What was the market price of onion per quintal at its pick selling season in 2013E.C?

 56. Are you ever storing onion bulbs for late selling? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____
 55.1. If no why?
 1. Lack of long-time stored varieties 4. Lack of storage facility
 2. High cost of storage facilities 5. Lack of awareness on storage methods
 3. Immediate cash need 6. Other, specify _____
 55.2. If yes for how long you stored the bulbs? _____
 57. Is there any loss of onion after harvest? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____
 56.1. If yes? how many quintals of onion losses due to lack of storage last year (2013E.C)? _____
 56.2. Can you explain the main reasons for the post-harvest loss of onion? (rank them)

Causes for PHL	Rank	
1.		
2.		
3.		
4.		

5.		
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58. How much produce are taking to the market? _____
 57.1. What type of container you are using? _____
 57.2. By what means (transportation method)? _____
59. What type of storage/packaging material do use do you use for home consumption or late selling? 1. Jute/Burlap bag 2. Spread on ground 3. Shelf/alega 4. Others _____
60. Are you selling all the products you are harvested and are taking to the market / are there any loss? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____
 59.1. If no, why? 1. Disease 2. Small bulb size 3. Larger bulb size 4. Others (specify) _____
 59.2. If no, why? 1. Disease 2. Small bulb size 3. Larger bulb size 4. Others (specify) _____
 59.3. What will be the fate for the rest/unsold products? _____
61. For whom do you usually sell your onion?
 1. Collectors 2. Wholesalers 3. Cooperatives 4. Retailers 5. Consumers 6. Others (specify) _____
 60.1. Why do you prefer selling to this buyer? 1. Better price 2. Customers 3. No quality discrimination 4. Large volume of purchase 5. Others(specify) _____
61. What are the reasons behind for reducing bulb quality?
 1. Improper production practices 3. Inefficient care during harvesting and transport
 2. Inadequate water resource 4. Immediate need for money 5. Others (specify) _____
62. What measures you are practicing to minimize loss after harvest? _____
63. Do you believe onion farming is a profitable venture? 1. Yes 2. No _____
64. If no, what problems do you think are the major constraints? List (by priority) _____
65. Have you ever taken trainings related to post-harvest handling of onion? 1. Yes 2. No _____
66. If yes for Q64; when did you take trainings? _____
67. Is there a cooperative for onion to collect harvest bulbs? 1. Yes 2. No _____
 67.1. If yes are you a member of cooperatives? 1. Yes 2. No _____
 67.2. If no are you interested to sell your onion through cooperatives? 1. Yes 2. No _____

Information:

Access to market information (AMI)

68. How do you get information about buyers/ transporters? _____
69. How do you know what price to take for your onions? _____
70. Does the farmer pay to brokers? How do the broker and farmer find each other? _____
71. How does you know how much onion is planted? _____
721. How does the farmer find sellers of fertilizers and disease protection? _____

Part II- Interview with onion wholesalers

I. Socio-demographic characteristics

1. City _____
2. Age _____
3. Sex 1. Male _____ 0. Female _____
4. Educational level (years of formal schooling) _____

- 1. Illiterate
- 2. Read and write only
- 3. 1-6
- 4. 7-9
- 5. 10-12
- 6. higher education
- 7. College level (10+ or 12+)
- 5. Family size _____
- 6. Marital status 1. Married 2. Single 3. Widowed 4. Divorced

II

- 7. Experience in selling onion _____ years
- 8. How do you collect your onion bulbs? 1. Through brokers 2. Collect from farm (Own) 3. Farmers delivers to you 4. Others _____
- 9. Do you get and evaluate samples of the onions before buying them?
- 10. Do you face quality problems from suppliers? 1. Yes ____ 2 No ____
- 10.1. If yes, what are the problems? 1. Type of variety 2. Drying problem 3. Bulb size 4. Disease 5. Others, specify _____

Reason	Rank	
1. Variety type		
2. Improper maturity		
3. Bruising		
4. Bulb size		
5. Rotting		
6. Sprouting		
7. Shrivelling		

- 11. On average, what amount of onion bulbs you bought from suppliers at a time? _____ qt; what amount of it will be sold? _____ qt.
- 12. Do you sell all you bought? 1. Yes ____ 2. No ____
- 12.1. If no, what are the reasons? 1. Poor quality 2. Reduced market demand 3. Others, specify _____
- 12.2. Are there any storage possibilities for onions at the market? 1. Yes ____ 2. No ____
Method of storage _____ and For how long? _____
- 13. What is the total estimated percentage of bulbs which are not-suitable for market? ____%
- 14. What do you do with bulbs rejected due to poor quality? 1. Sell with reduced price 2. Used for own consumption 3. Discard 4. Others _____
- 15. If onion is to be sold with discount price, by what amount will the price be reduced? _____ birr
- 16. If onion is to be discarded, what do you do with it? 1. Manure 2. Cattle feed 3. Thrown to garbage tanks 4. Others specify _____
- 17. What are the reasons behind for unsuitability for market? Rank in their order of importance.

Reason	Rank	
1. Variety type		
2. Immaturity		
3. Poor handling		
4. Poor packaging material		
5. Poor transportation		

6. Absence of suitable storage conditions		
7. Others (specify)		

18. What measures do you undertake to reduce the amount of rejected bulbs? _____
19. Do you have any suggestions to minimize the amount of rejected bulbs?
20. How many days does it take to finish selling your onion bulbs? _____ days
21. At what date interval do you buy new onion from suppliers? _____ days
22. How do you store bulbs for selling? 1. Inside jute bag 2. Heaping on the floor 3. Spreading on the shelf 4. Others (specify) _____
23. Is there any loss at storage? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____
24. What are the causes for loss? Rank _____
25. For whom do you usually sell your onion? 1. Restaurants, 2. Retailers 3. Consumers 4. All
26. How much is you sold for each customers?
 1. Resturants _____ 2. Retailers _____ 3. Consumers _____ 4. I don't know _____
 5. Varies every day _____
2. Do you face in supply shortage of onion bulbs in any of the seasons? 1. Yes 2. No
3. If yes, at which season of the year? _____; what are the reasons? _____
4. Is the demand for onion is seasonal? 1. Yes 2. No
5. If yes, when does the demand rises? (months of the year) _____; what are the reasons? _____
6. When does the demand fall? (months of the year) _____
7. What are the reasons for the fall in demand? _____
8. Is there a price variation for bulbs you sell? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____
9. If yes, when does the price rises? (months of the year) _____
10. What are the reasons for the rise in price? _____
11. Have you benefited from rise in price? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____
12. When does the price falls? (months of the year) _____
13. What are the reasons for the fall in price? _____
14. What type of packaging material do you use for the transport of onion to market?
 1. Plastic crates 2. Unpacked 3. Wooden-box 4. Sacks 5. Baskets 6. Others
15. What type of transportation /trucks you are using? 1. Open vehicle 2. Closed vehicle 3. Human (labor) 4. Others
16. How much onion can one truck carry? _____
17. Is there any loss during transportation? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____
 - 22.1. If yes causes for loss? _____
 - 22.2. Amount of actual losses at the market per week/Extent of losses? Per week
(Can for example be rotten onions, old onions, dry onion peel
_____)

Avg. quantity purchased in Qt	Avg. quantity sold Qt	Grading loss kg	Storage loss kg	Transportation loss kg	Selling loss kg	

18. What measures are you taking to minimize the losses during transportation, storage and selling? _____
19. Do you have contact with farmers? 1. Yes have direct contact 2. No direct contact with farmers, all contact goes through brokers 3. Sometimes direct contact with farmers but usually through a broker
20. What onion-varieties you bought? _____
21. Do different buyers pay different prices? _____
22. At what time you transport from the farm to you? _____
23. If the onion bulbs are damaged during the transportation, what is the most common cause _____

Information

24. How does the wholesaler find trucks for the onion transportation? _____
25. Any contact with the farmers? _____

Part III- Interview with onion retailers

I. Socio Demographic characteristics

1. City _____
2. Age _____
3. Sex 1. Male _____ 0. Female _____
4. Educational level (years of formal schooling)
 1. Illiterate
 2. Read and write only
 3. 1-6
 4. 7-9
 5. 10-12
 6. College level (10+ or 12+)
 7. higher education
5. Family size _____
6. Marital status 1. Married 2. Single 3. Widowed 4. Divorced

II

7. Experience in selling onion _____ years
8. Who is the source of your onion bulbs?
 1. Local retailers
 2. Collect from farm (Own)
 3. Farmers delivers to you
 4. others _____
9. Do you face quality problems from suppliers? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____
 - 9.1. If yes, what are the problems? 1. Drying problem 2. Bulb size 3. Disease 4. Others, specify _____
10. On average, what amount of onion bulbs you bought from suppliers at a time? _____ kg; what amount of it will be sold? _____ kg
11. Do you sell all you bought? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____

11.1. If no, what are the reasons? 1. Poor quality 2. Reduced market demand 3. Others, specify _____

12. If it is due to poor quality of the bulb, what is the reason? Rank in their order of importance based on their contribution to rejection:

Reason	Rank	
1. Variety type		
2. Improper maturity		
3. Bruising		
4. Bulb size		
5. Rotting		
6. Sprouting		
7. Shrivelling		

13. What is the total estimated percentage of bulbs which are not-suitable for market? ___%

14. What do you do with bulbs rejected due to poor quality? 1. Sell with reduced price 2. Used for own consumption 3. Discard 4. Others _____

15. If onion is to be sold with discount price, by what amount will the price be reduced? ___birr

16. If onion is to be discarded, what do you do with it? 1. Manure 2. Cattle feed 3. Thrown to garbage tanks 4. Others specify _____

17. What are the reasons behind for unsuitability for market? Rank in their order of importance.

Reason	Rank	
1. Improper maturity		
2. Poor handling		
3. Poor packaging material		
4. Poor transportation		
5. Absence of suitable storage conditions		
6. Others (specify)		

18. What measures do you undertake to reduce the amount of rejected bulbs?

19. Do you have any suggestions to minimize the amount of rejected bulbs?

20. How many days does it take to finish selling your onion bulbs? _____ days

21. At what date interval do you buy new onion from suppliers? _____ days

22. How do you store bulbs for selling? 1. Inside crate 2. Heaping on the floor 3. Spreading on the shelf 4. Others (specify) _____

23. Is there any loss at storage? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____

24. What are the causes for loss? Rank _____

25. For whom do you usually sell your onion? _____

26. Do you face in supply shortage of onion bulbs in any of the seasons? 1. Yes 2. No

27. If yes, at which season of the year? _____; what are the reasons? _____

28. Is there a price variation for bulbs you sell? 1. Yes 2. No

29. If yes, when does the price rises? (months of the year) _____

30. What are the reasons for the rise in price? _____
31. When does the price falls? (months of the year) _____
32. What are the reasons for the fall in price? _____
33. What type of packaging material do you use for the movement of fruits and vegetables to market? 1. Plastic crates 2. Unpacked 3. Wooden-box 4. Sacks 5. Baskets 6. Others
34. What type of transportation you are using? 1. Open vehicle 2. Closed vehicle 3. Human (labor) 4. Others
35. Is there any loss during transportation? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____
- 35.1 If yes causes for loss? _____
- 35.2. Extent of losses? _____

Avg. quantity purchased	Avg. quantity sold	Grading loss	Storage loss	Transportation loss	Selling loss	

36. What measures are you taking to minimize the losses during transportation, storage and selling?
37. Observations:

Part IV- Interview with local consumer

I. Socio Demographic characteristics

1. City _____
2. Age _____
3. Sex 1. Male _____ 0. Female _____
4. Educational level (years of formal schooling)
1. Illiterate 3. 1-6 5. 10-12
2. Read and write only 4. 7-9 7. Higher education
6. College level (10+ or 12+)
5. Family size _____
6. Marital status 1. Married 2. Single 3. Widowed 4. Divorced

II

7. Do you face quality problems from suppliers? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____
- 7.1. If yes, what are the problems? 1. Drying problem 2. Bulb size 3. Bulb skin color 4. variety type 5. Disease 6. Others, specify _____
8. On average, what amount of onion bulbs you bought from the market at a time? _____ kg;
9. Do you use all you bought without loss? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____
- 14.1 If no, what are the reasons? 1. Rotting 2. Sprouting 3. Bruising, 4. Others, specify _____
- 14.2. If yes, what mechanism to use to reduce loss of onion during storage

Mechanism	Rank	

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10. What is the total estimated percentage of bulbs which lost/not utilized every week from you bought? _____%
11. How long you store onion bulbs?
12. How do you store onion bulbs for consumption?
13. What was the market price of onion per quintal at its pick selling season in 2013E.C?
14. What was the market price of onion per quintal at its off/summer selling season in 2013E.C? _____
15. From where do you buy onions and why do you buy onions from that certain place?
16. Is it hard to find onions? _____
17. Do you ever buy too much or too little amount of onions? How often and how much?

Part I- Interview with onion cooperative union leader

1. Region _____ Zone _____ Woreda _____ Kebele _____
2. Name of the cooperatives _____
3. Members small-scale farmers _____
4. Year of establishment _____
5. Could you tell me about your working guidelines? _____
6. Do have sufficient input/onion? _____
7. What are your criteria to receive the commodity/onion? _____
8. How much produce do you receive daily, weekly? _____
9. Do you sell the whole product you receive? _____ How much on onion bulb will be lost? _____
10. Do you have sufficient space to store your received commodities? _____
11. For whom do you sell your produce/who are your customers? _____
12. Are your members are experiencing postharvest loss reduction technologies? What are they? _____
13. What are your major challenges? _____

Part VI: Interviews with Key informants

1. Please introduce yourself and briefly describe your role in the onion industry.
2. How long have you been involved in onion production and distribution?
3. What are the main challenges faced by onion farmers during the cultivation process?
4. What are the key steps involved in post-harvest handling of onions?
5. Are there specific technologies or practices used to minimize post-harvest losses in your area?
6. What challenges do onion producers encounter during post-harvest handling, and how are these addressed?

7. Can you outline the key stages of the onion supply chain from production to consumption?
8. Who are the primary actors or stakeholders involved in each stage of the onion supply chain?
9. How do onions move through the supply chain, from farms to markets or distribution centers?
10. What factors contribute to post-harvest losses along the onion supply chain?
11. Are there particular stages of the supply chain where losses are more prevalent?
12. How do you quantify or measure post-harvest losses in the onion industry?
13. What are the main challenges faced in reducing post-harvest losses in the onion supply chain?
14. Are there any innovative solutions or initiatives aimed at addressing post-harvest losses?
15. What are some common challenges experienced by onion producers and traders?
16. How can stakeholders collaborate to address the challenges identified and improve the onion supply chain?

APPENDIX TABLE

Appendix Table 3.2.1. Authors contribution

Contribution	Authors	Description
Supply chain dynamics, stakeholder roles, and constraints in onion production and marketing.	Insights from <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Gallo <i>et al.</i> (2007), ▪ Van der Vorst <i>et al.</i> (2007), ▪ FAO (2018), ▪ Mira <i>et al.</i> (2002) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The study synthesizes and builds upon existing literature, integrate insights from), and other scholars to provide a comprehensive understanding of supply chain management in agriculture.
Stakeholder Analysis	Based on insights from <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Minnens <i>et al.</i> (2019) ▪ Adamashvili <i>et al.</i> (2021) and ▪ WCDI (2021). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Conducted an in-depth examination of supply chain actors and their roles ▪ Identified and analyzed contributions of various stakeholders, including input suppliers, producers, collectors, wholesalers, retailers, consumers, and support entities, elucidating complex interactions within the onion supply chain.
Constraints Identification	Sources including <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ BoFED (2003) ▪ Lemma Dessalegn and Shimelis Aklilu (2003) ▪ Esheteu Bekele <i>et al.</i> (2006) ▪ Kumilachew Alamerie <i>et al.</i> (2014) ▪ Berhanu Gebremedhin <i>et al.</i> (2009) ▪ Melkamu Alemayehu <i>et al.</i> (2015) ▪ Agumas Yideg (2019) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Identified key constraints affecting onion production in Ethiopia. ▪ Analysis covers challenges related to soil fertility, post-harvest technologies, agronomic practices, fertilizer and pesticide access, and market integration.

Marketing Channels Analysis	<p>Sources from</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Kohls and Uhl (1985) ▪ Emana Bezabih <i>et al.</i> (2017) ▪ Kassa Getu and Ahmed Ibrahim (2018) ▪ Addisu Hailu <i>et al.</i> (2017) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Investigated into marketing channels of onions based on insights and other researchers. ▪ Explored diverse routes through which onions move from producers to consumers, highlighting prevalence of direct sales, wholesaler-driven channels, and role of cooperatives. ▪ By examining marketing landscape, provided valuable insights into market access and distribution strategies.
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Source: own analysis based on literatures

Appendix Table 4.1. Mean squares and significance levels for onion traits tested

Traits	Block(L)	Variety (Var)	Nitrogen(N)	Var*N
df	6	3	3	9
DPM	53.63ns	1143.00***	125.5**	7.58ns
PH	95.67**	51.433*	186.387***	6.382ns
LNPP	1.54ns	11.75***	5.20**	0.12ns
BD	20.88ns	78.25**	1084.97***	75.99ns
AVBW	428.92**	1178.36***	3080.09***	58.89ns
TYTH	21.12ns	297.16***	373.20***	4.32ns
UMYP	0.03ns	0.15***	0.096***	0.013ns
MYTH	6.75**	5.33**	0.64*	1.08ns
TSS	0.02ns	116.46***	8.17***	2.49**
Pungency	0.73ns	38.28***	0.72**	0.006ns

L=location, df=degrees of freedom, DPM = days to physiological maturity, PH = plant height, LNPP = leaf number per plant, BD = bulb diameter, AVBW = average bulb weight, TYTH = total yield ton per hectare, UMYP = unmarketable yield percentage, MYTH = marketable yield ton per hectare and TSS = total soluble solids; ***= $p < 0.001$; ** = $P < 0.01$; and $Ns = P > 0.05$. Means followed by the same letter within the same column are not significantly different at 5% probability level

Appendix Table 5.1. Mean squares and significance level for onion traits tested

Traits	Source of variation					
	Block (L)	Variety (V)	Density	V*D	Error	R ²
Df	6	3	2	6	70	
Days to physiological maturity	14.73ns	592.50***	4.92*	5.71ns	36.65	0.53
Plant height	108.58***	116.83***	129.04***	10.74ns	8.17	0.81
Leaf number plant ⁻¹	0.59ns	11.47***	27.96***	0.16ns	0.649	0.73
Leaf diameter	0.52ns	24.08***	10.05**	1.72ns	1.65	0.71
Bulb neck diameter	0.49ns	29.47***	10.71**	3.44ns	2.618	0.56
Bulb diameter	303.46**	168.18**	241.23**	22.19ns	38.16	0.48
Average bulb weight	219.7ns	1905.61***	2597.55***	170.95ns	158.83	0.64
Harvest index	62.13ns	273.29**	50.32ns	17.51ns	35.98	0.46
Small bulb percentage	192.92ns	1426.91***	2982.02***	230.11ns	135.73	0.75
Medium bulb percentage	186.68ns	135.41ns	709.74**	380.92**	159.65	0.46
Large bulb percentage	285.77ns	1771.88***	4521.23***	355.05*	233.07	0.7
Total yield t ha ⁻¹	123.80*	479.48***	628.09***	34.20ns	50.58	0.57
Marketable bulb yield tha ⁻¹	127.15*	492.03***	615.71***	34.30ns	57.69	0.53
Unmarketable bulb yield percentage	1.47**	8.860***	0.09ns	0.18ns	0.20	0.57
Total Soluble Solids	0.46ns	64.77***	6.94***	1.75***	0.25	0.95
Firmness	0.007ns	4.31***	1.23***	1.90***	0.24	0.98

Where; *** = very highly significant at $p < 0.001$; ** = highly significant at $p < 0.01$; * = significant at $p < 0.05$; ns = non-significance means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different

Appendix Table 6.1. Mean square values and significance level for post-harvest quality traits of onion

Source of variation	Block	Variety (Var)	Nitrogen(N)	Packaging material (PKM)	Var*N	STM*N	PKM *Var	Var*N*PK M	Error	R ²	CV(%)
Degree of freedom	2	3	3	2	9	6	6	18	286		
Days to first sprouting	40.55ns	31106.15***	319.36**	332.34**	56.15ns	33.30ns	21.55ns	54.82ns	55.08	0.87	12.1
Number of bulbs sprouted	7.59ns	361.58***	6.05ns	21.67**	23.09**	6.74ns	7.63ns	7.42ns	6.56	0.54	25.15
Sprouting (%)	448.84ns	11606.84***	42.16ns	909.10**	465.52ns	153.77ns	362.11ns	271.64ns	222.96	0.53	26.01
Decay (%)	207.66***	143.57***	2.43*	1403.33***	3.03ns	0.93ns	28.49**	1.48ns	5.96	0.7	29.95
Marketable bulbs(%)	10564.97** *	17.32***	1805.87**	298.91ns	189.89*	758.81ns	468.97**	82.13ns	37.69	0.57	25.47
Weight loss (%)	188.15**	858.57***	8120.09**	243.29**	9.67ns	21.64ns	46.08ns	36.24ns	45.25	0.57	22.78
TSS	0.002ns	135.44	5.73***	12.24**	2.56**	1.87**	3.57**	4.40**	0.001	0.98	1.49
Firmness	0.05ns	14.67***	15.20***	4.16***	2.90***	2.03***	1.33***	1.41***	0.03	0.98	2.36

Where; ***= very highly significant at $P < 0.0001$; **highly significant at $p < 0.001$; *, significant at $p < 0.01$; Ns = non-significant at $P > 0.05$ and DF = Degree of freedom

Appendix Table 7.1. Mean square values and significance level for post-harvest quality traits of onion

Source of Variation	DF	Sprouting percentage	Decay percentage	Total soluble solid	Firmness	Weight loss percentage	Marketable bulb percentage
Replication	2	113.27**	37.34**	1.13Ns	5.03**	6.10**	65.35**
Varieties (VAR	3	587.11***	499.25***	90.85***	11.96***	47.63***	1183.02***
Pre-harvest treatment (PRHT)	3	1183.41***	456.66***	7.26**	19.14***	22.82***	1396.81***
Storage duration (STD)	2	7759.79***	3677.39***	51.02**	79.87***	168.87***	5751.00***
VAR*PRHT	9	63.86***	69.07***	14.7***	1.66*	4.28**	82.68***
VAR*STD	6	58.25**	26.56**	1.90ns	0.04ns	3.091ns	34.02**
PRHT*STD	6	86.34***	18.23*	0.3ns	0.11ns	1.11ns	18.80ns
VAR*PRHT*STD	18	6.19ns	7.60ns	0.38 ns	0.03ns	0.974ns	13.21ns
CV(%)		16.11	15.4	0.74	11.27	16.27	0.94

Where; *** = very highly significant at $P < 0.001$; * = significant at $P < 0.05$; ns = non-significant and DF = Degree of freedom

APPENDIX FIGURE

Appendix Figure 2.1. Onion seedling at nursery

Appendix Figure 2.2. Transplanting

Appendix Figure 2.3. Data collection in field

Appendix Figure 2.4. Field performance

Appendix Figure 2.5. Harvested bulb yield

Appendix Figure 2.6. Data collection on quality parameters

Appendix Figure 2.7. Field supervision

Appendix Figure 2.8. Stored onion bulbs

Appendix Figure 3.1.1. Field observation on onion production practices in the study area

Appendix Figure 3.1.2. Hybrid onion varieties (Jambar, Russet and Red Coach) under production in the study area

Appendix Figure 3.1.3. Farmers harvesting and post-harvest handling practices

Appendix Figure 3.1.4. Post-harvest handling practices by farmers

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Appendix Table 3.2.1. Value addition activities (a) Poorly managed onion farm and partially weeded onion farm. (b) Properly managed onion farm (c) Field curing practice (d) Packaging for transportation. (e). Marketing practices of onion bulbs

BIOGRAPHY OF THE AUTHOR

The author, Yebirzaf Yeshiwas, was born on November 18, 1989, at Banja district, Awi zone of Amhara Region. She attended her elementary school from 1994-2001 at Kidamaja primary school and she started her high school study in 2002 at Injibara Preparatory School and completed it in 2005.

Following her success in the Ethiopian School Leaving Certificate Examination (ESLCE), Yebirzaf Yeshiwas enrolled at Jimma University College of Agriculture and Veterinary Medicine (JUCAVM) in 2006. She attained her Bachelor of Science degree in Horticulture and graduated in 2008.

Soon after graduation, she employed at the Amhara Regional Agricultural Research Center (ARARI), specifically at the Adet Agricultural Research Center (AARC) from 2009 to 2010 and worked as of a junior researcher specializing in horticulture. Subsequently, Yebirzaf Yeshiwas seized the opportunity to pursue her postgraduate studies at Jimma University College of Agriculture and Veterinary Medicine, commencing in September 2010 and successfully completing her studies in October 2012, achieving a master's of science degree in Horticulture Sciences.

Upon earning her postgraduate degree, she commenced her tenure at Debre Markos University in 2012, where she served as a lecturer and assistant professor for eight years. During her tenure, she contributed significantly to academia, publishing more than fourteen peer-reviewed journals. In 2020, she transitioned to the School of Graduate Studies at Bahir Dar University, pursuing further postgraduate studies in Horticulture. Presently, Yebirzaf Yeshiwas is a candidate for the Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) degree in Horticulture at Bahir Dar University, College of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences.